

Excellent peripheries for a strong
European Research Area

D6.5 Monitoring and impact assessment report on EXPER activities v2

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Author(s)	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>Laura Gaspar Ramírez</td> <td>FCPCT</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tanausú J. Dávila</td> <td>FCPCT</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Víctor Martínez</td> <td>CE</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Thor Rodríguez</td> <td>ATRINEO</td> </tr> </table>	Laura Gaspar Ramírez	FCPCT	Tanausú J. Dávila	FCPCT	Víctor Martínez	CE	Thor Rodríguez	ATRINEO
Laura Gaspar Ramírez	FCPCT								
Tanausú J. Dávila	FCPCT								
Víctor Martínez	CE								
Thor Rodríguez	ATRINEO								

Reviewers	Andrea Simeri	UNICAL
	Dayana Martín	ITC
	Alice Gervasoni	EMERGE
	Wieland Müller	UROS
	Juan Alberto Corbera	ULPGC

Acronyms & Abbreviations	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CBP	Capacity Building Plan
CE	Consulta Europa
CLAB	Contamination Laboratories
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
HEIs	Higher Education Institution
IPM	Intellectual property management
IPR	Intellectual property rights
ITC	Technological Institute of the Canary Islands
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
ORs	Outermost regions
RP	Reporting period
RTTP	Registered Technology Transfer Professional
SCWG	Societal challenges working groups
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
UAc	University of the Azores

ULPGC	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
UNICAL	University of Calabria
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the core objective of the EXPER project is to promote the institutional transformation of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) and the University of the Azores (UAc). This process has been guided by targeted capacity-building actions and strategic international collaboration with leading institutions, namely the University of Rostock (Germany) and the University of Calabria (Italy).

The initial monitoring report, delivered as *D6.2 Monitoring and impact assessment report on EXPER activities v1*, covered activities carried out between October 2022 and September 2023. Building upon that first assessment, this final report provides a comprehensive overview of the entire EXPER project, encompassing both previously reported actions and those implemented during the final eighteen months (October 2023 – March 2025). During this period, the consortium has concentrated its efforts on advancing the implementation of key actions across three central Work Packages (WPs), which constitute the operational backbone of the EXPER project:

WP3: Attracting and Retaining Talent – This work package has focused on enhancing the professional conditions for researchers by implementing concrete incentives, promoting gender equality, and developing targeted measures to mitigate brain drain in the Canary Islands and the Azores. Additionally, WP3 has led the design and rollout of an integrated entrepreneurial training program for students, inspired by the successful CLAB model developed at the University of Calabria (UNICAL), which has demonstrated strong replicability and impactful outcomes.

WP4: Promoting Excellence and Responsible Research – This work package has built upon the initial establishment of Societal Challenges Working Groups (SCWG) during the first reporting period, fostering structured collaboration among researchers in key areas such as Climate Change and the Blue and Circular Economy. Through initiatives such as online seminars, Summer Schools organised by ULPGC and UAc, and outreach event like “Investigafest”, WP4 has contributed to strengthening scientific excellence, enhancing interdisciplinary cooperation, and laying the groundwork for the formation of future European research consortia.

WP5: Connection with Business Environment – Knowledge Transfer and Spin-offs – This work package has focused on strengthening knowledge transfer process and building institutional capacity in technology transfer. It has delivered targeted training for researchers, administrative personnel, and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) professionals. In parallel, WP5 has supported the development of essential services such as patent roadmaps, consultancy schemes for spin-offs and start-ups, and the design of business plans for emerging ventures.

Furthermore, a key component of this deliverable is the *monitoring and impact assessment of the strategic actions outlined in the project's core planning instruments: the Action Plans and the Capacity Building Plans (CBP) developed for ULPGC and UAc.*

These documents, elaborated and validated in earlier stages of the project, include the following deliverables:

- D2.2 Action Plans Developed
- D4.1 Societal Challenges Working Groups and Thematic Action Plans
- D4.2 Capacity Building Plan and Report on Capacity Building Activities

The effective implementation of these Plans is critical, as the actions they contain are directly aligned with the overarching objectives of the EXPER project, particularly through the operational deployment of WP3, WP4, and WP5. Their execution has been systematically monitored through the assessment of predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), ensuring a results-oriented evaluation of progress and impact.

In summary, this deliverable offers an integrated assessment of the EXPER project's implementation, presenting a consolidated overview of all actions undertaken throughout its duration. It critically evaluates the extent to which these actions have contributed to institutional capacity building, scientific excellence, and knowledge transfer, thereby confirming the alignment of project outcomes with the strategic commitments established by the European Commission.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

This deliverable (D6.5) provides a comprehensive evaluation of the EXPER project's implementation across its full lifecycle. It builds upon the previous monitoring report (D6.2 Monitoring and Impact Assessment Report on EXPER Activities v1), which documented the activities executed during the project's first reporting period (October 2022 – September 2023).

The main objectives of this deliverable are as follows:

a. To provide a structured account of all project activities, divided into two reporting periods:

- Actions implemented between October 2022 and September 2023 (as reported in Deliverable D6.2).
- Actions executed from October 2023 to March 2025, representing the final implementation phase.

b. To assess the overall level of project implementation, focusing on task completion and alignment with the project's strategic objectives.

c. To conduct an in-depth monitoring of the implementation status of actions defined in key project deliverables:

 D2.2 Action Plans Developed

 D4.1 Societal Challenges Working Groups and Thematic Action Plans

 D4.2 Capacity Building Plan and Report on Capacity Building Activities

This evaluation is based on the systematic analysis of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) specified in each of the above plans.

By addressing the objectives outlined above, this report delivers a final and integrated assessment of the project's implementation and impact, ensuring both transparency and alignment with the strategic goals of the EXPER initiative.

The following table presents a comprehensive overview of the tasks carried out under the EXPER project, identifying the responsible partners and the respective reporting periods in which each task was implemented. While the previous monitoring report focused solely on the initial implementation phase (October 2022 to September 2023), this version encompasses the full duration of the project, including the second reporting period (October 2023 - March 2025). The table offers a structured representation of the project timeline, and highlights the key contributors responsible for driving task execution.

Table 1. Overview of Tasks Leaders and Reporting Periods (RPs) in the EXPER Project

WP No	Task	Task leader	RP
1	1.1 Methodology for assessment (M1-M3)	ATRINEO	1
	1.2 Widening Universities assessment (M3-M9)	ATRINEO	
	1.3 Assessment of surrounding ecosystems (M4-M9)	ULPGC	
	1.4 Good practices from leading universities (M6-M12)	UROS	
	1.5 Good practices from European universities alliances (M3-M12)	CE	
2	2.1 Stakeholder involvement and co-design methodology (M3-M6)	CE	1 & 2
	2.2 Creating a community-based vision of the University (M6-M10)	ULPGC	
	2.3 Developing a joint strategy (M10-M14)	ULPGC	
	2.4 Developing Action Plans (M14-M18)	ULPGC	
3	3.1 Implementing the HRS4R and improving framework conditions (M18-M30)	UNICAL	2

	3.2 Replicating the CLAB model (UNICAL) (M18-M30)	UNICAL	
	3.3 Ensuring gender equality and promoting diversity (M18-M30)	CE	
	3.4 Addressing brain drain (M18-M30)	EMERGE	
4	4.1 Establishment and coordination of “societal challenges working groups” (M12-M30)	ITC	
	4.2 Implementation of Societal Challenges Action Plans (M18-M30)	ITC	
	4.3 Transversal skills for excellent and responsible research (M18-M30)	ULPGC	
5	5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities	ATRINEO	
	5.2 Exchanges of staff and good practices on IPR management	ATRINEO	
	5.3 Piloting Spin-off supporting services	ATRINEO	
6	6.1 Analysis of institutional, legal, and administrative barriers (M6-M12)	ULPGC	1
	6.2 Monitoring and impact assessment of Action plans implementation (M18-M30)	ULPGC	2
	6.3 Feasibility studies and partnership agreement for establishment of spin-offs supporting offices (M18-M30)	SPEGC	2
	6.4 Creation of a forum of peripheral Universities (M6-M30)	CE	
7	7.1 Dissemination strategy & visual identity (M1-M30)	CE	1 & 2
	7.2 Project website and media dissemination (M1-M30)	CE	
	7.3 Focused communication campaigns (M1-M30)	CE	
	7.4 Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events (M7-M30)	CE	
	7.5 Outreach to children and schools (M7-M30)	CE	
8	8.1 Coordination, reporting, and data management (M1-M30)	ULPGC	
	8.2 Kick-off and other periodic meetings (M1-M30)	ULPGC	
	8.3 Internal evaluation, quality and risk management (M1-M30)	ULPGC	

1.2. STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The structure of this deliverable is organised as follows:

- Introduction (section 1).
- WPs – Monitoring and Impact Assessment (section 2).
- Monitoring and Impact Assessment of the EXPER Plans (section 3)
- Conclusions and future perspectives (section 4).
- Annexes (section 5).

2. WPS – MONITORING AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT

2.1. WP1 – REGIONAL ECOSYSTEMS ASSESSMENT AND COOPERATION MODELS ACTIVITIES

Table 2. Activity: Assessment of Widening universities and their surrounding ecosystems

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Assessment of Widening universities and their surrounding ecosystems</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	ATRINEO, ULPGC and UAC
WP	WP1
Associated task/s	T1.2 Widening Universities Assessment and T1.3 Assessment of surrounding ecosystems.
Implementation RP	1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity leader: ATRINEO; Implementation of the activity: ULPGC and UAC.
Number of participants (if applicable)	Variable, depending on the type of the conducted assessment (internal/external) and entity.
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>As described in Task 1.1 Methodology for assessment, Task 1.2 Widening Universities assessment and Task 1.3 Assessment of surrounding ecosystems of the project, the associated assessments of both Widening Universities (internal or "Widening Universities assessment" and external or "Assessment of surrounding ecosystems") should identify challenges and opportunities for cooperation between Widening universities and their ecosystems, and how to efficiently enhance the role of the HEIs as driver for regional development and competitiveness. These two assessments have been conducted under the planned activities in Tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3. Through the common methodology implemented in Task 1.1, an internal assessment of UAC and ULPGC has been accomplished, involving internal members of each organisation with the aim of understanding in depth the strengths, weaknesses and operational capabilities of both universities in terms of scientific excellence, talent attraction and retention, and knowledge and technology transfer.</p> <p>UAc and ULPGC, as Widening HEIs, carried out the internal questionnaires (to University Leadership positions, R&D Centres, PhD and Post-Doc students) – all responses culminated in the "D.1.2 Azores and Canary Islands Regional ecosystem assessment reports" (submitted to EC on 30/June/2023). In addition, the feedback provided by stakeholders to the universities has been integrated in this work, which was obtained by conducting interviews with these external agents. UAc and ULPGC worked together with the partner ATRINEO for conducting the regional external stakeholder's interviews which feed the chapter "Internal Stakeholders' Reports: Self-assessment results for each ecosystem - UAC Internal Assessment" of the D.1.2.</p> <p>The analysis of their answers allowed us to know their criteria regarding the role that these two Widening Universities should play in terms of promotion and support for regional development, and how cooperation between agents of the ecosystem itself should be developed.</p>	
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)	
<p> Online questionnaires were conducted using Microsoft forms platform. A sample of the questionnaires completed can be found at the following links:</p>	

<https://forms.office.com/e/Wz8yqn6jcN>: Part I
<https://forms.office.com/e/qTE5Rh14J5>: Part II
<https://forms.office.com/e/xAZ8YaFypk>: Part III
<https://forms.office.com/e/RURVTXuaYC>: Part IV
<https://forms.office.com/e/P9G5tC0wwz>: Part V

 Conducting interviews with stakeholders.

Results, findings, and main conclusions

The internal self-assessment of both universities has allowed us to collect valuable information, which was ultimately be of paramount importance for decision-making, especially for the elaboration of the individual strategies, the joint strategy and, finally, the corresponding action plans. All these tasks were developed in later stages of the project and in the framework of tasks 2.3 Developing a joint strategy, and 2.4 Developing action plans of the project. In general terms, this analysis highlights the lack of a unified strategy aimed at optimising the resources of the institution and its environment in order to reach common objectives such as advancing impactful research, fostering innovation and entrepreneurship or engaging with local communities. The analysis also highlights a general lack of effective internal communication systems, which hampers cooperation between departments and the alignment of actions undertaken with the institution's objectives. On the other hand, the lack of financial resources is another of the difficulties identified in both institutions, so that an improvement in the available resources would favour the support of research, digital transformation and infrastructure development. It is also worth highlighting the difficulty that both the UAC and the ULPGC have in recruiting and attracting talent, a difficulty that is mainly linked to the lack of conditions for staff career development, uncompetitive salaries or competition with other prominent universities.

Regarding the conducted interviews, the main conclusions, suggestions, and challenges drawn from these interviews were as follows:

Both universities share the need to improve collaboration and communication with stakeholders in their respective ecosystems, and to work on the optimization of bureaucratic procedures and general management issues.

In relation to the University of the Azores, the following points stand out:

- Improving practical application of research
- Enhancing a culture of entrepreneurship and innovation
- Addressing the knowledge and skill gap
- Leveraging unique geographical and ecological features

Regarding the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, the following issues should be addressed:

- Alignment of educational programs and internships with industry needs
- Skill gaps in the workforce (practical and real industry-aligned skills for students).
- Need for more collaborative research programs (between university and industry)

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Table 3. Activity: ATRINEO's Interview

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>ATRINEO's interview</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		ATRINEO
WP		WP1
Associated task/s		T1.2 Widening Universities Assessment
Implementation RP		1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	ATRINEO: Organizer, EMERGE: Interviewee	
Number of participants (if applicable)	3	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>In May 2023, EMERGE was invited by Vikesh Chugani, Innovation Manager at ATRINEO, for an interview to explore our experience working with the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC). During the meeting, we provided our feedback on the relationship we have established so far with ULPGC in terms of technology transfer, specifically concerning the promotion and support of regional development. We also discussed suggestions on how to improve this collaboration on both ends.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Oral survey		
Results, findings, and main conclusions		
<p>We also discussed suggestions on how to improve this collaboration on both ends. The meeting was very constructive, and the results of this interview were reported in D1.2 Azores and Canary Islands Regional ecosystem assessment reports prepared by ULPGC/UAc/ATRINEO as a deliverable of WP1.</p>		
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)		

Table 4. Activity: Best Practices Catalogue

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Best Practices Catalogue</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		UROS
WP		WP1
Associated task/s		Task 1.4 Good practices from leading Universities
Implementation RP		1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organizer	
Number of participants (if applicable)	2	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
All possible activities of the University of Rostock regarding the three project goals were identified (website and personal communication). For each activity, methods and objectives were identified, contacts were sought, and a summary of the content was given. The activities were assigned to the 3 project goals (research excellence, attraction and retention of talent and technology transfer/cooperation with the business ecosystem). In addition, an overview PDF was created to present all activities (see Annex I).		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Research (Website, Personal) and Microsoft Word		
Results, findings, and main conclusions		
The result is a summary and presentation of all activities of the University of Rostock, which can be used as a template by the partner universities (UAC and ULPGC) to achieve the three different project goals.		
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)		
EXPER Best Practices Catalogue UROS (See Annex I).		

Table 5. Activity: Staff Exchange at UROS

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Staff Exchange at UROS</i>				
Organizer/Responsible partner		UROS				
WP		WP1				
Associated task/s		Task 1.4 Good practices from leading Universities				
Implementation RP		1				
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	UROS: Organiser, UAC and ULPGC/FCPCT staff: Assistants					
Number of participants (if applicable)	26					
General description of the activity/event and objectives						
<p>One of the milestones of the EXPER project is the organization of staff exchanges between the leading Universities (UROS and UNICAL), and the Widening Universities (UAC and ULPGC). Because of this, the first staff exchange was organised between the days 4th and 5th of July 2023 at UROS facilities. As part of this staff exchange, 24 guests from ULPGC and UAC visited the University of Rostock. Preparatory measures included: general preparation for staff exchange (identification and evaluation of necessary program points); organisation of rooms and speakers for the presentations on day 1; organisation and placement of university staff for the personal talks on day 2; procurement of catering. An outline was drawn up showing the daily schedule for the two days, as well as important places in Rostock and within the university. During the two days, the main task was to coordinate all presentations and meetings that took place. After the project meeting, the dismantling of the premises, payment of invoices, etc. for the catering took place.</p>						
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)						
Slides, Microsoft Word, individual and group meetings.						
Results, findings and main conclusions						
<p>The main results came out of the individual meetings, based on the topics of interest for Widening Universities which had been selected previously. The staff exchange made it possible to exchange experiences about programmes at the University of Rostock, which can then be adopted or integrated at the Widening universities (UAC and ULPGC).</p>						
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)						
EXPER	Visit	Guide	UROS	(See	Annex	I).
Some photos during the Staff Exchange at UROS are shown below:						

Table 6. Activity: Online Workshops led by UROS

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Online Workshops</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		UROS
WP		WP1
Associated task/s		Task 1.4 Good practices from leading Universities
Implementation RP		1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	UROS: Organiser, UAC and ULPGC/FCPCT staff: Assistants	
Number of participants (if applicable)	13	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>Three workshops were conducted online between September 25 and 27, 2023, representing a key activity within the EXPER modernization strategies and being part of the actions outlined under Task 1.4 of the project (Good Practices from Leading Universities). This task focuses on identifying and sharing existing structures, services, and practices supporting excellent and responsible research, academia-business cooperation, and the attractiveness of researchers' careers.</p> <p>Organized by UROS in collaboration with all EXPER partners, the workshops served as a collaborative platform for knowledge-sharing and planning. Participants, including members from the EXPER community, had the opportunity to discuss existing practices, with a particular emphasis on successful examples implemented by UROS and UNICAL.</p> <p>The workshops not only facilitated the exchange of good practices but also laid the groundwork for the deployment of capacity-building activities foreseen under work packages WP3, WP4, and WP5. Preparation for the sessions included the collection of relevant topics from widening universities, which were categorized and aligned with the objectives of WP3, WP4, and WP5. This structured approach ensured focused discussions that directly supported the overarching goals of the EXPER modernization strategies.</p> <p>Informed by the assessments conducted under Tasks 1.2 and 1.3, these workshops marked a significant step in translating shared knowledge into actionable plans, further strengthening the alignment of all partners towards the long-term objectives of the project.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Slides, online presentations, surveys (during online workshops), handbooks, SMART Action Plans.		
Results, findings and main conclusions		
<p>The activity produced the following results:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ranking of each action from leading universities (in an assessment sheet) according to the importance to fulfil the goal of WPs (WP3, WP4, WP5) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Results were presented in a raking for each WP and each university individually 2. Collection of specific tasks for each action. Thereby integrating best practices from leading universities, proposals by UROS members and new ideas <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Results were presented in a SMART action plan for each Widening University (ULPGC and UAc) 		
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)		

The following documents are included in

Annex I. Documentation from Workshops on Good Practices and Action Planning (Task 1.4):

- Workshop Summary
- Information Sheets for WP3, WP4 & WP5
- Recommendations for Action Plans
- SMART Action Plan for UAc
- SMART Action Plan for ULPGC
- UROS Best Practices Catalogue

Table 7. Activity: Staff Exchange at UNICAL

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Staff Exchange at UNICAL</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		UNICAL
WP		WP1
Associated task/s		Task 1.4 Good practices from leading Universities
Implementation RP		1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	UNICAL: Organiser, ULPGC/FCPCT staff: Assistants	
Number of participants (if applicable)	14	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>One of the milestones of the EXPER project is the organization of staff exchanges between the leading Universities (UROS and UNICAL), and the Widening Universities (UAC and ULPGC). Because of this, the second staff exchange was organised between the days 12th and 13th of September 2023 at UNICAL facilities. As part of this staff exchange, 7 guests from ULPGC/FCPCT visited the University of Calabria. Preparatory measures included: general preparation for staff exchange (identification and evaluation of necessary program points); organisation of rooms and speakers for the presentations on day 1; organisation and placement of university staff for the personal talks on day 2; procurement of catering. During the two days, the main task was to coordinate all presentations and meetings that took place. After the project meeting, the dismantling of the premises, payment of invoices, etc. for the catering took place.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Slides, Microsoft Word, individual and group meetings.		
Results, findings and main conclusions		
<p>The main results came out of the individual meetings, based on the topics of interest for Widening Universities which had been selected previously. The staff exchange made it possible to exchange experiences about programmes at the University of Calabria, which can then be adopted or integrated at the Widening universities (UAC and ULPGC).</p>		
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)		
Some photos during the Staff Exchange at UNICAL are shown below:		

Table 8. Activity: Regional Ecosystems assessment and cooperation models activities

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Regional Ecosystems assessment and cooperation models activities</i>
Organiser/Responsible partner		CE
WP		WP1
Associated task/s		Task 1.5 Good practices from European universities alliances
Implementation RP		1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organizer, facilitator	
Number of participants (if applicable)	Variable, depending on the activity (interview, workshop).	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>Within the scope of task 1.5, CE, an extensive compilation of valuable insights was procured through meticulous desk research and an in-depth interviewing process, specifically focusing on the funded European University Alliances. This meticulous selection of exemplary practices served to feed the Deliverable 1.3, submitted in September 2023 (M12). Also, as a preliminary phase in organising an online workshop, under the framework of the Forum of Peripheral Universities (Task 6.4 Creation of a forum of peripheral Universities) aimed at extracting valuable lessons related to the challenges and opportunities encountered by these alliances. The primary objective of this workshop was to assess the potential for replicating successful cooperation models and to generate insights that would contribute to the development of the forthcoming EXPER Strategy. It is noteworthy that this workshop was conducted in an inclusive manner, with open access for the public, and other EU-Funded Projects were actively invited to foster meaningful networking opportunities in areas directly relevant to HEIs.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Zoom meetings, slides, mailing campaign, social media posts.		
Results, findings, and main conclusions		
<p>The analysis of cooperation models within the ongoing European Universities Alliances has provided valuable insights to support the development of the long-term EXPER European University Alliance project. This analysis serves as a foundation for fostering meaningful cooperation among European universities and advancing the goals of the EXPER project. The project is better equipped to establish effective partnerships and achieve its objectives by examining successful collaboration frameworks.</p>		

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

 Workshop held under the Forum of Peripheral Universities:

2.2. WP2 – CO-DESIGNING MODERNIZATION WITH SURROUNDING ECOSYSTEMS ACTIVITIES

Table 9. Activity: Co-design Methodology Activities

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Co-design Methodology Activities</i>
Organiser/Responsible partner	CE
WP	WP2
Associated task/s	Task 2.1 Stakeholder involvement and co-design methodology and Task 2.2 Creating a community-based vision of the University
Implementation RP	1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	CE: Organiser, collaborator, facilitator; ULPGC and UAC: activity providers
Number of participants (if applicable)	Variable
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>During Task 2.1, significant emphasis was placed on the development of stakeholder involvement and co-design methodologies. As part of this endeavour, Deliverable 2.1, which pertains to the co-design methodology, was diligently prepared and submitted in M6. This comprehensive document outlines the various phases and tools required to effectively execute the tasks specified in WP2 of the EXPER GA, ensuring seamless implementation of these activities. In M3, our dedicated partners, led by CE, successfully established an internal stakeholder database to identify key representatives from various organisations. This initiative was undertaken to facilitate the co-design activities, which was conducted in conjunction with the Dissemination Activities outlined in WP7.</p>	

Task 2.2 focuses on the collaborative development of a shared vision for Widening universities, emphasising their role in regional development and addressing societal challenges specific to local territories. To achieve this objective, CE provided support to ULPGC and UAC in organising a foundational workshop aimed at defining the vision and mission of both universities. These workshops took place in M7 and brought together high-level representatives from relevant organisations within the ecosystems. Furthermore, in collaboration with WP7, a social media campaign was launched to gather perspectives from citizens in the Widening regions on their aspirations for the future of the universities. To facilitate data analysis, a keyword analysis was conducted on the comments received, and a survey link was included in the campaign. These outreach efforts were conducted in Spanish and Portuguese to actively engage with local citizens and maximise participation. The campaign was promoted across various channels, including the EXPER project's website, ULPGC's social media channels, and UAC's social media channels. Next step is to hold event involving high representatives from the HEIs to gather feedback for the elaboration of the individual strategy of both universities.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Team meetings, leaflets, folders, notebooks, banners to hold the brainstorming session, Microsoft Office, Online ads, EU survey platform

Results, findings, and main conclusions

The implementation of Task 2.1 has resulted in the successful development of stakeholder involvement and co-design methodologies. Deliverable 2.1, which outlines the co-design methodology, was meticulously prepared and submitted in M6, providing a comprehensive guide for executing the tasks specified in WP2 of the EXPER GA. The establishment of an internal stakeholder database in M3 has facilitated the identification of key representatives from various organisations, streamlining the co-design activities in conjunction with the Dissemination Activities outlined in WP7.

Moving on to Task 2.2, our focus has been on fostering collaboration and building a shared vision for Widening universities, emphasising their pivotal role in regional development and addressing societal challenges specific to local territories. With the support of CE, ULPGC, and UAC, both workshops were organised in M7 to define the vision and mission of both universities. These workshops brought together high-level representatives from relevant organisations within the ecosystems, ensuring a comprehensive and inclusive approach.

Additionally, a social media campaign was launched in collaboration with WP7 to actively engage citizens in the Widening regions, seeking their perspectives on the future of the universities. Through this campaign, conducted in Spanish and Portuguese, the project aimed to maximise participation and capture valuable insights. To facilitate analysis, a keyword analysis was performed on the received comments, and an open survey link was incorporated into the campaign to gather further data. The promotion of the campaign across various channels, including the EXPER project's website, ULPGC's social media channels, and UAC's social media channels, extended our reach and enhanced the engagement of local citizens.

The combined efforts of Task 2.1 and Task 2.2 have yielded significant progress in strengthening stakeholder involvement, co-design methodologies, and the development of a shared vision for the Widening universities. These findings served as a solid foundation for subsequent tasks, fostering continued collaboration and guiding the successful implementation of the EXPER project.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Regional social media campaigns launched:

Table 10. Activity: Baseline Workshop to develop the Vision & Mission of ULPGC and UAC

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Baseline Workshop to develop the Vision & Mission of ULPGC and UAC</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	CE, ULPGC and UAC
WP	WP2
Associated task/s	Task 2.2 Creating a community-based vision of the University
Implementation RP	1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator: CE; Organization of the activity: CE, ULPGC and UAC; EMERGE: Attendee
Number of participants (if applicable)	10 to 15 persons (maximum), depending on the entity (ULPGC or UAC)
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>The EXPER project plans to co-design modernisation strategies for transformations of the Widening HEIs based on research and innovation. The co-design aims to ensure that the final product meets the needs of its intended users. As the first co-design phase, the vision and mission of each Widening University must be established in order to identify areas of improvement, which informed the creation of a cohesive and impactful vision for the future. The conducted workshops brought together high-level representatives of each university, representatives of students, businesses association representatives and local authorities.</p> <p>UAc carried out the Workshop "Mission and Vision" on 23/May/2023 (online), while ULPGC conducted theirs on 24/April/2023 (in-site). The sessions commenced with an introduction to the EXPER project,</p>	

providing participants with an overview of its objectives and significance. The co-design session brought together key stakeholders from various domains. Throughout the workshop, the participants engaged in fruitful discussions, sharing their valuable insights and perspectives on the future direction of the UAC and ULPGC.

The aim of the co-design workshop conducted by the EXPER project at the Widening Universities (ULPGC and UAC) was to gather input from senior representatives of the institution to elaborate a vision and mission to guide its future development. Through a series of questions, valuable inputs were collected that reflect the aspirations and needs of the university community, as well as organisations in the local environment. In this analysis, the data collected was examined in detail in order to propose a mission and vision that encompasses all the inputs and guides the future direction of the institution based on the results obtained after the questioning of the participants.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Microsoft Teams meetings, online presentations, elements of dynamization (vision and mission boards, notes, etc.)

Results, findings, and main conclusions

Some of the general aspects/concepts that arose during the conduction of this WS were:

For "Vision": Openness and collaboration, dialogue, fair and equitable remuneration model, focus on people and governance, critical thinking, etc.

For "Mission": To prepare human resources for technological and climate change, improve employability, tractors in new industries, etc.

Once the Widening Universities' mission and vision had been obtained in the framework of the project activities, these results were compared with the vision and mission currently in force at each university. To make this comparison, the universities' current strategic plans were used, trying to find similarities and differences. In this way, work was finally done on those aspects that were not contemplated at the time in these strategic documents, in order to include and update them, and as a basis for preparing the individual strategies of each university.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos of the workshops to elaborate the mission and vision of the ULPGC and the UAC:

Links to ULPGC strategic plans:

- [ULPGC's V Institutional strategic plan](#)
- [Specific Research and Transfer Plan 2022-2025](#)

Table 11. Activity: Strategic development Workshops: Individual Strategy and Joint Strategy Workshops

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Strategic development Workshops: Individual Strategy and Joint Strategy Workshops</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	ULPGC, UAc, CE, ITC, EMERGE,
WP	WP2
Associated task/s	Task 2.3 - Developing a joint strategy & Task 2.4 - Developing Actions Plans
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator: CE; Organization of the activity: FCPCT, CE, ULPGC and UAc; ITC and EMERGE: Attendees
Number of participants (if applicable)	ULPGC: Individual Strategy - 8 (1 st workshop), 5 (2 nd workshop) Joint Strategy – 3 UAc Individual Strategy - 14 (1 st workshop), 10 (2 nd workshop) Joint Strategy – 17
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>As part of the EXPER project's strategic development framework, both the ULPGC and the UAc conducted a series of workshops aimed at establishing their Individual Strategies and developing a Joint Strategy to strengthen collaboration and align their long-term institutional goals. These workshops were implemented under the framework of Task 2.3 and 2.4, which seeks to enhance the institutional capacities of both Widening Universities through structured strategic planning and cooperation.</p> <p> <u>Joint Strategy Workshop</u></p> <p>Following the establishment of individual strategies, ULPGC and UAc held a Joint Strategy Workshop on March 1, 2024, to consolidate the strategic approaches of both universities and define a shared vision for</p>	

future collaboration. The workshop involved stakeholders from diverse backgrounds, including innovation leaders, researchers, gender equality experts, and educators, to discuss and agree on joint objectives and key actions.

The Joint Strategy focused on three core areas:

- 🌐 Excellent and Responsible Research – Defining research priorities, establishing joint research calls, and fostering multidisciplinary participation.
- 🌐 Attracting and Retaining Talent – Creating incubator connections and promoting entrepreneurial training and business development.
- 🌐 Knowledge Transfer and Collaboration – Enhancing cooperation with businesses, organizing joint events, and improving technology transfer practices.

The outcomes of the joint strategy workshop established a roadmap for institutional transformation, ensuring strategic alignment between ULPGC and UAc in research excellence, attracting and retaining talent and societal impact.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Slides, online platforms, questionnaires, reports, strategic planning matrix (a conceptual matrix linking the strategic objectives of each university with the key WPs of the EXPER project was prepared to serve as a strategic reference).

Results, findings, and main conclusions

🌐 **Individual Strategy Workshops**

ULPGC defined strategic objectives and alternative KPIs aligned with the institution's research, innovation, and societal impact goals. The workshop confirmed the importance of enhancing the university's internationalization strategy and strengthening its technology transfer mechanisms.

UAc established a clear set of strategic objectives and KPIs aimed at improving its research capacity and collaboration with regional and international partners. The second workshop validated these KPIs, ensuring their alignment with institutional goals and the broader EXPER project strategy.

🌐 **Joint Strategy Workshop**

The Joint Strategy Workshop led to several key conclusions and commitments:

- 🌐 Organizing joint events – Agreement to organize joint workshops and training sessions to boost the creation of spin-offs and business projects (e.g., following the CLAB model).
- 🌐 Connecting incubator programs – Establishing a formal connection between ULPGC and UAc's incubators to share best practices, resources, and business support services.
- 🌐 Promoting entrepreneurship – Emphasis on integrating entrepreneurship into academic programs and encouraging the creation of start-ups and spin-offs.
- 🌐 Strengthening research collaboration – Identification of research areas for collaboration, including joint calls for proposals and interdisciplinary projects.
- 🌐 Addressing social challenges – Exploring social entrepreneurship programs and creating observatories to collect and analyze data on social challenges.
- 🌐 Cooperation under the HRS4R Strategy and European University Alliances – Commitment to share experiences related to HRS4R certification and explore collaboration opportunities within the framework of European University Alliances.

The outcomes of these strategic workshops reinforce the commitment of both universities to promoting entrepreneurship, cutting-edge research, and strategic collaboration to address social and economic challenges in their territories in a sustainable and innovative manner.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos during the organized workshops:

2.3. WP3 – ATTRACTING AND RETAINING TALENTS

Table 12. Activity: UNICAL - Supporting the Implementation of HRS4R and improving framework conditions

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>UNICAL - Supporting the implementation of HRS4R and improving framework conditions</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	UNICAL, ULPGC, UAc
WP	WP3
Associated task/s	Task 3.1 Implementing the HRS4R and improving framework conditions
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser, leading partner and facilitator (UNICAL)
Number of participants (if applicable)	Not applicable
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>As the leader of Task 3.1 "Implementing the HRS4R and Improving Framework Conditions," UNICAL has played a pivotal role in supporting the implementation and enhancement of the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) at UAc and ULPGC. The task focuses on improving framework conditions for researchers while aligning efforts with the objectives of the European Charter for Researchers.</p> <p>Throughout Task 3.1, UNICAL has actively facilitated knowledge exchange, provided guidance, and promoted collaboration among the involved partners. Key activities and milestones included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> November 2024: Suggesting participation in the EC's online event to provide updates on HRS4R strategies and the European Charter for Researchers. <p>These activities aimed to address specific needs identified under WP1, enhancing institutional frameworks and promoting an attractive research career environment.</p>	
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)	

Presentation materials, documentation templates, communication channels (emails for regular updates, feedback and progress monitoring), internal planning documents.

Results, findings and main conclusions

For UAc:

- 🌐 A timeline for HRS4R implementation was established with tailored actions to guide the process.
- 🌐 UNICAL supported the revision of UAc's initial HRS4R strategies and provided a structured self-assessment matrix.
- 🌐 The endorsement letter and future strategy for HRS4R implementation were refined and aligned with European standards.

In this regard, UAc worked together with UNICAL in order to make an initial submission from UAc to the HRS4R. The support of UNICAL provided UAc with recommendations on how write the initial UAc endorsement letter to EC, establishment of the responsible UAc HRS4R Steering Committee and Working Group, timeline for launching the HRS4R accreditation process, elaboration of Internal Analysis and Construction and compilation of Self-Assessment Matrix, internal survey and documentation needed for submission, namely the GAP Analysis + OTM+R Checklist + Action Plan.

For ULPGC:

- 🌐 The HRS4R Action Plan was revised, incorporating feedback from UNICAL to enhance alignment with good practices.
- 🌐 A draft Catalogue of Good Practices for ULPGC was shared, serving as a key reference for the implementation process (See Annex III. Catalogue of Good Practices for ULPGC (HRS4R Strategy))
- 🌐 Strategies for creating an attractive career environment were outlined, informed by examples from UNICAL and UROS.

General Outcomes:

- 🌐 UAc submitted the HRS4R endorsement letter through the EURAXESS portal on 25/Mar/2024. UAc established its HRS4R Steering Committee and Working Group.
- 🌐 Strengthened collaboration between partners through regular steering meetings and task-specific workshops.
- 🌐 Development of actionable frameworks and good practice catalogues to support sustainable implementation of HRS4R.
- 🌐 Clear alignment with the goals of the EXPER European University Alliance, fostering attractive and responsible research environments.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Table 13. Activity: Replicating the CLAB Model

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Replicating the CLAB Model</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		ULPGC, FCPCT, UNICAL, EMERGE, UAc
WP		WP3
Associated task/s		Task 3.2 Replicating the CLAB model (UNICAL)
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser (ULPGC and UAc), trainer, facilitator and leading partner (UNICAL), teachers (FCPCT, EMERGE, ULPGC).	
Number of participants (if applicable)	11-26	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The primary goal of Task 3.2 was to replicate the Contamination Lab (CLAB) model, a successful entrepreneurial training program pioneered by UNICAL, at the two Widening Universities: ULPGC and UAc. This task aimed to foster an entrepreneurial mindset and cultivate interdisciplinary collaboration among university students and researchers involved.</p> <p>The program was divided into five phases: Dissemination, Academy, Pre-Acceleration, Final Competition, and Acceleration. Each phase was carefully planned to provide participants with key competencies for developing entrepreneurial projects, such as business modelling, market analysis, team management, and risk management, while also emphasizing transversal skills like creative thinking, negotiation, and communication.</p> <p>UNICAL acted as the technical lead, providing comprehensive guidance, training materials, and methodological support for replicating the CLAB model. EMERGE and Consulta Europa played a significant role in designing and delivering specific activities, as detailed below.</p> <p>Activities carried out by partners:</p> <p>1. ULPGC/FCPCT:</p> <p><u><i>Organization of the first CLAB at ULPGC (April 2024-March 2025):</i></u></p> <p>The ULPGC and FCPCT managed all phases of the program at their facilities, from the dissemination of the call to the final competition.</p> <p><u><i>Development of the Academy phase (June-July 2024):</i></u></p> <p>ULPGC/FCPCT coordinated six theoretical classes with the participation of local professors and experts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elisa Rodríguez (FCPCT/ULPGC): Business model and project pitching. <p>Groups received specialized guidance in areas such as financial plan development, economic projections, market analysis and validation strategies.</p>		

"Team Building by Cooking" Workshop (July 2024):

ULPGC/FCPCT organized this hands-on workshop as a team cohesion activity, fostering transversal skills such as problem-solving, creativity, and leadership in a collaborative environment.

Pre-Acceleration Phase (September-November 2024)

The Pre-acceleration phase at CLAB ULPGC focused on refining business ideas for the final competition through four key stages: (1) Expert consulting to develop business plans using AI tools, including market analysis and value proposition; (2) Financial projections covering investment, financing, sales, and expenditure plans; (3) Networking sessions with SPEGC, ITC, and the Chamber of Commerce to provide strategic insights; and (4) Presentation preparation with mentor guidance and a communication workshop to enhance pitching skills.

Final competition (December 2024):

ULPGC/FCPCT organized the CLAB closing session, which included project presentations, jury evaluations, and the awarding of the prize to the winning team.

Acceleration Phase (March 2025):: Organization of the Exchange Program for the Winning Team (January-March 2025):

The Acceleration Phase involved organizing an Exchange Program (March 2025) for the winning team, "Safewotah". ULPGC/FCPCT managed the logistics for the team's visit to the UNICAL, where up to three students and one mentor refined their project and engaged with local mentors. Activities at UNICAL included: a masterclass on market identification and problem-solution fit, a laboratory on target audience analysis and segmentation, and meetings with past winning teams to share experiences and insights.

2. UAc:

UAc was involved in the initial steps of ULPGC CLAB (as this was a joint effort) by running a parallel "call for applicants", both students/mentors at UAc until 26/May/2024. Only one UAc student applied and participated in the initial ULPGC CLAB sessions.

3. UNICAL:

Training and guidance (June 2024):

UNICAL provided pre-training sessions to the CLAB organizers at ULPGC and UAC, focusing on the program structure, content, and methodologies. These sessions equipped local organizers with the knowledge and tools to replicate the CLAB model successfully. Topics covered included market analysis, value proposition, team building, business modelling, and growth hacking.

Delivery of specialized lessons (July 2024):

UNICAL directly contributed to the Academy phase by delivering two complementary lessons:

 Motivational Strategies and Innovation:

This session emphasized the importance of motivation, identifying market gaps, and crafting an effective elevator pitch.

 Go-to-Market and Digital Tools:

This session explored the fundamentals of business development, distinguishing between B2B and B2C strategies, and identifying target audiences.

Support during the Pre-Acceleration phase:

UNICAL provided detailed guidance for the development of business plans, financial projections, and pitch preparation. They also supplied supporting materials, such as presentation templates and mock-ups, to ensure the quality of deliverables.

Hosting the Acceleration phase (March 2025):

UNICAL hosted the winning team, "Safewotah," for a formative exchange stay at UNICAL. This allowed the team to refine their project, interact with other students and mentors, and learn from successful case studies within the CLAB ecosystem.

4. EMERGE:

Expert contribution during the Academy phase (June-July 2024):

EMERGE played a vital role in the Academy phase by delivering the "Validation" module. This session introduced participants to Lean management principles and guided them in designing and validating their value propositions. Specific topics included:

- Market innovation and the theoretical framework of "Jobs to be done."
- Problem-Solution Fit (P/S Fit) and the Value Proposition.

Mentorship during Pre-Acceleration:

EMERGE provided tailored mentorship to the working groups, focusing on customer development strategies and market validation. Their expertise in digital transformation and growth hacking significantly contributed to refining business models.

5. Consulta Europa:

Project coordination and communication:

Consulta Europa ensured smooth communication between partners and facilitated the exchange of best practices among all involved parties. This coordination was essential for aligning efforts and maintaining the quality standards of the CLAB program replication.

Support for dissemination activities:

Consulta Europa actively supported the dissemination phase by designing and sharing promotional materials, including posters, social media posts, and news updates on the EXPER website. These efforts maximized awareness and engagement among students and researchers at ULPGC and UAc.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Communication and documentation tools, AI for modelling business models, presentation materials (slides, templates, etc.), educational resources, interactive workshops, registration forms, images.

Results, findings and main conclusions

- A total of four teams completed the program, with "Safewotah" emerging as the winning project during the final competition.
- Participants gained essential transversal skills, including critical thinking, negotiation, teamwork, and effective communication.
- The ULPGC CLAB strengthened the innovation and business capabilities of the University, reinforcing its role in driving socio-economic transformation of the region.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

 Academy Phase:

 “Team building by cooking” Workshop:

 Final competition:

Table 14. Activity: Engaging activities for children and schools

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Engaging activities for children and schools</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		CE/ULPGC-FCPCT, UAc, Terinov
WP		WP3
Associated task/s		T3.3. Ensuring gender equality and promoting diversity
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser	
Number of participants (if applicable)	Not applicable	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>Task 3.3 Ensuring gender equality and promoting diversity aimed to conduct one focus group in each EXPER University to identify existing barriers and outline interventions to promote diversity. A diversity strategy has been formulated for both the Widening HEIs and awareness raising and communication activities were organised in conjunction with WP7.</p> <p>"Within the context of communication activities, and in collaboration with the ATHENA project and the Macaronight Project, CE and ULPGC organised a series of engaging activities for children and schools to promote diversity and gender equality in the research field.</p> <p>In 2024, a campaign was launched to celebrate the accomplishments of women in science while simultaneously inspiring and cultivating a passion for scientific exploration among the younger generation in the celebration of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science. This initiative, aligned with T7.3 and T7.5 of the EXPER project, emphasised the significance of research and the crucial role of diversity within the research community. Children had the opportunity to interact with renowned female scientists from ULPGC.</p> <p>A similar approach was implemented in the Azores by UAc, in collaboration with Terinov, through a series of engaging activities and school visits. These initiatives aimed not only to spark curiosity in the field of research but also to cultivate a diverse pool of future researchers. A total of 310 children across various schools in the Canary Islands participated in these activities, while 180 children engaged with these initiatives in the Azores during 2024, demonstrating the successful collaboration among partners.</p> <p>Furthermore, within the scope of T3.3, a focused group discussion was organised on October 29th, 2024, with representatives from ULPGC and the surrounding ecosystem on the basis of the results of the Smart Action Plans from T1.4 series of workshops. This discussion, attended by over 25 participants from diverse organisations and the university, aimed to identify and address existing barriers to diversity within the university. Notably, the rector of ULPGC participated in this event, underscoring the university's commitment to fostering a diverse and inclusive environment.</p> <p>Similarly, UAc supported by CE conducted an online session on February 11th, 2025, involving various actors from the university and the Azorean region. This session aimed to outline the necessary interventions to promote diversity within the institution and was attended by 5 experts on Gender Equality.</p> <p>The valuable feedback collected from these focus group discussions served as a crucial foundation for the development of a comprehensive Diversity Strategy (D3.2), which both HEIs will implement beyond the scope of the EXPER project.</p> <p>Finally, to support all of these online ads were published in geolocating the campuses of both universities in the Azores and the Canary Islands, segmented by profession (workers and students) with key messages to raise awareness on diversity resulting with an outreach of 2000 people on Instagram and Facebook, the most used social media networks of the project.</p>		

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Slides, online presentations, workshop methodology (focus group), T7.4 Game Scientists and Achievements (ULPGC and UAc cards), EXPER promotional materials, social media posts.

Research questions used for the Focus Groups:

1. What good practices related to gender equality and diversity have you come across in your professional field? Are there any that you have implemented?
2. What do you see as the biggest obstacles or challenges to achieving gender equality and diversity in your field? Focusing on the university setting, what are the most significant barriers preventing the university from achieving true equality and fostering excellence in research and innovation? Why is this important? How does a lack of equality impact both the university and businesses?
3. If you could prioritize one specific action or initiative to promote gender equality and diversity in your field, what would it be? Why is this particular action or initiative so important to you?

Results, findings and main conclusions

- Diversity Strategy developed for both the ULPGC and UAc
- 25 stakeholders engaged in discussions on diversity and gender equality (ULPGC)
- 491 children engaged in T7.5 discovered the role of the researchers and why is diversity important
- XX stakeholders engaged in discussions on diversity and gender equality (UAc)

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Dissemination on the project's website: <https://exper-project.eu/scientists-and-achievements-celebrating-international-day-of-women-and-girls-in-science/>

Some photos of the activities performed can be found below:

Table 15. Activity: Strategies to address Brain Drain and strengthen research Talent Retention in ORs

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Strategies to address Brain Drain and strengthen research Talent Retention in ORs</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	EMERGE, ULPGC, UAc, UROS
WP	WP3
Associated task/s	T3.4. Addressing brain drain
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	EMERGE: Task leader, organizer and facilitator
Number of participants (if applicable)	Not applicable
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>As part of Task 3.4: Addressing Brain Drain, EMERGE has led a series of coordinated activities aimed at identifying the underlying causes of brain drain and developing strategies to enhance the attractiveness and retention of research talent in the Canary Islands and the Azores. The overarching objective of this task is to mitigate the loss of highly skilled researchers from these outermost regions by improving local research environments, expanding career development opportunities, and strengthening international collaboration.</p> <p>The first step involved exploring current HR management practices at ULPGC to identify strategic priorities for improving internationalization and attracting top-tier researchers, particularly at the R1 and R2 career stages. This was followed by interviews with early-stage researchers (R1 and R2) at both ULPGC and UAc, which provided insights into the challenges they face and their motivations for seeking career opportunities abroad.</p> <p>To further understand the socioeconomic drivers behind brain drain, EMERGE conducted a series of interviews with key stakeholders, including representatives from the Regional Association of Young Researchers in the Canary Islands (JINTE) and experienced researchers who have pursued careers abroad. Additionally, EMERGE organized interviews with leading European institutions such as UC3M and the University of Zurich to gather insights into best practices for talent retention and attraction.</p> <p>A significant milestone was the organization of an international webinar (20th February 2025), which was part of the planned activities under Task 3.4. The objective of the webinar was to present and discuss the findings of the study with leading European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The event focused on fostering intersectoral collaboration, enhancing research career stability, and improving working conditions for researchers in outermost regions. The University of Rostock (UROS) was invited to present best practices and outstanding programmes specifically aimed at supporting and promoting young researchers. The focus was on sharing successful initiatives and best practices. These activities laid the foundation for a comprehensive set of recommendations to strengthen research ecosystems in the Canary Islands and the Azores, with the ultimate goal of creating a more attractive and sustainable environment for research talent.</p>	
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)	
Online presentations and interviews, in person interviews, slides.	
Results, findings and main conclusions	
The activities conducted under Task 3.4 have yielded valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities related to research talent retention and attraction in the Canary Islands and the Azores.	

- 🌐 **HR Management at ULPGC** – The analysis of HR practices at ULPGC highlighted the need to enhance internationalization strategies and leverage upcoming funding opportunities to improve the global positioning of the university. Concrete plans have been proposed to align with these opportunities and foster global collaborations.
- 🌐 **Interviews with early-stage researchers** – Feedback from R1 and R2 researchers underscored the lack of postdoctoral opportunities, inadequate support networks, and the need for stable research funding. The insights gathered have informed tailored recommendations to improve career stability and enhance the working environment for young researchers.
- 🌐 **Causes of brain drain** – Interviews with stakeholders identified key challenges, including the limited availability of postdoctoral positions, structural and logistical barriers (e.g., customs restrictions on research materials), and insufficient regional funding. Proposed solutions include creating sustainable postdoctoral programs, increasing research funding, and improving the overall research infrastructure.
- 🌐 **Exchange of Best Practices with leading institutions** – Discussions with European universities and regional agencies highlighted successful strategies such as targeted mobility programs, talent retention incentives, and enhanced intersectoral career pathways. The engagement established during these meetings has laid the groundwork for future collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- 🌐 **International Webinar on talent retention (20 February 2025)** – The webinar confirmed that geographic isolation, limited economic diversification, and funding constraints are major obstacles to talent retention in ORs. Key strategies discussed included enhancing intersectoral mobility, expanding access to EU funding, and improving research training. The importance of building stronger local ecosystems and fostering cross-border collaboration was emphasized as critical to sustaining research talent in the long term.

The insights gained through these activities have informed a strategic roadmap for addressing brain drain in the Canary Islands and the Azores, combining targeted policy recommendations, improved funding mechanisms, and enhanced institutional support to create a more attractive and sustainable research environment.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos of the activities performed can be found below:

🌐 Interviews

 International webinar

The presentation slide, titled "GRANTEES ERC", is divided into three main sections: "Option of a distinguished researcher contract with the Axencia Galega de Innovación", "PRO-ERC support:", and "POST-ERC support:".

Option of a distinguished researcher contract with the Axencia Galega de Innovación

Salary according to the type of grant:

Grant Type	Salary (€/year)
ADVANCED GRANT	€100,000
CONSOLIDATOR GRANT	€81,000
STARTING GRANT	€65,000

PRO-ERC support: Financial resources complementary to the ERC funding provided by the Consellería de Educación, Ciencia, Universidades e Formación Profesional, and by the Axencia Galega de Innovación during the life of the project.

Grant Type	Amount (€/year)
ADVANCED GRANT	€80,000
CONSOLIDATOR GRANT	€65,000
STARTING GRANT	€50,000

POST-ERC support: Continued financial support after the end of the ERC assistance period. Optima's Programa remuneración for researchers contracted by the SGR or by the ERC.

Grant Type	Amount (€/year)
ADVANCED GRANT	€30,000
CONSOLIDATOR GRANT	€8,000
STARTING GRANT	€6,500
STARTING GRANT	€5,000

Support services for excellent science and hosting of new research staff offered on an individual basis by the host institutions.

The video conference overlay on the right shows participants from "Asociación Emerge", "mjmardon", "Wieland Müller", "Yasna Mimbela - Busin...", "LIUDMILA", "Asociación Emerge", "Carmen Méndez", "Vicerrector de I...", "Vicerrector de Investig...", "Vera Martinelli", and "Alain Marengi...".

exper EMERGE:
STARTING INNOVATION

Retaining and Attracting Research Talent in Europe: Challenges, Strategies, and Solutions

Online Seminar: Learn best practices for attracting & retaining top research talent.

February 20th, 2025, 10:30 CET.

Register today!

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

2.4. WP4 – PROMOTING EXCELLENT AND RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

Table 16. Activity: Preparatory meetings and work

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Preparatory meetings and work</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		ITC
WP		WP4
Associated task/s		Task 4.1 – Establishment and coordination of “societal challenges working groups”
Implementation RP		1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser and speaker	
Number of participants (if applicable)	Not applicable	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>WP4 aims at sharing research & innovation strategies to create impact for society. For this purpose, two multidisciplinary “societal challenges working groups” were established and coordinated under Task 4.1. Each working groups counts with an Action Plan delivered under D4.1 Societal Challenges working groups and thematic action plans, handed in March 2024.</p> <p>This WP was developed from Month 12 to Month 30, and during the first year of EXPER project, some preparatory actions and meetings were held, including:</p> <p>All the activities done under WP4 and especially under Task 4.2 have been disseminated. On the one hand, it was necessary to showcase the work done under EXPER, but especially to make visible the societal challenges and the research areas that are trying to address and create solutions.</p> <p>Dissemination has been organised among all EXPER partners, specially among CE, ITC, ULPGC, UAc and UAc.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Images and texts.		
Results, findings and main conclusions		
Communication well done with the support of clear images and concrete posts on social networks.		
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)		
<p>https://exper-project.eu/exper-project-advances-establishing-societal-challenges-working-groups-for-sustainable-solutions/</p> <p>UROS Seminar: https://exper-project.eu/events-page/university-of-calabria-showcases-solutions-for-climate-change-and-ocean-restoration-at-exper-project-webinar/</p> <p>ULPGC Seminar: https://exper-project.eu/events-page/university-of-las-palmas-de-gran-canaria-showcases-sustainability-solutions-at-exper-project-webinar/</p> <p>UROS Seminar: https://exper-project.eu/events-page/university-of-rostock-tackles-sustainability-challenges-at-exper-project-seminar/</p>		

UAc Seminar: <https://exper-project.eu/events-page/university-of-the-azores-hosts-exper-project-seminar-bridging-excellence-for-a-sustainable-future/>

General dissemination: <https://exper-project.eu/exper-project-invites-you-to-online-seminars-bridging-excellence-in-peripheral-regions/>

Gran Canaria Summer School, July 2025. Meeting with the 4 chair researchers to foster project proposals:

<https://exper-project.eu/the-exper-projects-core-societal-challenges-working-groups-set-strategic-course-at-gran-canaria-summer-school/>

<https://exper-project.eu/exper-summer-school-concluded-in-gran-canaria/>

<https://exper-project.eu/open-science-and-communication-technology-transfer-and-proposal-writing-for-excellent-research-and-innovation/>

<https://exper-project.eu/the-summer-school-of-the-exper-project-will-reinforce-the-knowledge-and-the-writing-of-proposals-for-horizon-europe-in-gran-canaria/>

Addressing Blue and Green R&D Priorities', Terceira regional event, February 2025.

<https://exper-project.eu/terinov-event-bridges-gap-between-academia-business-and-society-in-blue-and-green-ri/>

<https://exper-project.eu/events-page/exper-regional-event-in-terceira-island/>

Table 17. Activity: SCWGs Management

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>SCWGs Management</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		ITC
WP		WP4
Associated task/s		Task 4.1 – Establishment and coordination of “societal challenges working groups”
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser and facilitator	
Number of participants (if applicable)	More than 15: 4 researchers + 4 facilitators + 8 Project managers (1 per partner)	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>WP4 aims at sharing research & innovation strategies to create impact for society. For this purpose, it was needed to establish and coordinate multidisciplinary “societal challenges working groups”. The working groups include researchers, entrepreneurs and representatives of relevant organizations from EXPER regions and other European organizations engaged in green transition and blue growth.”</p> <p>In this WP, since the first year of EXPER project but particularly from Month 12 to Month 30, different meetings and actions have taken place, including:</p>		

- 🌐 Presentations during kick-off, on-line and in-site project meetings.
- 🌐 Analysis and presentation of previous work developed in FORWARD project and lessons learned to define and coordinate the working groups.
- 🌐 Bilateral and group meetings with partners ULPGC, UAc, UNICAL, UROS, TERINOV and Consulta Europa, to check the advance of the first WPs (Ecosystem analysis and workshop outcomes) and WP5 (Connection with business environment) and align them to the WP4.
- 🌐 Establishment of 2 Societal Challenges Working Groups (SCWGs): 1) ADAPTATION TO CLIMATE CHANGE IN THE BLUE AND/OR CIRCULAR ECONOMY; 2) RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS IN THE BLUE AND/OR CIRCULAR ECONOMY.
- 🌐 Establishment of the groups' governance, led by 4 researchers, 2 from ULPGC and 2 from UAc.
- 🌐 Organization and leadership of several meetings with the ULPGC and UAc researchers and regional innovation ecosystem representatives to create the groups' Action Plans and milestones.
- 🌐 Delivering **D4.1 Societal Challenges working groups and thematic action plans**, in March 2024.
- 🌐 Organization and leadership of several meetings with the partners to implement the SCWGs Action Plans.
- 🌐 Promoting and disseminating the actions done.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

- 🌐 Working documents and presentations
- 🌐 Online seminars and meetings
- 🌐 In place meetings

Results, findings and main conclusions

- 🌐 Taking into account previous WPs results, it was possible to choose and focus on specific societal challenges in line with RIS3 priorities, SDG, Horizon Europe Missions and challenges detected in ULPGC and UAc ecosystems.
- 🌐 Definition of working groups in line with EXPER priorities (green transition and blue growth).
- 🌐 Integration and management of the working group expectations.
- 🌐 According to D4.1 Action Plans' milestone: Task 1.2) Management: more than 6 managing meetings were done with 10 attendances in average: 4 researchers + 6 project partners. Task 3.1) Networking: more than 10 stakeholders identified among EXPER regions. Task 3.2) Networking: several events identified. Task 4.1 Implementation) More than 5 calls of interest were identified. Task 4.2 Implementation) 1 project proposal has been delivered and 1 is under redaction. Task 5.1 Dissemination) 6 pieces of news has been published on the website and share on the project social networks.

Photographs or other associated documents

GOVERNANCE TEAM

SCWG1 – Adaptation to Climate Change

CHAIRS:

- **UAC: Joana Barcelos e Ramos** (IITAA - Institute of Agricultural and Environmental Research and Technology)
- **ULPGC: Leví Aday García Romero** (Institute of Oceanography and Global Change IOGAG ULPGC)

SCWG2 – Restore our Oceans and Waters

CHAIRS:

- **UAC: Andrea Zita Botelho** (CIBIO-A - Research Center for Biodiversity and Genetic Resources - Azores)
- **ULPGC: Rodrigo Riera Elena** (BIOCON (Biodiversity and Conservation) IU-ECOQUA ULPGC)

Facilitators:

- **ULPGC: Tanausú Dávila**
- **UAC: Emanuel Mecha**

WP4 coordinators

- **ITC: Dayana Martín & Lucía Dobarro**

MEMBERS

EXPER TEAM

Core group

- UROS, UNICAL, TERinov

Other EXPER members

- SPEGC, EMERGE, aTRineo, CE

Other stakeholders

1. Government Agencies.
2. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Conservation Organizations.
3. Policymakers.
4. Research Institutions.
5. Industry Partners.
6. Local Communities.
7. International Organizations.
8. Educational Institutions.
9. Media and Communication Channels.
10. Civil Society and Community Groups.
11. End Users and Consumers.

<https://exper-project.eu/exper-project-advances-establishing-societal-challenges-working-groups-for-sustainable-solutions/>

Table 18. Activity: EXPER Summer School in Gran Canaria

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>EXPER Summer School in Gran Canaria</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	ULPGC, CE, ITC
WP	WP4
Associated task/s	Task 4.2 Implementation of Societal Challenges Action Plans
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	ULPGC-FCPCT and CE: Organiser; Facilitator: FCPCT, CE, ITC, EMERGE; Attendees: UAc
Number of participants (if applicable)	89
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>The EXPER Summer School took place from July 17 to July 19, 2024, at the NEXO Building of the ULPGC. This event, held under the framework of Task 4.2 of the EXPER project, aimed to enhance the research management skills of participants from the ULPGC and UAc. The summer school provided an immersive training experience focusing on open science, writing successful project proposals for Horizon Europe (HE) 2021-2027, and promoting entrepreneurial innovation through European funding programs such as the European Research Council (ERC) and the European Innovation Council (EIC).</p> <p>The summer school gathered a diverse group of participants, including early-stage and senior researchers, project managers and research support staff from both universities (ULPGC and UAc), as well as representatives of the regional entrepreneurial ecosystem, including ULPGC start-ups representatives and external stakeholders. This mix of profiles ensured a multidisciplinary approach, fostering knowledge exchange and collaborative problem-solving.</p> <p>The summer school was structured into three key training areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EIC and Innovation – Focused on developing business models, securing funding through EIC instruments (Pathfinder, Transition, and Accelerator), and supporting spin-offs and startups. <p>The program also included practical workshops on project development, networking sessions with international stakeholders, and collaborative work aimed at addressing societal challenges such as climate change adaptation and marine ecosystem restoration. Expert presentations and hands-on exercises ensured that participants gained both theoretical knowledge and practical skills for future project execution.</p>	
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)	
Presentation slides and working documents, Online registration and feedback surveys (Microsoft Forms).	

Handouts on Horizon Europe, ERC, and EIC guidelines, physical training materials (notebooks, folders, pens), Conference rooms and multimedia equipment at NEXO building, networking and coffee break areas for informal discussions, digital resources (EXPER website and online repository).

Results, findings and main conclusions

The EXPER Summer School successfully strengthened the research capacity and project development skills of participants from ULPGC and UAc. Pivotal outcomes include:

- Enhanced knowledge of Horizon Europe, ERC, and EIC funding opportunities and evaluation criteria.
- Improved proposal writing skills for securing competitive European funding.
- Strengthened research management capabilities, with a focus on open science and strategic alignment with European Commission priorities.
- Reinforced institutional capacity to support spin-offs and startups through knowledge transfer and business development strategies.
- Active participation of researchers from ULPGC and UAc, with positive feedback highlighting the value of networking and collaborative exercises.
- Practical application of knowledge through proposal writing workshops and direct engagement with industry and academic experts.

The event fostered collaboration among participants and experts, encouraging the formation of multidisciplinary partnerships and enhancing the strategic positioning of ULPGC and UAc within the European Research Area (ERA).

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

- Some photos of the event are included below:

Table 19. Activity: UAc Summer School: Open Science and Communication, Technology Transfer and Proposal writing for Excellence Research and Innovation

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>UAc Summer School: Open Science and Communication, Technology Transfer and Proposal writing for Excellence Research and Innovation</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		UAc
WP		WP4, WP5 and WP7
Associated task/s		Task 4.2 Implementation of Societal Challenges Action Plans, Task 5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities and Task 7.4 Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator and organization: UAc; Attendees: Academia, companies, local authorities, civil society	
Number of participants (if applicable)	90	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The University of the Azores (UAc) held online from September 24th to 26th, 2024, via Microsoft Teams, its EXPER Summer School, tailored for all regional stakeholders in the quadruple helix model, bringing together academia, industry, government, and civil society. This event aimed to enhance participants skills in science communication, technology transfer, and proposal writing.</p> <p>Day 1 - September 24: Science Communication and Open Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Practical Case Study on Proposal Preparation. <p>Through expert presentations, interactive sessions, and insights from and local industry representatives, the event aimed to foster a culture of innovation and effective knowledge transfer, ultimately contributing to societal advancements and economic growth in the ORs.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Expert presentations, hands-on practical exercises, tailored slides.		
Results, findings and main conclusions		
This event brought together over 90 participants and leading experts from across Europe and national/regional involvement with the UAc to engage in an intensive programme designed to enhance skills in proposal writing, open science and communication, technology transfer and research excellence.		

Designed to cultivate project development through group work, the programme enabled participants to collaboratively refine their further development. Three crucial areas of training and expertise were addressed during the summer school:

-
HE funding opportunities and proposal writing: Participants gained a better understanding of the available funding sources and opportunities (to the Azores and based on regional S3 strategy) in order for them to make the right choices when applying to EU funding calls, maximizing the regional approval rates and R&D+I in the region. Furthermore, their practical skills in writing successful proposals for Horizon Europe were increased, which results in a raise in competitiveness UAc researchers and their partners and regional stakeholders, contributing to boosting research excellence and ORs participation in EU funding programmes.
-
Improving Science Communication and Open Science practices: The participants raised their awareness on the importance of science communication and general concepts, good practices and science education to make better use of research results. They also improve their knowledge about open science general concepts, policies/requirements and available tools, data management in open science, the current situation on a national scale, and the opportunities, constraints and challenges in this field.
-
Technology Transfer and Innovation: Through one day dedicated to technology transfer, the project partner ATRINEO conducted a mini-masterclass (which also paved the way for what would be presented on the 2-day workshop to be conducted in Nov/2024) focusing on capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities, which aimed to equip participants with the necessary skills and knowledge to bridge the gap between research and practical applications, fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship. This session also included several testimonies of regional companies previously involved with UAc, from the beginning of the knowledge transfer process, through the creation of the companies, typologies of received funding, products and current customers, also giving space to discuss the main obstacles encountered in the company's creation process.

Overall, the UAc Summer School contributed the EXPER WPs objectives, by providing the participants with the tools and knowledge necessary to drive research excellence, innovation, and effective knowledge transfer, ultimately benefiting both the academic and broader regional communities.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

- Some photos of the event are included below:

Additional information:

- <https://noticias.uac.pt/inscricoes-abertas-para-a-exper-summer-school/>
- <https://exper-project.eu/open-science-and-communication-technology-transfer-and-proposal-writing-for-excellent-research-and-innovation/>
- <https://exper-project.eu/successful-online-summer-school-explores-open-science-technology-transfer-and-horizon-europe-proposal-writing/>
- <https://noticias.uac.pt/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/aqui-1.pdf>

Table 20. Activity: Action Plans implementation.

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Action Plan Implementation. Objective 1: Management Activity from Month 18 to Month 30</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	ITC
WP	WP4
Associated task/s	Task 4.2 Implementation of Societal Challenges Action Plans
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser and facilitator
Number of participants (if applicable)	8 participants: 4 researchers + 4 facilitators
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>WP4 aims at sharing research & innovation strategies to create impact for society. For this purpose, 2 "societal challenges working groups" were established and coordinated under Task 4.1. Each working groups counts with an Action Plan delivered under D4.1 Societal Challenges working groups and thematic action plans, handed in March 2024.</p>	

Each group counted with a governance team to lead the implementation of the Action Plan.

The governance team had regular meetings in order to achieve the goals of the 2 Groups' Action Plans:

- 🌐 **March/April 2024:** definition of the common working areas (Action Plan – Objective 2: Focusing).
- 🌐 **June 2024:** First networking interactions (Action Plan – Objective 3: Networking) + searching for potential financing opportunities in line with the working areas (Action Plan – Objective 4: Implementation).
- 🌐 **July 2024:** In place networking at Gran Canaria Summer School. Face to face meetings with the objective to building up new project proposal among the group members (Action Plan – Objective 3: Networking + Objective 4: Implementation).
- 🌐 **September / October 2024:** Defining the proposal for online networking (Action Plan – Objective 3: Networking) + New potential financing opportunities in line with the working areas (Action Plan Objective 4: Implementation).
- 🌐 **November / December / January 2024:** Organisation and implementation of 4 online networking events. (Action Plan – Objective 3: Networking + Objective 4: Implementation).
- 🌐 **February 2024:** in place meeting in Terceira, Azores. Face-to-face meetings with the objective of building up new project proposals among the group members (Action Plan – Objective 3: Networking + Objective 4: Implementation).
- 🌐 **March 2024:** in place meeting in Gran Canaria, at the final event. (Action Plan – Objective 3: Networking + Objective 4: Implementation).

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Online and in-place meetings, presentations and working documents.

Results, findings and main conclusions

WP4 successfully fostered collaboration and knowledge exchange by establishing and coordinating two Societal Challenges Working Groups under Task 4.1. The implementation of the Action Plans, as outlined in D4.1, led to tangible outcomes in networking, research collaboration, and funding exploration.

Key achievements include:

- 🌐 **Structured governance and coordination:** Each SCWG operated under a governance team that ensured the effective execution of the Action Plan, holding regular meetings to track progress and align objectives.
- 🌐 **Definition of common working areas:** By March-April 2024, the groups identified shared priorities, streamlining their focus on key societal challenges.
- 🌐 **Networking and collaboration:** Multiple in-person and online networking events facilitated interactions among group members, enabling the development of new project proposals. Significant milestones included the Gran Canaria Summer School (July 2024) and the Terceira meeting in February 2024.
- 🌐 **Exploration of funding opportunities:** Members actively sought financing opportunities aligned with their thematic focus, particularly during the June and September-October 2024 meetings.
- 🌐 **Implementation of online networking events:** Between November 2024 and January 2025, four online networking events were successfully organized, enhancing connectivity and collaboration across institutions.
- 🌐 **Final Consolidation and impact:** The culminating face-to-face meetings in Gran Canaria (March 2025) reinforced partnerships and solidified project proposals, ensuring a lasting impact beyond the WP4 framework.

- Overall, WP4 effectively established a collaborative framework that strengthened research and innovation strategies, fostering long-term synergies among stakeholders and increasing the potential for societal impact.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Chart of the planned meetings (blue colour) and implemented monthly meetings (black dots):

SCWG Objectives	2024												2025		
	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March		
Obj 1 Management: Successful development of the SCWG management tasks to achieve goals within the set scope, time, quality and budget specifications.	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•		
Obj 2 Focusing: Selecting key research fields and subjects	•	•													
Obj 3 Networking: Establishment of networks between the widening and the leading actors to build consortia				•	•			•	•	•	•	•	•		
Obj 4 Implementation: fostering the participation of joint research projects in European R&D&I programmes				•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•		
Obj 5 Dissemination: Disseminating SCWG activities	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•		

Table 21. Activity: Action Plans. Focusing.

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Action Plan Implementation. Objective 2: Focusing Activity from Month 18 to Month 19</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	ITC
WP	WP4
Associated task/s	Task 4.2 Implementation of Societal Challenges Action Plans
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser and facilitator
Number of participants (if applicable)	4 researchers
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>WP4 aims at sharing research & innovation strategies to create impact for society. For this purpose, 2 “societal challenges working groups” were established and coordinated under Task 4.1. Each working groups counts with an Action Plan delivered under D4.1 Societal Challenges working groups and thematic action plans, handed in March 2024.</p> <p>The 4 researchers (2 from ULPGC and 2 from UAc), with the support of the facilitators, were in charge of defining the working areas of each of the groups in line with:</p>	

- The EU Missions in Horizon Europe.
- Adapted to the Canary Islands and Azores RIS3.
- Contributions to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and solutions to societal challenges affecting peripheral areas.
- The challenges of the ULPGC and UAC surrounding ecosystems identified under WP1.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Online meetings and working documents.

Results, findings and main conclusions

SCWG 1, “Adaptation to Climate Change in the blue and/or circular economy”, main research areas are:

- Biodiversity conservation and protection Environmental impacts
- Sustainable environmental policy and governance
- Sustainable land and sea use planning and ecosystem services
- Green infrastructures
- Education and raising awareness
- Coastal and Marine Socio-ecological systems
- New tools, techniques and technology for the marine and coastal socio-environmental management
- Strategies for adaptative management

SCWG 2, “Restore our Ocean and Waters in the blue and/or circular economy”, main research areas are:

- Marine Biodiversity Conservation
- Marine Pollution Prevention and Control
- Sustainable Fisheries Management/Aquaculture
- Climate Change Adaptation and Resilience
- Marine Spatial Planning
- Community Engagement and Empowerment
- Education and Awareness-raising
- Scientific Research and Monitoring
- International Cooperation and Partnerships
- Policy and Governance

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

The detailed research areas are included in the D4.1 Societal Challenges working groups and thematic action plans.

Main proposed research project areas:

Table 22. Activity: Action Plan Implementation Networking

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Action Plan Implementation. Objective 3: Networking Activity from Month 21 to Month 30</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	ITC
WP	WP4
Associated task/s	Task 4.2 Implementation of Societal Challenges Action Plans
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser and facilitator. Attendee: ULPGC; EMERGE, UAc, UNICAL, and other institutions and researchers.
Number of participants (if applicable)	About 80 (speakers + attendants)
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>WP4 aims at sharing research & innovation strategies to create impact for society. For this purpose, 2 “societal challenges working groups” were established and coordinated under Task 4.1. Each working groups counts with an Action Plan delivered under D4.1 Societal Challenges working groups and thematic action plans, handed in March 2024.</p>	

In order to promote the chosen research areas of importance for the peripheral partners, and with the objective to establish potential cooperation among them and also with the leading universities a set of activities are included in the Objective 3 of the Action Plan (Networking):

- A) Online seminars
- B) In-place meetings

The activities developed are:

- A) Online seminars: "Bridging Excellence among Peripheral Regions"

Each of the four involved Universities presented their main research strands and projects on the fields related to the EXPER Societal Challenges Working Groups: Adaptation to Climate Change in the Blue and/or Circular Economy (SCWG 1) and Restoring Our Oceans and Waters in the Blue and/or Circular Economy (SCWG 2).

The objective of the Online Seminars, was enhancing the potential collaborations among the EXPER project participant regions, with focus on:

- Presentation of ongoing Research strand/projects;
- Identification of new research projects to address societal challenges;
- Preparation of joint research projects under Horizon Europe calls, aligned with the identified research areas.

Researchers, SMEs, and stakeholders with relevant expertise were invited to join these Online Seminars, which were designed to foster networking among experts with a high commitment to submitting project proposals for EU funding. The EXPER project will provide full support for these proposals

The online seminars took place in zoom, with the presentations from:

- December 4th 2024, University of Azores (UAC).
- December 12th 2024, University of Rostock (UROS).
- January 9th 2025, University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC).
- January 21st 2025, University of Calabria (UNICAL).

- B) In-place meetings

These meetings took place in the frame of other face-to-face EXPER events. The Chair researchers were invited to participate in the events where the societal challenges were addressed and counted with relevant stakeholders as other researchers, representatives of business sectors or policy makers.

In line with this, the following face-to-face meetings were meaningful for them:

- Summer School in Gran Canaria, July 2024. The 4 chairs researchers from ULPGC and UAC, as well as other ULPGC researchers had the opportunity to meet with invited speakers as Jelena Pantel from University of Franche-Comté (France), Manuel Amarin from the company Sustain Azores, and other event participants. Thanks to the B2B meetings, a cooperation project was established and new others can be set.
- Addressing Blue and Green R&D Priorities, regional event in Terceira, February 2025. The 4 chair researchers had the opportunity to meet with companies and technology-based spin-offs incubated at the partner premises of TERINOV. Also, 2 more researchers from ULPGC joined: Mr. Lorenzo Carlos Quesada Ruiz and Mrs. Joana Barcelos e Ramos. Thanks to the B2B meetings, new projects and cooperation can be set.
- EXPER final conference, Gran Canaria, March 2025. The 2 chair researchers from ULPGC met in person the invited speakers with relevant projects promoters as well as policy makers.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

- 🌐 Online presentations.
- 🌐 Online and in place meetings

Results, findings and main conclusions

- 🌐 Same research areas are focused from different perspectives.
- 🌐 Face to face meeting are needed in order to set new collaborations

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

EXPER HEIs. Online seminars. Bridging Excellence among Peripheral Regions

UNICAL Seminar: <https://exper-project.eu/events-page/university-of-calabria-showcases-solutions-for-climate-change-and-ocean-restoration-at-exper-project-webinar/>

ULPGC Seminar: <https://exper-project.eu/events-page/university-of-las-palmas-de-gran-canaria-showcases-sustainability-solutions-at-exper-project-webinar/>

UROS Seminar: <https://exper-project.eu/events-page/university-of-rostock-tackles-sustainability-challenges-at-exper-project-seminar/>

UAc Seminar: <https://exper-project.eu/events-page/university-of-the-azores-hosts-exper-project-seminar-bridging-excellence-for-a-sustainable-future/>

General dissemination: <https://exper-project.eu/exper-project-invites-you-to-online-seminars-bridging-excellence-in-peripheral-regions/>

Table 23. Activity: Action Plan Implementation. Implementation.

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Action Plan Implementation. Objective 4: Implementation Activity from Month 21 to Month 30</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		ITC
WP		WP4
Associated task/s		Task 4.2 Implementation of Societal Challenges Action Plans
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser and facilitator	
Number of participants (if applicable)	More than 200	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>WP4 aims at sharing research & innovation strategies to create impact for society. For this purpose, 2 “societal challenges working groups” were established and coordinated under Task 4.1. Each working groups counts with an Action Plan delivered under D4.1 Societal Challenges working groups and thematic action plans, handed in March 2024.</p> <p>The Action Plans involves several objective, including Objective 4: fostering the participation of joint research projects in European R&D&I programmes, divided into 4 tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.1 Identifying funding opportunities 4.2 Building potential consortiums to develop new research proposals 4.3 Involvement of the business sector in the group 4.4 Organization of Summer Schools, international seminar and attending to conferences in line with the selected research topics (More information about Gran Canaria Summer School and Azores Summer School is fully detailed in another activity file). 4.5 Capacity building plan <p>Both task 4.1 and 4.2 has been implemented hand in hand, since the potential project proposals must be in line with the funding opportunities.</p> <p>Tasks 4.3, 4.4 and 4.5 were also aligned. On one hand the capacities identified by the Universities as key topics were included in EXPER events as Summer Schools, while representatives of the business sector were also part of the same events.</p> <p>The whole objective 4 of the Action Plans was set to support concrete and valuable networking that could end with potential and relevant project proposal that could apply to Horizon Europe funding opportunities.</p> <p>In order to achieve the objectives, during the implementation period, the researchers were in constant communication to try building – up new project proposals.</p> <p>Also, on the different face to face EXPER project events, the Chair researchers could find opportunities to integrate their contributions for solutions to the societal challenges. Both ‘Gran Canaria Summer School’ in July 2025 and regional event in Terceira ‘Adressing Blue and Green R&D Priorities’ in February 2025 had a high relevance. Researchers could meet face to face not only with researchers but with other stakeholders who share their mind-set towards contributing to solutions for the challenges to adapting to climate change and restoring oceans.</p> <p>At the same hand, ITC and Consulta Europa, informed frequently about the funding opportunities in line with the topics on circular and blue economy in order to find matching with the project ideas they had in mind.</p>		

Several meetings took place among CE, ITC, ULPGC and UAc, in order to inform that the working period, from October to December, did not seem to be the best to prepare a concrete project proposal due to the lack of calls opened in relation to the interesting topics.

After all the activities, some project proposals have been focused at different level:

- **1 project proposal submitted** to funds under the EIT HEI Initiative 2024 <https://eit-hei.eu/calls/previous-calls/call-for-proposals-4/>
EXPER partners involved: ULPGC, UAc, UNICAL, CE.
Short summary: The proposal allows higher education institutions (HEIs) and business partners to collaborate on innovative projects, transforming HEIs into hubs for innovation and entrepreneurship. Concretely, the project is structured around the following pillars: Pillar I: Strengthening Ecosystem Collaboration; Pillar II: Empowering Innovators; Pillar III: Accelerating Technology Transfer.

- **1 project proposal ready to be submitted** under Twinning call CORE - CLIMATE OCEAN REVERSIBILITY
EXPER partners involved: ULPGC (One of the Chair Researchers of the EXPER SCWGs has been supported – Dr. Rodrigo Riera).
Short summary: The CORE Twinning proposal aims at stimulating scientific excellence and innovation capacity in a defined area of research and innovation (climate-ocean science) of a Widening coordinating institution, namely ULPGC.
Status of development: the proposal has been prepared but not submitted since the new Twinning Call for 2025 is not yet published. The call of reference for the drafting of the proposal has been the latest (2023) Twinning call available on the EU Funding and Tenders Portal (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-widera-2023-access-02-02>). The new Twinning call for 2025 is expected to be published in the next months, probably after the end of the EXPER project.

- **1 project proposal in progress** under ERC starting grant
EXPER partner involved: ULPGC (One of the Chair Researchers of the EXPER SCWGs has been supported – Dr. Leví García-Romero).
Short summary: The age of the Canary Islands archipelago is not the same as that of the continents, but they were formed much later (20-12 million years ago). The emersion of the islands from the ocean floor by volcanic processes (hotspot archipelago) makes their coastal relief mainly abrupt and rocky, explaining at the same time the reduced prominence of aeolian sedimentary systems, especially dune systems (DS). The project will explore how the sedimentary dynamics associated with the SDs of the Canary Islands function and which at the same time would be useful for taking environmental management measures in the current context of Climate Change.
Status of development: the proposal will be submitted to ERC, which is the premier European funding organisation for excellent frontier research (<https://erc.europa.eu/homepage>). The new ERC calls for 2026 are expected to be published between July and October, probably after the end of the EXPER project.

- **3 project ideas under** calls to be identified in the framework of Interreg MAC or Horizon Europe calls.
Project partners interested: UAc, ULPGC, OKEANOS (UAc research group), Biotechnology Center of Azores (CBA), Sustain Azores (Azorean SME) other partners to be searched in Canary Islands, Azores and Cape Verde or other regions according to the calls.
Project idea 1. Short summary: modelling of waste and discharges, for understanding the impact on the coast and its negative influence. It is necessary to explore the coastline on two fronts: first, the deep ocean zone, and then inland. It is important to monitor these areas at defined scales.
Project idea 2. Short summary: Enhancement of landscapes on abandoned agricultural lands, such as vineyards. This situation is common not only in the Azores and the Canary Islands, but also in other steep agricultural areas outside of Macaronesia.
Project idea 3. Short summary: Intertidal zone research on habitat fragmentation: interaction and balance of fauna in the defined area. Biological and morphological study. Study of temporal evolution.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

- Online presentations.
- Online and in place meetings.

Results, findings and main conclusions

- 🌍 To foster project proposals to emerge, it is needed that a person with double technical and funding knowledge is involved.
- 🌍 Usually, researchers want to conduct research with their solid networks; it is not easy to establish new cooperation among unknown individuals.
- 🌍 New project proposals required time and deep knowledge about the financing opportunities.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Gran Canaria Summer School, July 2024. Meeting with the 4 chair researchers to foster project proposals:

<https://exper-project.eu/the-exper-projects-core-societal-challenges-working-groups-set-strategic-course-at-gran-canaria-summer-school/>

<https://exper-project.eu/exper-summer-school-concluded-in-gran-canaria/>

<https://exper-project.eu/open-science-and-communication-technology-transfer-and-proposal-writing-for-excellent-research-and-innovation/>

<https://exper-project.eu/the-summer-school-of-the-exper-project-will-reinforce-the-knowledge-and-the-writing-of-proposals-for-horizon-europe-in-gran-canaria/>

Addressing Blue and Green R&D Priorities', Terceira regional event, February 2025.

<https://exper-project.eu/terinov-event-bridges-gap-between-academia-business-and-society-in-blue-and-green-ri/>

<https://exper-project.eu/events-page/exper-regional-event-in-terceira-island/>

Table 24. Activity: InvestigaFest

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>InvestigaFest</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s		ULPGC
WP		WP4
Associated task/s		Task 4.3 Transversal skills for excellent and responsible research
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser: ULPGC, Facilitators/speakers: ULPGC, Assistant: Institutions, ULPGC staff, FPCT staff, students, researchers.	
Number of participants (if applicable)	81	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>Investigafest is the inaugural edition of an event aimed at creating a relaxed environment where researchers from various disciplines can connect and foster future collaborations. Through a range of activities such as organised meetings, round tables, inspirational speeches, open mic sessions, etc., the event serves as a platform for proactive connections and future partnerships among researchers from different disciplines.</p> <p>To facilitate this networking, a specific tool (b2match) was made available months prior to the event to organise meetings. This tool employed a series of filters to suggest connections and meetings between researchers, allowing ULPGC to previously prepare rooms during the event for holding these meeting sessions.</p> <p>Fruitful meetings were conducted between experts in several pivotal and multidisciplinary fields. To promote the use of this tool, an email campaign was developed among the registered users.</p> <p>For participants who did not get to establish a match beforehand, the activity “<i>Connect the Thesis</i>” was created, which featured an open mic where authors of last two years awarded thesis at ULPGC had the opportunity to briefly present their work. If any audience member expressed interest in knowing more and wished to arrange a subsequent meeting, they could raise designated posters we prepared for this purpose, thereby encouraging a more spontaneous connection.</p> <p>In addition, during the event, inspiring talks and round tables were conducted on the themes of interdisciplinary collaboration, successful stories, and the benefits of forming multidisciplinary consortia for European projects.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
B2March application, physical elements to provide comfort to the attendees. Facilities, stage, screens, sound, catering,		
Results, findings, and main conclusions		
Investigafest was highly successful in achieving its goal of fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and strengthening the research ecosystem within the Canary Islands. The event’s innovative structure and carefully designed activities generated meaningful outcomes for the research community:		

- Successful use of the Networking tool: The b2match platform facilitated targeted networking between researchers from various fields. Participants were able to identify common research interests and initiate discussions on potential future projects. The platform's filter-based suggestions ensured that meetings were efficient and relevant, contributing to a high level of participant satisfaction.
- Productive B2B Meetings: The pre-scheduled one-on-one meetings enabled researchers to engage in focused conversations, resulting in the identification of several promising areas for future research collaborations. These meetings established a foundation for ongoing interdisciplinary projects.
- Impact of the "Connect the Thesis" session: This session provided a platform for showcasing award-winning doctoral research. The interactive format, where audience members could express interest in collaborating with presenters, facilitated spontaneous and organic connections. Several participants reported that this session led to concrete plans for follow-up meetings and potential joint research projects.
- Engagement and knowledge exchange: The round tables and inspirational talks offered valuable insights into the benefits and challenges of interdisciplinary collaboration. Successful case studies presented during these sessions served as motivation for participants to explore new research partnerships.
- Community building and informal networking: The relaxed atmosphere created by the social elements of the event, including the lunch, food trucks, and live music by "The Teachers," fostered informal exchanges and strengthened the sense of community among researchers. This setting encouraged deeper conversations and the building of lasting professional relationships.
- Satisfaction questionnaire: A satisfaction questionnaire was sent to all registrants, from which we obtained 27 responses with the following data and conclusions.
 - **96.3%** of participants would attend another edition.
 - **100%** would recommend the event to colleagues.
 - **96.3%** believe the event fosters interdisciplinary collaboration.
 - **74.1%** established connections with researchers from other disciplines:
 - 37.0% discussed specific projects.
 - 37.0% engaged in networking.
 - **48.1%** obtained valuable results from meetings.
 - **29.6%** did not attend meetings.

InvestigaFEST effectively promoted interdisciplinary interaction, with nearly three-quarters of attendees establishing connections with researchers from different fields. Moreover, almost half of the participants reported obtaining valuable outcomes from their meetings, such as initiating research discussions or meeting potential collaborators. However, a small percentage either did not participate in meetings or did not find them helpful. Future editions could encourage more structured matchmaking or follow-up sessions to enhance collaboration opportunities.

In short, INVESTIGAFEST successfully combined structured networking with informal engagement, creating a balanced and stimulating environment for researchers to connect, exchange ideas, and lay the groundwork for future interdisciplinary collaborations. The event's positive reception underscores its potential to become a key fixture in the Canary Islands' research calendar.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

- Some photos of the event are included below:

2.5. WP5 – CONNECTION WITH BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT: KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER AND SPIN-OFFS

Table 25. Activity: Workshop for Researchers Capacity Building – ULPGC: Sessions 1 & 2

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Workshop for Researchers Capacity Building – ULPGC: Sessions 1 & 2</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	ATRINEO
WP	WP5
Associated task/s	T5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Trainer: ATRINEO; Facilitator: ULPGC
Number of participants (if applicable)	Session 1/2: 15; Session 2/2: 9
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>The Capacity Building Training for Researchers was designed to equip scientists with the knowledge and tools necessary to bridge the gap between research and market-driven innovation. Conducted over two days in the ULPGC premises, the event focused on fostering the skills required to transform scientific research into practical, impactful ideas and entrepreneurial ventures.</p> <p>The training provided participants with a clear understanding of innovation in the context of scientific research, exploring its definition, practical application, and importance in addressing real-world challenges. Through structured sessions on ideation, the program highlighted the processes that drive innovation and emphasized the critical role of creativity in translating research into market-ready solutions. Market orientation served as a central theme of the training, underscoring its significance in identifying and prioritising opportunities that align with market needs. Participants were introduced to essential tools and methodologies for validating innovations, using data and market analysis to ensure the feasibility and potential impact of their ideas. The agenda included hands-on exercises on market segmentation and sizing, which allowed attendees to apply these concepts in practical scenarios.</p> <p>The program also introduced the fundamentals of startup creation and business models, tailored to the unique challenges and opportunities faced by science-based enterprises. By the end of the training, participants gained a comprehensive understanding of the pathways from research to innovation.</p> <p>Two editions of the training workshop were held for ULPGC staff due to high demand: the first on 19-20 June 2024 and the second on 10-11 July 2024, with each edition lasting 12 hours over two days.</p>	
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)	
Workshop slides in PowerPoint format.	
Results, findings and main conclusions	
24 certified participants in the core elements of innovation, knowledge and technology transfer and management. Workshop material on innovation, knowledge and technology transfer was provided to ULPGC	
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)	

 Some photos of the training workshops given by ATRINEO:

Table 26. Activity: Capacity Building Workshops on Innovation, Technology Transfer, and IPM for Researchers and TTO Staff – UAc

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Capacity Building Workshops on Innovation, Technology Transfer, and IPM for Researchers and TTO Staff – UAc</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		ATRINEO
WP		WP5
Associated task/s		T5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Trainer: ATRINEO; Facilitator: UAc; Attendee: UAc, TERINOV	
Number of participants (if applicable)	Researchers: 12; TTO Staff: 6	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>As part of the capacity building initiatives under the EXPER project, two complementary training workshops were delivered to researchers and Technology Transfer Office (TTO) staff at the UAc. These workshops aimed to enhance the skills and knowledge necessary to bridge the gap between research, innovation, and market-driven opportunities, while strengthening the institutional capacity to manage intellectual property and technology transfer processes effectively.</p> <p>The first workshop, held on the 12th and 13th of November 2024, focused on building the capacity of researchers to transform scientific research into practical, market-oriented solutions and entrepreneurial ventures. The sessions covered key topics such as innovation processes in research, ideation techniques, market validation, and business model development tailored to science-based initiatives. Through interactive exercises and practical case studies, researchers gained hands-on experience in identifying innovation potential and aligning their work with market needs.</p> <p>The second workshop, held on the 3rd of December 2024, was specifically designed for TTO staff, equipping them with essential tools and strategies to manage intellectual property, evaluate technology transfer opportunities, and apply practical solutions in real-world scenarios. Participants explored strategies to align IP management with institutional goals, assess the commercialization potential of new technologies, and implement effective knowledge and technology transfer strategies through case-based learning and expert-led discussions.</p>		

Both workshops provided comprehensive training materials, ensuring participants could revisit the content and apply the concepts to their institutional and professional contexts.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Workshop slides in PowerPoint format, Zoom video platform.

Results, findings and main conclusions

- A total of 17 participants (12 researchers and 5 TTO staff) completed the training programs and received certification.
- Participants gained practical knowledge and tools in innovation management, intellectual property strategies, market validation, technology assessment, and technology transfer processes.
- The training equipped researchers with a clear understanding of how to move from research outputs to innovation opportunities, fostering greater awareness of the importance of market orientation and entrepreneurial approaches within academic environments.
- TTO staff acquired hands-on experience in evaluating potential technology transfer cases, prioritizing opportunities with high commercialization potential, and aligning intellectual property strategies with institutional and regional development goals.

Both workshops contributed to strengthening the overall innovation ecosystem at UAc, promoting better collaboration between researchers and technology transfer professionals.

All training materials were provided to UAc for future reference and potential internal use in future capacity building initiatives.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

- Some photos of the training workshops, given by ATRINEO:

Table 27. Activity: Workshops - Strengthening Market-Oriented strategies and technology transfer at UAc

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Workshops - Strengthening Market-Oriented strategies and technology transfer at UAc</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		UAc (InUAc)
WP		WP5
Associated task/s		T5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	InUAc: Organiser	
Number of participants (if applicable)	Workshop 1 - Brand Strategy: ~ 10; Workshop 2 - Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property: ~ 60	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The UAc organized two strategic workshops aimed at strengthening the university's capacity for technology transfer and improving the market-oriented approach of its research and business ecosystem. These workshops, coordinated by the Technology-Based Business Incubator of the University of the Azores (InUAc) with the support of the American Corner, provided valuable insights and practical tools to enhance participants' expertise in key areas such as brand strategy, intellectual property, and technology transfer.</p> <p> <u>Workshop 1: Brand Strategy</u></p> <p>The first workshop on Brand Strategy took place at the InUAc Training Lab on the campus of Ponta Delgada in November 2024. It was led by Ricardo Freitas, founder of Rebola Caixotes - Brand Expert. The workshop focused on equipping participants with the skills necessary to create a strong and impactful brand identity in the market. Over the course of four sessions totalling 12 hours, 10 trainees, including InUAc incubators and employees from regional companies such as Yoçor and Marques Group, participated in dynamic discussions and hands-on exercises. The workshop encouraged an active exchange of knowledge and ideas among participants, fostering innovative thinking and improving their ability to develop competitive brands.</p>		

Workshop 2: Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property

The second workshop on Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property was organized within the scope of the Knowledge Transfer and Enhancement Center at UAc. It aimed to raise awareness within the academic community about the importance of transferring technology to the market and protecting intellectual property rights. The workshop was held at the InUAc Training Lab and featured guest speakers from Instituto Pedro Nunes (IPN), including Jorge Pimenta (IPN's Innovation Director) and José Aguilar (IPN's Head of Legal). The session targeted university researchers, PhD students, and members of the university's incubator, providing valuable insights into technology transfer strategies, intellectual property management, and the importance of aligning university research with market needs. This initiative reinforced the university's commitment to fulfilling its third mission: transferring knowledge to the market.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Slides, Roll up, online and presentational session, questionnaire of satisfaction, certificate of participation.

Results, findings and main conclusions

- **Brand Strategy Workshop:** Participants acquired essential skills in brand development and digital marketing, equipping them with tools to strengthen their brand positioning and market impact. The workshop fostered a collaborative environment where ideas were exchanged, and participants benefited from the insights of an experienced brand expert.
- **Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property Workshop:** The workshop increased awareness of the importance of technology transfer and intellectual property within the academic community. Participants gained a deeper understanding of how to translate research outcomes into market-ready products and the legal frameworks necessary to protect intellectual assets. This activity reinforced the university's role as a driver of innovation and market-oriented research.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

- Some photos of the workshops organised by InUAc:

Table 28. Activity: Colloquium on Innovation and internationalisation

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Colloquium on Innovation and internationalisation with ICEX Director</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	FCPCT, ULPGC
WP	WP5 and WP7
Associated task/s	Task 5.1 Capacity building on technology transfer and market-driven activities and Task 7.4 Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator: FCPCT; Organization of the activity: ULPGC
Number of participants (if applicable)	28
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>As part of the EXPER project initiatives in the Canary Islands, startups and businesses within the entrepreneurial ecosystem of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) engaged in a productive dialogue with José María Blasco Ruiz, Director of Infrastructures, Health, and ICT at ICEX. This event, aligning with WP5 focused on business environment connection and knowledge transfer, and WP7 focused on outreach, was held to foster interaction between the university's spin-offs and ICEX's internationalization initiatives.</p> <p>During the colloquium, Blasco shared valuable insights into ICEX's initiatives supporting entrepreneurship, innovation, and internationalization. He highlighted opportunities such as participation in international fairs, commercial missions, and the Desafia programme, which offers a two-week immersion in diverse multi-sector destinations like San Francisco, Berlin, London, Singapore, and the Nordic countries. These initiatives aim to enhance the global reach and scalability of startups.</p> <p>The event, chaired by ULPGC's Vice-Rector for Research and Transfer, Sebastián López, and led by María José Miranda, Director of Scientific Infrastructures and Relations with Companies at ULPGC, emphasized the importance of international market opportunities for the university's entrepreneurial ventures. The discussion also involved key participants such as Loreto Taborga, Territorial Director of Commerce and ICEX Delegate in Las Palmas, and María Josefa Padrón, Managing Director of the Canarian Foundation Science and Technology Park of ULPGC, where the colloquium took place on February 21 (2024).</p> <p>The primary objective of this activity was to strengthen the connection between the entrepreneurial ecosystem associated with ULPGC and ICEX, with the aim of providing entrepreneurs, start-ups, spin-offs and other stakeholders in the Canary Islands region with firsthand knowledge of the resources and opportunities that ICEX offers in this field.</p>	
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)	
On-site meeting, tailored slides, institutional facilitators and representatives, open colloquium.	
Results, findings, and main conclusions	
The ICEX colloquium with the ULPGC entrepreneurial ecosystem strengthened the connection between local startups and spin-offs with ICEX resources, highlighting international opportunities and support programs like "Desafia". Participants gained key information about participation criteria and showed increased interest in engaging with ICEX initiatives.	
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)	

Some photos taken during the Colloquium with ICEX:

Table 29. Activity: Staff Exchange

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Staff Exchange with KIT (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology)</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s		FCPCT-ULPGC, ATRINEO
WP		WP5
Associated task/s		Task 5.2 Exchanges of staff and good practices on IPR management
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Activity facilitator and organization: FCPCT-ULPGC, ATRINEO. Attendee: ITC	
Number of participants (if applicable)	4	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>From June 12 to June 13, 2024, a delegation from the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) visited the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) in Germany to explore KIT's pioneering work in knowledge transfer, particularly within the realms of innovation and sustainability. The visit was strategically aligned with the "Innovation Day in Neuland" event at KIT, which emphasized innovations contributing to a greener, more digital, and healthier future in line with the EU's sustainability goals. The ULPGC delegation, participating under the Exper project, included representatives from the university's Knowledge Transfer Office (OTC), ITC (Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias), and ATRINEO AG. The exchange focused on sharing best practices in intellectual property rights (IPR) management and exploring potential future collaborations between ULPGC and KIT.</p> <p>The principal objectives of this activity were to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance the application of ULPGC's research in the market, supporting the development of start-ups and fostering innovation and entrepreneurship within the Canary Islands. 		

- Provide ULPGC's delegation with exposure to cutting-edge research and innovative practices at KIT, thereby informing and improving their own knowledge transfer initiatives.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

On-site meetings, oral presentations.

Results, findings, and main conclusions

The visit to KIT provided valuable insights into several of its key initiatives. The intrapreneurship program at KIT, which focuses on maximizing the impact of each employee, was particularly noteworthy. This program not only facilitates knowledge transfer but also empowers employees to influence various dimensions, including basic research. The TRIANGEL initiative was another highlight, offering a versatile space that serves both entrepreneurs and the public, fostering citizen science and science dissemination. However, it was noted that the initiative currently faces staffing challenges.

The relationship between KIT and local companies, bolstered by a strong alumni network, stood out as a significant advantage. In contrast to the Canary Islands, where connections between researchers and companies often rely on intermediary organizations, the collaborations in Karlsruhe are more organic and spontaneous. This difference underscores the varying levels of innovation maturity between the two regions, with Karlsruhe being an "innovation leader" and the Canary Islands an "emerging" region.

Overall, the exchange reinforced the importance of strategic collaboration, the role of innovation spaces, and the potential of tailored intrapreneurship programs. It also highlighted the need for ULPGC to explore similar initiatives to enhance its own innovation ecosystem and strengthen ties between academia and industry.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos taken during the staff exchange with KIT:

Table 30. Activity: Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Management and Technology Transfer Support for ULPGC & UAc

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Management and Technology Transfer Support for ULPGC & UAc</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	ATRINEO
WP	WP5
Associated task/s	T5.2 Exchanges of staff and good practices on IPR management
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Trainer: ATRINEO
Number of participants (if applicable)	N/A
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>Atrineo AG provided strategic support to both the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) and the University of the Azores (UAc) to enhance their intellectual property rights (IPR) management capabilities and to improve the potential for successful technology transfer and commercialization. The support was tailored to the specific needs of each institution, focusing on key patents within their respective portfolios.</p> <p> Market analysis with forecasts and competitor analysis 	

- Identification of market trends
- Detailed transfer assessment

This analysis ensured a thorough understanding of the patent's commercialisation potential and provided a structured pathway for its exploitation. The results of the assessment was delivered to UAc by the end of February 2025.

Atrineo's tailored support to both ULPGC and UAc strengthened their capacity to manage intellectual property, evaluate commercialization opportunities, and align technology transfer activities with market needs.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Assessment was written and prepared using Microsoft Office Suite (Word, Excel, and PowerPoint). Data was collected through the use of restricted-access market databases and analysis platforms.

Results, findings and main conclusions

 Results for ULPGC

The patent shows significant innovative potential in a growing market. According to our study, there is currently no system on the global market comparable to the one proposed by this patent. Additionally, the inventors have already garnered interest from various market players.

However, two strategic decisions must be made before moving forward with commercialisation: whether to create a spin-off or license the invention to a third party and determining the countries in which to extend patent protection. These decisions will shape the subsequent steps in the commercialization roadmap. In addition to these strategic decisions, several steps must be completed before commercialization can take place.

The invention has not yet been tested in real-world environments, meaning its presumed benefits have not been validated. This will require further technical development and securing funding to build functional prototypes.

Finally, the invention will need to undergo regulatory certification, a lengthy and costly process that has not yet been initiated.

 Results for UAc

Although the technology holds moderate innovative potential and could present a commercialisation opportunity with further development and refinement, two major limitations significantly hinder its transfer potential: limited patent protection and a short timeframe until patent expiration.

Currently, the patent is valid only in Portugal, which severely restricts its geographical scope to a market with insufficient potential to justify the high investment and development costs required to transform the technology into a market-ready product. Expanding the patent protection to an EU-wide scope would substantially increase its commercial viability, opening access to a larger and more lucrative market.

Additionally, the patent is set to expire in 2032, leaving only seven years of protection from the current date (2025). Human healthcare technologies often require extensive regulatory approvals and safety testing, which involve significant investment and take several years to complete. These processes typically consume a substantial portion of the patent exclusivity period. With only seven years remaining, there is insufficient time to both meet regulatory requirements and capitalise on exclusivity through commercial sales. This short exclusivity period makes it unattractive for potential investors or product developers, who prioritise technologies with longer patent durations to ensure a sufficient return on investment after covering development and compliance costs.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

 ULPGC

Roadmap patent TRAINIRS – Blood Flow Restriction - If the document in question does not contain confidential technology information, pre-patent content, or confidential know-how, and the cooperation partners agree with the sharing of content, then this document will be made available as part of the deliverable "D5.2. Commercialisation summary report on individual technology and spin-off cases piloted during the project detailing activities, findings and commercial roadmap".

 UAc

Transfer Assessment for Patent PT106522A - This document will be made available as part of the deliverable "D5.2. Commercialisation summary report on individual technology and spin-off cases piloted during the project detailing activities, findings and commercial roadmap".

Table 31. Activity: MetaRedX International Exchange Program

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>MetaRedX International Exchange Program</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		UAc (InUAc)
WP		WP5
Associated task/s		T5.2 Exchanges of staff and good practices on IPR management
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	InUAc: Organiser	
Number of participants (if applicable)	~4 (17 Regional Entrepreneurship Ecosystem)	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The InUAc (Business Incubator of the University of the Azores) team received a delegation from the Universidad Europea de Madrid, represented by the Director of Employability and Entrepreneurship and the responsible for Entrepreneurship, between 27 and 31 May 2024. This visit took place within the framework of the MetaRedX International Exchange Program, a network that InUAc integrates as a member of the Executive Committee in Portugal and Coordinator of the Entrepreneurship Ecosystems Working Group.</p> <p>The objective of this program was to foster the exchange and sharing of experiences and good practices among the members of the teams of the entrepreneurship management units of the universities that are part of MetaRedX.</p> <p>In order to know the work developed by InUAc and the regional entrepreneurship ecosystem, internal meetings were held for the sharing of good practices, as well as meetings with incubators, Mentors, spinoffs, researchers and teachers in the area of UAc entrepreneurship. The articulation with the ecosystem occurred with visits and meetings with NONAGON, the Regional Board of Entrepreneurship and Competitiveness and with the companies Plantation of Tea Gorreana and Algicel.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Slides; meetings with incubators, entrepreneurship teachers and researchers; visit to UAc laboratories and research centers; visits to the regional entrepreneurship ecosystem (companies, spinoff UAc, science and technology parks, government/Regional Network of Incubators, etc.).		
Results, findings and main conclusions		

It was an excellent opportunity to establish professional contacts, exchange good practices and gain new perspectives to strengthen the entrepreneurial culture in UAc, bringing tangible benefits and promoting sustainable and intelligent development in the Azores.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

 Some photos taken during the event:

Table 32. Activity: Spin-off Supporting Services for ULPGC & UAc

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Spin-off Supporting Services for ULPGC & UAc</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		ATRINEO
WP		WP5
Associated task/s		T5.3 Piloting Spin-off Supporting Services
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Trainer: ATRINEO	
Number of participants (if applicable)	N/A	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>Under the Spin-off Supporting Services initiative, Atrineo AG provided strategic and operational support to two early-stage spin-offs at the ULPGC and UAc, aiming to advance their business models and prepare them for market entry. The objective was to strengthen the innovation ecosystem within the Widening HEIs by transforming early-stage ideas into structured and viable business ventures.</p> <p> Market study – Analysis of market trends, competitive landscape, and customer demand.</p>		

- 🌐 Marketing plan – Strategies for customer acquisition, branding, and market positioning.
- 🌐 Production and investment plans – Operational requirements, capital needs, and cost structure.
- 🌐 Financial projections – Profit and loss statements, cash flow forecasts, financial ratios, and funding strategies.
- 🌐 Legal framework – Legal structure, intellectual property management, and regulatory considerations.
- 🌐 Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) plan – Integration of sustainability and ethical practices into the business model.

This initiative represents a structured approach to transforming early-stage research outcomes into a scalable commercial enterprise, ensuring Blue Restoration is well-positioned for market success.

🌐 **Support for UAc**

Atrineo AG provided tailored support to Biotech Synergy during its foundational phase as an early-stage startup at UAc. The consulting services focused on building a solid business framework and positioning the company for future growth and investment.

Key aspects of the support included:

- 🌐 Defining the core value proposition – Clarifying the unique benefits and solutions offered by Biotech Synergy.
- 🌐 Identifying target customer segments – Conducting market research to assess demand and competition and defining key customer profiles.
- 🌐 Validating product-market fit – Ensuring alignment between the product offering and customer needs.
- 🌐 Developing the business model – Establishing a sustainable revenue model and identifying potential revenue streams.
- 🌐 Creating an initial business roadmap – Outlining the next steps for product development, funding acquisition, and market entry.

Atrineo's strategic input provided Biotech Synergy with a structured pathway toward operational stability and market competitiveness, ensuring the startup is equipped to capitalise on emerging opportunities within the biotech sector.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Assessment was written and prepared using Microsoft Office Suite (Word, Excel, and PowerPoint). Data was collected through the use of restricted-access market databases and analysis platforms. If required, Atrineo conduct surveys and direct interviews with relevant stakeholders to collect primary data.

Results, findings and main conclusions

🌐 **Results for ULPGC**

The goal is for Blue Restoration to become the fourth spin-off of ULPGC. Blue Restoration represents a pivotal initiative dedicated to marine reforestation both within the Canary Islands and internationally. Its mission aligns directly with the Canary Islands' Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS3) in the area of blue economy, underscoring its importance as a key driver of sustainable development and innovation in the region.

By focusing on marine reforestation, Blue Restoration addresses critical environmental challenges while leveraging the unique marine resources of the Canary Islands. This not only reinforces the region's commitment to preserving its natural heritage but also positions it as a leader in the emerging blue economy sector. The company's activities will contribute to ecological restoration, biodiversity conservation, and the promotion of sustainable industries, making it a vital asset for the Canary Islands and beyond.

🌐 **Results for UAc**

Biotech Synergy is uniquely positioned in the Azores region to become one of the most prominent stakeholders in the field of biological sciences, leveraging a combination of local talent, specialised expertise, and strategic proximity to its core customer base. While the startup's primary challenge lies in

effectively convincing potential customers of the strength and relevance of its value proposition, successfully addressing this challenge will enable Biotech Synergy to establish itself as a cornerstone for innovation and a key driver of scientific and commercial advancements in the region. By building strong relationships with local industries and public stakeholders, the company can create a robust ecosystem for collaboration and knowledge exchange in the Azorean region.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

 ULPGC

Business Plan for Blue Restoration - If the document in question does not contain confidential technology information, pre-patented content, or confidential know-how, and the cooperation partners agree with the sharing of content, then this document will be made available as part of the deliverable "D5.3 Commercialisation summary report on individual technology and spin-off cases piloted during the project detailing activities, findings and commercial roadmap "

 UAc

Startup Opportunity Assessment - This document will be made available as part of the deliverable "D5.3 Commercialisation summary report on individual technology and spin-off cases piloted during the project detailing activities, findings and commercial roadmap ".

Table 33. Activity: Start-up Supporting Services for ULPGC

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Start-up Supporting Services for ULPGC</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		ATRINEO
WP		WP5
Associated task/s		T5.3 Piloting Spin-off Supporting Services
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Trainer: ATRINEO	
Number of participants (if applicable)	N/A	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The ULPGC informed its seven start-ups about the option of receiving advisory services from Atrineo. Three of them engaged Atrineo's services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For Fast Free Lane, Atrineo supplied a list of potential industrial partners and investor contacts. <p>These documents were provided to each start-up between September and November 2024.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Assessment was written and prepared using Microsoft Office Suite (Word, Excel, and PowerPoint). Data was collected using restricted-access market databases and analysis platforms.		

Results, findings and main conclusions
<p>Through meetings with the CEOs of the ULPGC start-ups, Atrineo identified their specific needs and agreed on the scope of support for each. The tailored assistance provided by Atrineo addressed key challenges and growth objectives, significantly enhancing the start-ups' market positioning. Atrineo designed bespoke solutions for each start-up based on their individual challenges and growth objectives, ensuring the support provided was both relevant and actionable.</p> <p>The state-of-the-art patent analysis for SubSea Mechatronics highlighted technological gaps and opportunities, guiding their R&D efforts. Similarly, the market study for Rethink Medical revealed key market trends and demand patterns, enabling informed business decisions. The contact lists provided to Rethink Medical and Fast Free Lane facilitated connections with potential investors and industrial partners, opening pathways for collaborations, funding, and scaling opportunities.</p>
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contacts for Fast Free Lane. <p>If the document in question does not contains confidential technology information, pre-patented content, or confidential know-how, and the cooperation partners agree with the sharing of content, then these documents will be made available as part of the deliverable "D5.3 Commercialisation summary report on individual technology and spin-off cases piloted during the project detailing activities, findings and commercial roadmap".</p>

Table 34. Activity: Transfer Knowledge Offices Workdays

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Transfer Knowledge Offices Workdays</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner/s	ULPGC
WP	WP5
Associated task/s	Task 5.3 Piloting Spin-off supporting services
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser: ULPGC Facilitators/speakers: ULPGC, ULL, Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities, the Galician Innovation Agency, Canarian Government, Astrophysics Institute of the Canary Islands. Assistants: Institutions, ULPGC staff, FPCT staff
Number of participants (if applicable)	Day 1 - 7 Nov: 38 Day 2 - 8 Nov: 41
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>The ULPGC carried out two key activities to support spin-off services and knowledge transfer in ULPGC. These activities aimed to facilitate the progression of early-stage ideas/IPR towards commercial propositions by leveraging local and international expertise, engaging stakeholders, and strengthening the regional innovation ecosystem.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Work sessions based on design thinking methodology: This initiative focused on co-creating solutions to enhance knowledge transfer processes in research institutions. Through a structured Design Thinking approach, participants addressed key challenges, such as professionalization, network strengthening, and Technology Transfer Offices (OTCs) visibility. 	

2. **IV Technical Conference on Knowledge Transfer and European Projects in the Canary Islands:** This event gathered over 40 stakeholders from academia, government, and industry to discuss and develop strategies for improving knowledge transfer and spin-off creation. Sessions included thematic working groups, expert panels, and discussions on best practices from other regions (e.g., Galicia's *Oportunius* and *IGNICIA* programs).

These activities contributed to the EXPER project's objectives by identifying pathways to commercialize early-stage ideas, fostering cross-institutional collaboration, and providing insights into sustainable spin-off ecosystems.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Physical elements to provide comfort to the attendees. Facilities, stage, screens, sound, catering, Microsoft power point, materials (blocks, pens, folders).

Results, findings, and main conclusions

 Work sessions based on design thinking methodology:

These sessions resulted in a series of proposals pursuing three objectives:

1. Professionalisation and stabilisation of staff.
2. Networking for knowledge transfer offices in the Canary Islands to optimise resources, share good practices, and promote joint projects.
3. Promotion and communication to increase the visibility and recognition of these offices at a national and international level.

 IV Technical Conference on Knowledge Transfer and European Projects in the Canary Islands

1. **Challenges in Knowledge Transfer and Spin-Off Creation**

- The need to professionalize and stabilize staff in Knowledge Transfer Offices (KTOs) and European Project Offices (EPOs).
- Issues related to talent retention and preventing the loss of knowledge from research institutions.
- The necessity of increasing the visibility of KTOs and their services at a national and international level.

2. **Best Practices and strategic insights**

- **Learning from Galicia's model:** Programs like *Oportunius* (focused on talent attraction and retention) and *IGNICIA* (supporting the market transfer of R&D results) provided valuable examples for improving spin-off creation strategies in the Canary Islands.
- **Collaboration between stakeholders:** The event reinforced the importance of multi-level collaboration between universities, government institutions, businesses, and investors.
- **Bridging research and commercialization:** Identified gaps in the transition from academic research to commercial ventures, highlighting the need for structured support mechanisms.

3. **Future directions and recommendations**

- Establishing a systematic screening process for identifying high-potential research with commercialization potential.

- Developing financial structuring and business model validation programs to assist academic entrepreneurs.
- Strengthening networks between regional, national, and international actors to support spin-off incubation and market entry.
- Exploring policy and regulatory adjustments to facilitate licensing, patenting, and spin-off creation.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos of the event: **Work sessions based on design thinking methodology**

Some photos of the event: **IV Technical Conference on Knowledge Transfer and European Projects in the Canary Islands**

2.6. WP6 – SUSTAINABILITY AND EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

Table 35. Activity: Analysis of institutional, legal, and administrative barriers

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Analysis of institutional, legal, and administrative barriers</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	ULPGC
WP	WP6
Associated task/s	Task 6.1 Analysis of institutional, legal, and administrative barriers
Implementation RP	1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	ULPGC: activity leader
Number of participants (if applicable)	Not applicable
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>Under the framework of Task 6.1, the Widening Universities taking part in the project (ULPGC and UAC) have conducted an assessment which analysed the barriers previously detected in the evaluation of their regional ecosystems (WP1), setting some proposals for solutions at the administrative/legislative level, which would be raised with the regional, autonomous and/or national governments in the forums/meetings that will be held with these institutions in the future. The assessment has been displayed in Deliverable 6.1.</p> <p>On the other hand, <i>Task 6.4 Creation of a forum of peripheral Universities</i>, through activities led by CE, contacted peripheral Universities in Widening and other European countries to share information on challenges, obstacles, and good practices in modernization of HEIs. Synergies among organization and institutions were achieved. This workshop was conducted on 20th of September 2023.</p>	
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)	
D1.2 Azores and Canary Islands Regional ecosystem assessment reports, online presentations, Zoom platform.	
Results, findings, and main conclusions	
<p>The main barriers and potential measures to overcome these barriers have been collected in Deliverable 6.1. Report on administrative and legal barriers hampering the cooperation among Widening Universities. This document was the basis for establishing the future strategies of the UAC and the ULPGC, as well as the corresponding action plans based on task 2.4 of the project.</p>	
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)	
Some photos of the online Forum of peripheral universities, organised by CE:	

Table 36. Activity: Surveys to students, researchers and staff of the university

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Collection of quantitative data through surveys to students, researchers and staff of the university</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	ULPGC
WP	WP6
Associated task/s	Task 6.2 Monitoring and Impact Assessment of Action Plans Implementation
Implementation RP	1
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	ULPGC: activity leader
Number of participants (if applicable)	253
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
Under the framework of Task 6.2, four types of surveys were designed based on the indicators of the Action Plans and the Capacity Building Plan to obtain quantitative data on the perception of the different target groups regarding the status of the activities and issues addressed by the EXPER project.	
The surveys were addressed to four specific groups: university staff, researchers, students and stakeholders. The latter group did not respond to any of the mailings, so it is not included in the analysis.	

The surveys were completed by a total of 253 individuals: 38 students, 52 researchers, and 163 university staff members.
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)
D2.2 UAc and ULPGC Action Plans, D4.2 Capacity Building Plan and report on capacity building activities. Microsoft forms
Results, findings, and main conclusions
Annex IV. Surveys Conducted under Task 6.2 of this document includes the responses obtained and a complete analysis of each of the surveys conducted, as well as a comparative analysis between targets on those common questions
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)
https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=HHO7sg1GD0KkdT7WFagphwPVXajATTdCjsye7vJ0_31UMEMySUdIWVFMOTdIVDdYVVdSQjVXNTFMNS4u
https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=HHO7sg1GD0KkdT7WFagphwPVXajATTdCjsye7vJ0_31URFRLVTZHUE9XTkFEVkiETIFBRFM0STA5WC4u
https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=HHO7sg1GD0KkdT7WFagphwPVXajATTdCjsye7vJ0_31UOTUwSkhHTUJZNUxESENaQ1RHUEZMVjM1TS4u

Table 37. Activity: Training session to foster University -Business collaboration

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Support tools to encourage University-Business collaboration and the creation of spin-offs through R&D&I taxation</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	SPEGC
WP	WP6
Associated task/s	Task 6.3: Feasibility studies and partnership agreement for establishment of spin-offs supporting offices
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	SPEGC: activity leader
Number of participants (if applicable)	10
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>Under the framework of Task 6.3, SPEGC, as task leader, launched a pilot training session to promote university-business collaboration.</p> <p>This activity served as a foundational step toward building a sustainable framework for spin-off creation and support. The training session, was specifically designed to equip leading researchers and administrative staff from the ULPGC and FCPCT with practical knowledge and tools to facilitate collaboration with the business sector through R&D&I-based incentives.</p> <p>The session centered on support Tools to Incentivize and Promote University-Business Collaboration through R&D&I Taxation</p>	

The session aimed to create awareness and build internal capacity within the university ecosystem by providing insight into national-level R&D&I tax instruments and collaboration tools. The content included:

- Introduction to the strategic context of university-business collaboration.
- Explanation of key R&D&I tax incentives available to entities engaging in collaborative research.
- Use cases demonstrating how universities can interact with private companies to benefit from tax-based tools.
- Overview of additional mechanisms and resources to strengthen university-industry ties.
- Participatory planning segment to translate insights into actionable strategies.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Presentations, physical facilities, projector

Results, findings, and main conclusions

Four principal investigators and key administrative personnel from various research institutes attended the pilot session, representing a diverse array of scientific domains. As a result, the session laid the groundwork for future collaborative practices and internal alignment on support strategies for spin-offs. By targeting the actors most directly involved in the potential creation and support of spin-offs, this pilot initiative contributed significantly to helping identify operational gaps, raised awareness of collaboration mechanisms, and initiated the development of structured support services, aligning with the task's objective to explore viable frameworks for long-term university-enterprise engagement and spin-off sustainability.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Table 38. Activity: Ensuring collaboration with Widening Institutions

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Ensuring collaboration with Widening Institutions</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	CE/ULPGC-FCPCT; UAc
WP	WP6

Associated task/s	Task 6.4 –Creation of a forum of peripheral Universities
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser: CE/ULPGC-FCPCT
Number of participants (if applicable)	78
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>Throughout the project's duration, CE, in collaboration with ULPGC and UAc, actively engaged in mapping and contacting peripheral universities. This effort aimed to foster collaborative relationships and gain insights into the common challenges faced by these institutions and explore potential solutions.</p> <p>A key milestone was the organisation of the "Forum of Peripheral Universities" in Month 12. This forum served as a platform to address critical issues such as nurturing future researchers, enhancing the attractiveness of research careers, promoting researcher mobility, and retaining talent that then would serve developments in WP3, WP4 and WP5.</p> <p>Recognising the unique challenges faced by Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Outermost Regions, CE, in conjunction with ULPGC, developed a comprehensive Forum Strategy. This strategy focused on identifying and addressing the specific challenges and barriers faced by these institutions. To achieve this, a thorough desk research process was conducted, complemented by a series of interviews with representatives from various HEIs. The gathered insights informed the development of a comprehensive set of solutions and recommendations.</p> <p>The Forum was seamlessly integrated into the project's website as a platform to share knowledge, good practices and a space for discussions, and the interviews conducted with HEI representatives served as valuable input for the development of the Forum Strategy, which was subsequently submitted by ULPGC in M30.</p>	
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)	
Templates, Zoom and Microsoft Teams, Research Questions, Wordpress, HTML	
Results, findings and main conclusions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contacts established by potential partners with both universities 	
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)	

Forum

Forum

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Activity

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Forum

EXPER - Forum

Last post

Forum of Peripheral Universities - EXPER

No topics yet!

2.7. WP7 – DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Table 39. Activity: Implementation of Dissemination and Communication activities

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Implementation of Dissemination and Communication Activities</i>
Organiser/Responsible partner		CE
WP		WP7
Associated task/s		All WP7 Tasks, from T7.1 to T7.5
Implementation RP		1 & 2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	CE: Organizer, facilitator; UNICAL: team member	
Number of participants (if applicable)	Variable	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The development of Deliverable 7.1, which encompasses the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, including communication activities (DE&C), was initiated during the early stages of the project under Task 7.1. This deliverable was submitted to the EC in M6. Subsequently, the project's visual identity and website were meticulously designed to establish strong connections with relevant stakeholders and the project's target groups as defined. Additionally, a comprehensive set of promotional materials has been meticulously crafted to effectively communicate and disseminate the project's objectives. These materials include document templates, leaflets, flyers, roll-ups, and other relevant items outlined in Deliverable 7.3, titled "EXPER Promotional Materials." It is worth noting that these materials are continuously updated and adapted to cater to the specific needs of each partner when attending events or organising their activities. UNICAL collaborated on D7.1 and D7.3, proposing the "EXPER Cultural Aperitifs" event, a periodic informal discussion on project issues and outcomes involving researchers, students, EXPER staff, representatives of HEIs in surrounding ecosystems, and citizens in order to build networks and exchange ideas.</p> <p>During M3, as part of Task 7.2, a professional website was meticulously designed and subsequently launched following the submission of D 7.2 of the project website. This website serves as a dynamic platform that undergoes daily updates and maintenance. It serves as a comprehensive repository of project information, encompassing detailed descriptions of partners, events, news, and funding. Upon the approval of project deliverables by the EC, the website featured a dedicated results section to showcase the outcomes. Additionally, the project established its presence on various social media platforms, including Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn. Notably, the project experiences significant engagement on LinkedIn, with active interactions taking place. As part of the project's outreach efforts, compelling podcasts were produced, capturing testimonials from partners highlighting the project's ongoing activities. In accordance with the project's DE&C Plan, the biannual newsletters for the year 2023 were published. The first edition was released during M6 in March 2023, followed by the second edition in September 2023 (M12). UNICAL provided some feedback and proposals on the implementation of the EXPER First Newsletter.</p> <p>Task 7.3 was initiated in parallel with Task 2.1, which involved the definition of the mission and vision for the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) and the University of the Azores (UAc). To promote the project and gather feedback from online users in the Widening regions, a social media campaign accompanied by an online consultation was launched during M7 and M8. This campaign was conducted in both Spanish and Portuguese languages. The purpose was to inform the public about the project and gather valuable insights to inform the development of the mission and vision for ULPGC and UAC. Furthermore, it is planned to launch two additional campaigns in 2024. The first campaign focused on the "Role of knowledge and research in addressing green deal-related challenges and opportunities," while the second campaign explored the "Role of knowledge and research in addressing blue economy-related challenges and opportunities."</p>		

Task 7.5 aims to engage with children and schools as part of the Country Plan outlined in D 7.1. The objective is to implement activities in the Widening ecosystems of the EXPER project. Currently, the partners, in collaboration with the CE, are in the planning phase of two types of activities. Firstly, an informative-educational game was organised in primary schools, aiming to introduce children to research. This involved the creation of a memory card game featuring local researchers and their achievements. Simultaneously, a contest titled "The University We Want" was conducted in the Azores and the Canary Islands, targeting secondary students. The contest's purpose is to stimulate dialogue regarding the role of universities in the green and blue economy, as well as to encourage students to envision their ideal university. The contest took the form of an essay competition. The design of the games and the development of a lesson plan on the blue and green economy are currently underway.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Design Software: Adobe Creative Pack (mainly: InDesign, Illustrator and Photoshop), slides, Microsoft Office, meta ads, EU Survey

Results, findings, and main conclusions

The DE&C activities within the EXPER project have been diligently executed, aiming to effectively disseminate project objectives and engage with stakeholders. The development of Deliverable 7.1 and the subsequent creation of promotional materials have provided a strong foundation for communication efforts. The project website, regularly updated and maintained, serves as a dynamic platform for sharing information and showcasing project outcomes. Engaging with social media platforms and producing podcasts have enhanced the project's online presence and fostered active interactions. Biannual newsletters have been published, keeping stakeholders informed about project progress.

The implementation of Task 7.3 involved launching social media campaigns and online consultations to gather feedback and shape the mission and vision of ULPGC and UAc. Task 7.4 has seen active participation in events, such as the European Year of Skills Event and Macaronight 2023, to raise awareness and promote the project. Additionally, the project has organised events, such as "El futuro es femenino: Liderando la revolución tecnológica," in collaboration with other organisations, celebrating International Girls in ICT Day.

Under task 7.4, in line with Task 6.4 and Task 1.5, the Forum, organised by CE, provided a platform to explore best practices from EUAs, facilitate knowledge exchange, and enable the forging of valuable connections. Participants delved into strategies and approaches that have proven successful within these alliances, fostering collaboration and innovation in the European higher education landscape.

The workshop's attendees under the Forum hailed from countries such as the Czech Republic, Portugal, Spain, Croatia, Romania, Malta, Cyprus, Ireland, Germany, The Netherlands, France, Greece, Italy, Bulgaria, Austria and the United Kingdom. Their active participation exemplified a collective commitment to advancing European higher education and innovation as well as an impact on the message of the project.

Notable institutions, European Universities Alliances, and projects involved in this collaborative endeavour included the ULPGC, UAC, University of Zagreb, Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal, MCAST, The Cyprus Institute, University of La Réunion, University of La Laguna, Tsenov Academy of Economics, University of Groningen, Rostock University, University of Bucharest, University of Glasgow, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, University of Bucharest, and many others created initial synergies under the projects umbrella.

Under Task 7.5, the ongoing development of the game and the creation of a lesson plan and the contest demonstrate the project's commitment to these activities by increasing public awareness of science, fostering collaborations, and shaping the future of research and education in the green and blue economy.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

 Visual identity:

Professional website for Exper Project:

Social media campaign and online consultation to define the Vision and Mission for ULPGC and UAC:

Estamos a recolher contributos cidadãos para definir a Missão e Visão da Universidade dos Açores.

A sua opinião conta!

🌐 Organization of the event "El futuro es femenino: Liderando la revolución tecnológica":

 Informative educational game:

 Outreach to citizens and organisations:

Table 40. Activity: Dissemination and Communication activities (UROS)

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Dissemination and communication activities</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		UROS
WP		WP7
Associated task/s		Tasks 7.1, 7.2 and 7.4
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	UROS: Organiser	
Number of participants (if applicable)	Not applicable	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The EXPER project, project events and results were advertised in various ways and through different media:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press releases via the UROS website (e.g. on 12/2024: https://www.dienstleistungsportal.uni-rostock.de/ur-interne-nachrichten/detailansicht-der-news/n/gemeinsam-fuer-exzellente-forschung-in-der-eu-227577/) 		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Presentations, graphics, texts and summaries.		
Results, findings and main conclusions		
<p>The promotional activities carried out under WP7 successfully enhanced the visibility of the EXPER project and its associated initiatives. Key outcomes include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased Engagement on Social Media: Regular updates on the Instagram and LinkedIn channels of the Centre for Entrepreneurship resulted in improved reach and engagement with relevant stakeholders, including entrepreneurs, university members, and the broader academic community. 2. Effective Outreach at MVPreneurDay: The advertising banner and presentation at the MVPreneurDay effectively engaged attendees interested in entrepreneurship, strengthening connections within the Mecklenburg-Vorpommern region and fostering interest in the project. 3. Successful Workshop Promotion: The internal university newsletter and direct e-mail campaign facilitated broad participation in the WP4 online seminars, emphasizing the importance of leveraging internal communication channels for targeted outreach. 		

4. Media Coverage: The press release on the university website provided broader public awareness of the project's relevance to fostering excellent research within the EU framework, highlighting its alignment with institutional and regional goals.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

For further information and dissemination materials:

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7272951257160409088>

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7270396572817887232>

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7269802872765091841>

<https://www.dienstleistungsportal.uni-rostock.de/ur-interne-nachrichten/detailansicht-der-news/n/gemeinsam-fuer-exzellente-forschung-in-der-eu-227577/>

Table 41. Activity: Communication campaign

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Communication campaign</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		CE/ULPGC-FCPCT, UAc, Terinov
WP		WP7
Associated task/s		T7.3 Focused communication campaigns
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser/Facilitator: CE/ULPGC-FCPCT, UAc, Terinov	
Number of participants (if applicable)	Not applicable	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>During the development of the present deliverable, four distinct social media campaigns were conducted by CE, with the support of researchers from the ULPGC and UAC, utilising Meta platforms (Facebook and Instagram). The initial campaign, focused on the definition of the mission and vision of ULPGC and UAC, is detailed in D6.2. Subsequent campaigns addressed critical themes related to the project's objectives.</p> <p>One campaign disseminated video interviews with ULPGC researchers, focusing on the role of knowledge and research in addressing Green Deal-related challenges and opportunities, achieving an outreach of 6925 users. A parallel campaign, featuring video interviews with UAC researchers, explored the role of knowledge and research in addressing Blue Economy-related challenges and opportunities, reaching 5192 users.</p> <p>Additionally, a geolocated campaign targeted students and workers from both ULPGC and UAC to promote the importance of gender equality and diversity in research and innovation, resulting in an outreach of 2000 users.</p>		

Finally, a campaign utilising video content emphasised the significance of responsible research and citizen science for the Canary Islands and the Azores, reaching 5.051 users. These campaigns were strategically designed to maximise engagement and disseminate key research insights to relevant audiences.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Adobe Premiere, Adobe Illustrator and Meta Business Suite

Results, findings and main conclusions

- Social media platforms, particularly Meta, are effective tools for disseminating research findings and promoting key project themes to diverse audiences.
- Video interviews are highly engaging and effective in conveying complex research concepts.
- Targeted advertising allows for the effective reach of specific demographics, maximising the impact of campaigns.
- There is a strong public interest in research related to the Green Deal, Blue Economy, gender equality, and responsible research practices.
- The collaborative effort between CE and the universities ULPGC and UAC was crucial to the success of the campaigns.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

- Some photos and audiovisual materials related:

Table 42. Activity: Scientists' Achievements and The University We Want

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Scientist's Achievements and The University We Want</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	CE/ULPGC-FCPCT, UAc, Terinov
WP	WP7
Associated task/s	T7.5 Outreach to children and schools
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	CE: Organiser/Facilitator/Speaker
Number of participants (if applicable)	970
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>This task aimed to foster a deeper understanding of research and science among primary and secondary school students, cultivating their creative thinking skills and resilience for future changes.</p> <p>In February 2024, coinciding with the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, a series of engaging activities were organised in primary schools in the Canary Islands. These initiatives, conducted in collaboration with ULPGC, FCPCT, and CE, included the "Scientists and Achievements" game (ULPGC scientists version), reaching approximately 250 children in four schools. These activities, aligned with the objectives of Task 7.3, focused communication campaigns on gender equality, effectively highlighted the achievements of female researchers and encouraged girls to pursue careers in STEM fields.</p> <p>Researchers from the ULPGC engaged with over 450 secondary school students in a variety of activities, showcasing their most significant scientific inventions, discoveries, and achievements at the Mini Science Fair 2024 in the Canary Islands on April 23rd, 2024.</p> <p>Subsequently, in October 2024, engaging science-themed activities, including the "Scientists and Achievements" (UAc scientists version) card game, were conducted in diverse schools on the Island of Terceira in the Azores, reaching over 60 students.</p> <p>To maximise reach and impact, the project developed and disseminated teaching methods and informative materials through an online training program for teachers. These were included in a set of materials provided along with the game so guaranteeing the use of the games in the schools of the Azores and the Canary Islands.</p> <p>A key component of this task was the "The University We Want" call for essays. In the Azores, Terinov and the UAc successfully launched this call for essays supporting UAc, engaging 120 students from Tomás de Borba Secondary School in Angra do Heroísmo with 14 essays collected. Following this, in Gran Canaria, a team from ULPGC and CE conducted a promotional tour across the island, visiting five schools and reaching over 140 students, encouraging their participation in the essay contest. This initiative, building upon a previous presentation at the Mini Science Fair 2024, invited students to share their visions for a university that fosters sustainability, innovation, and addresses societal challenges with 7 essays collected. The essays were voluntary and under the topics of the blue and circular economy, the university they envision and the role of research in society.</p> <p>Through these diverse activities, the project successfully increased student engagement with research and science, empowered teachers with valuable resources, fostered critical thinking and creativity among students, and effectively promoted gender equality in the scientific field. These outcomes demonstrate the</p>	

successful fulfilment of Task 7.5's objectives in cultivating a deeper understanding of research and science among young people while preparing them for the challenges of the future.

Moreover, on February 18, 2025, during the celebration of the Regional Event held in conjunction with WP4, WP5 and WP7 in the Azores by Terinov, attendees had the opportunity to meet the winner of the Call for Essays in the Azores and a Prize was given to the student to acknowledge participation. Similarly, during the celebration of the final conference of the EXPER project in Gran Canaria, on March 11, 2025 an activity with students took place at the university premises to give award to 3 of the participants' institutions and their teachers, this activity was held in conjunction with Disa Foundation as they donated prizes for the students, the students also had the opportunity to engage with EXPER researchers given their visit to the island and learn about the Blue and Circular economy along with ITC, EMERGE, ULPGC, UROS and Terinov."

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Card games Scientists and Achievements (UAc & ULPGC versions); Flyers, Slides, Sheets and Pencils, EXPER Promotional Materials.

Results, findings and main conclusions

- 340 primary school students connected with research and science in the Azores and the Canary Islands.
- 630 secondary school students engaged with blue and circular economy and understood the future of universities in the Azores and the Canary Islands.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Some photos of the activities performed in the Azores and Canary Islands can be found below:

Azores:

Canary Islands:

Table 43. Activity: Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		CE, all partners involved
WP		WP7
Associated task/s		T7.4 Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	CE: Organiser/Speaker/Trainer	
Number of participants (if applicable)	Not applicable	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>The EXPER project has actively fostered collaborations and engaged in diverse events to maximise its impact and dissemination efforts, aligning with tasks T7.5 and T3.3. Key collaborative activities included partnerships with the ATHENA Project and participation in Macaronight, the European Researchers' Night event, held in both the Azores and the Canary Islands. These collaborations facilitated knowledge exchange and public engagement with citizen science. Furthermore, the project established synergies with the Entrenovators project, organising both physical and virtual events to broaden its reach and impact.</p> <p>The project actively participated in significant European research events. CE and ULPGC representatives attended the EU Research and Innovation Days from March 21-23, 2024, in Brussels, engaging in discussions and networking with other stakeholders. Additionally, UNICAL and CE participated online in the annual research conference on November 21-22, 2024, contributing to the broader academic discourse.</p>		

The culmination of the project's dissemination efforts was the organisation of the final EXPER project conference, held hybridly in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain, on March 10, 2025. This event brought together stakeholders from various sectors, facilitating the dissemination of project results and fostering dialogue on citizen science and responsible research.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)

Forms and templates

Results, findings and main conclusions

- Strategic collaborations with projects like ATHENA and Entrenovators significantly enhanced the project's reach and impact. Entrenovators also participated in the EXPER Final Conference.
- Participation in events such as Macaronight and EU Research and Innovation Days effectively disseminated project findings and fostered engagement with diverse audiences.
- The hybrid Final Conference in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria successfully concluded the project's dissemination activities, ensuring wide accessibility and stakeholder engagement.
- Active participation in both physical and virtual events demonstrates the project's adaptability and commitment to maximising dissemination efforts.
- The attendance of the annual research conference shows the project's commitment to academic dissemination.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

- Some photos during the EXPER project events:

Table 44. Activity: Strengthening Research talent and Innovation through strategic engagement and capacity building

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Strengthening research talent and Innovation through strategic engagement and capacity building</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		EMERGE
WP		WP7
Associated task/s		T7.4 Outreach to citizens, organization and participation in events
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	Organiser/Speaker/Trainer	
Number of participants (if applicable)	Workshop during the Third International Conference for Young Researchers: 50	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>As part of Task 7.4, EMERGE performed two key activities aimed at engaging with the research community and strengthening strategic collaborations to enhance research capacity and talent development.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The second activity involved a strategic meeting with Francesca Barisani, a representative of the EIT Deep Tech Talent Initiative. The discussion explored potential areas of collaboration between EXPER and the EIT Deep Tech Talent Initiative, which offers specialized training programs to equip students, researchers, and professors with the practical skills needed to advance innovation in deep tech fields. By leveraging this partnership, the EXPER community—particularly researchers from the participating universities—can strengthen their capacity to drive technological development and address global challenges. The meeting concluded with EMERGE’s commitment to the EIT Deep Tech Talent Initiative, reinforcing the shared goal of fostering talent and promoting the growth of start-ups and technology. 		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
Slides, online presentation and surveys.		
Results, findings and main conclusions		
<p>The workshop at the Third International Conference for Young Researchers highlighted the importance of empowering the research community to drive institutional reforms and modernize universities. Participants identified key barriers contributing to brain drain and proposed actionable strategies to address them, emphasizing the need for greater flexibility in research careers, more funding opportunities, and improved career development frameworks. The collaborative format of the workshop underscored how collective efforts within the research community can inspire tangible institutional change and foster a more resilient and inclusive research ecosystem.</p> <p>On the other hand, the strategic meeting with the EIT Deep Tech Talent Initiative resulted in a formal commitment from EMERGE to support the initiative’s goals. By engaging with the EIT’s training programs,</p>		

the EXPER community stands to benefit from enhanced knowledge transfer and the development of practical skills essential for innovation in deep tech fields. This collaboration strengthens the capacity of participating universities to support technological development and the creation of start-ups, contributing to long-term talent retention and reinforcing the role of academia in addressing global challenges.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Photography of the workshop during the 3rd International Conference for Young Researchers:

2.8. WP8 – PROJECT MANAGEMENT ACTIVITIES

Table 45. Activity: General Project Management activities

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>General Project Management activities</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	ULPGC/FCPCT
WP	WP8
Associated task/s	Task 8.1 Coordination, reporting, and data management, Task 8.2 Kick-off and other periodic meetings and Task 8.3 Internal evaluation, quality and risk management
Implementation RP	1 & 2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	ULPGC: Coordinator, project management
Number of participants (if applicable)	Not applicable
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
<p>The ULPGC, through FCPCT, played a central role in ensuring the efficient management, coordination, and successful implementation of all project activities during the second reporting period. This was achieved through continuous collaboration and communication with all partners, facilitating the smooth execution of the defined tasks.</p> <p>Key highlights of this period included the coordination of consortium meetings in collaboration with the host institutions (UNICAL/UAc), the implementation of the CLAB model in Widening Universities (WP3), the coordination and launch of the SCWG (WP4), and the organization of major events such as the Summer Schools (ULPGC and UAc), which focused on the three main pillars of the project: Research Excellence, Attraction and Retention of Talent, and Knowledge Transfer. Additionally, events such as Investigafest, which promoted interdisciplinary research collaborations, and various technology transfer and innovation workshops were successfully executed (WP5).</p> <p>During this period, essential project management activities were carried out, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support for communication and dissemination activities, ensuring effective outreach and visibility of project outcomes. <p>To ensure the project's objectives were met within the established timelines and budget, WP8 followed the structured management approach outlined in Deliverable 8.1 – Management & Coordination Plan (ver.</p>	

1). Additionally, the project's data management strategy remained a key focus, addressing data collection, sharing, and preservation, as detailed in Deliverable 8.2 – FAIR Data Management Plan (ver. 1).

Through its leadership in project coordination and management, ULPGC, via FCPCT, ensured the effective implementation of all planned activities, reinforced collaboration among partners and engagement with the European Commission, and contributed to the overall success and sustainability of the project, laying the groundwork for its long-term impact.

Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)
Teams meetings, online presentations, slides, materials for the dynamization of events (post-it, posters, roll-ups, notebooks, etc.)
Results, findings and main conclusions
Smooth communication between project partners, follow-up and implementation of actions and tasks, development of event dynamics and logistical tasks.
Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

Table 46. Activity: Consortium meeting at UAc facilities

ACTIVITY/EVENT	<i>Consortium meeting at UAc facilities</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner	UAc, ULPGC
WP	WP8
Associated task/s	Task 8.2 Kick-off and other periodic meetings
Implementation RP	2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	UAc: Coordinator, organiser; Rest of the partners: Attendees
Number of participants (if applicable)	20
General description of the activity/event and objectives	
UAc organized and hosted the Consortium Meeting, held at UAc premises (Ponta Delgada), on 16-17/Oct/2023. The objective of the 1st Consortium Meeting was to share the progress made within the framework of teach project WP. The two-day assembly saw fruitful discussions on various aspects of project management, cooperation models, and strategies for the modernization of Widening Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) with an emphasis on research and innovation. The meeting took place at the University of the Azores and included a visit to the NONAGON Science and Technology Park.	
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)	

Teams' meetings, online presentations, slides, materials for the dynamization of events (post-it, posters, roll-ups, notebooks, etc.)

Results, findings and main conclusions

1st Day: Assessing Regional Ecosystems and Modernization Strategies

On the first day, the consortium conducted a thorough assessment of the regional ecosystems associated with the Widening universities participating in the project. The University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria and the University of the Azores were the focal points of this evaluation. The aim was to gather knowledge and assess existing cooperation models and practices among these institutions, closely aligned with the project's leading organisations—the University of Calabria and the University of Rostock.

Additionally, discussions centred around strategies to modernise HEIs and promote research and innovation. Key sustainability and exploitation topics included:

- Sustaining the adoption of modernization results in Widening HEIs.
- Preparing for the establishment of a European University Alliance.
- Engaging with additional HEIs to expand the EXPER European University Alliance."

"2nd Day: Co-Design Activities and Brain Drain Mitigation

The second day focused on co-design activities to enhance the appeal of Widening Universities to talented individuals. This involved improving career conditions and devising strategies to prevent or mitigate brain drain, especially in the two outermost regions, the Azores and the Canary Islands.

Moreover, discussions covered research and innovation strategies, emphasising the creation of an interdisciplinary critical mass to drive societal impact. These discussions will lead to the identification of new research strands that involve multidisciplinary research working groups from both Widening and leading HEIs.

Finally, the assembly addressed the need to enhance knowledge transfer mechanisms at Widening organisations. It was proposed to organise dedicated training for researchers and provide technical assistance to Widening Universities in establishing Spin-offs supporting offices."

"Visit to NONAGON: Engaging with the surrounding ecosystem

The consortium expressed its gratitude to the University of the Azores for hosting the event and providing an opportunity for partners to visit the NONAGON Park. NONAGON, the first Science and Technology Park of the Autonomous Region of the Azores, situated in Lagoa, São Miguel Island, plays a pivotal role in fostering technological innovation and developing human resources in information and communication systems. The Park aligns its mission with the key strategic areas of the Research and Innovation Smart Specialisation Strategy for the Azores (RIS3 Azores), including Agriculture, Animal Husbandry and Agro-industry, Fisheries and the Sea, and Tourism. NONAGON functions as a vital catalyst within the Azorean innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem, facilitating technology transfer."

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

- Some photos taken during the Consortium meeting at the UAc premises:

Table 47. Activity: Consortium meeting at UNICAL facilities

ACTIVITY/EVENT		<i>Consortium meeting at UNICAL facilities</i>
Organizer/Responsible partner		UNICAL, ULPGC
WP		WP8
Associated task/s		Task 8.2 Kick-off and other periodic meetings
Implementation RP		2
Type of participation <i>(organiser, attendee, facilitator, speaker, trainer, etc.)</i>	UNICAL: Coordinator, organiser; Rest of the partners: Attendees	
Number of participants (if applicable)	~ 15	
General description of the activity/event and objectives		
<p>UNICAL organized and hosted the Consortium Meeting on the 23rd and 24th of October 2024, held at their premises in Calabria, Italy. The objective of this meeting was to review and align the progress of the activities within the work packages of the project. It also served as a platform for discussing ongoing and future collaboration efforts among the project partners.</p> <p>The two-day event included in-depth discussions on the progress of each WP, the identification of challenges, and the formulation of strategies to ensure the successful implementation of the project objectives. Additionally, partners collaborated on designing future activities aimed at improving the operational efficiency and outcomes of the project.</p>		
Tools for the development/implementation of the activity (slides, online presentation, surveys, questionnaires, etc.)		
In-person presentations, slides, flipcharts, Post-its, and other visual aids		
Results, findings and main conclusions		

1st Day: Project Progress Review and Strategic Discussions

The first day of the meeting was dedicated to reviewing the progress of the project activities, with presentations from each WP leader. Discussions focused on assessing the effectiveness of ongoing tasks, identifying any bottlenecks, and proposing solutions. Partners also discussed the alignment of the project goals with the broader objectives of the program, ensuring that the activities are on track.

2nd Day: Upcoming activities

The second day centered on the planning of upcoming activities and strategies to enhance inter-institutional collaboration, thus meeting the final goals of the project during its final period. Key discussions revolved around strengthening partnerships, developing synergies between the participating institutions, and exploring the most effective ways to smartly implement the pending tasks of the project. Partners also worked on according common methods to ensure the long-term sustainability of the project's results.

Visit to university facilities and the city centre of Cosenza

During the meeting, a visit was organized to the university facilities, providing an opportunity for partners to engage with the surrounding academic and innovation ecosystem. This visit was aimed at fostering deeper connections between the project's goals and the local research and development landscape.

As part of the Consortium Meeting, the partners had the opportunity to enjoy a cultural visit to the city of Cosenza. This tour allowed participants to explore the city's rich history, architecture, and local heritage.

Photographs or other associated documents (if applicable)

 Some photos taken during the Consortium meeting at the UNICAL premises:

3. MONITORING AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF THE EXPER PLANS

The section presents a comprehensive monitoring and impact assessment of the actions and activities defined in the project's strategic plan documents. These actions, articulated in three core deliverables—D2.2 Action Plans Developed, D4.1 Societal Challenges Working Groups and Thematic Action Plans, and D4.2 Capacity Building Plan and Report on Capacity Building Activities—constitute key strategic initiatives designed to advance the overarching objectives established as the outset of the EXPER project.

One of the primary objectives of this section is to evaluate the degree of implementation of these actions by analysing their associated KPIs. The assessment has been conducted separately for each Widening University (ULPGC and UAc), ensuring a comprehensive review of the progress and impact of their implemented activities.

Beyond tracking implementation, the ultimate objective of this section is to quantify and evaluate the extent to which the ULPGC and the UAc have progressed toward Excellence in Research, Talent attraction and retention, as well as KTT and entrepreneurship. This analysis provides valuable insights into the project's effectiveness, highlighting achievements, identifying challenges, and ensuring alignment with the overarching goals of EXPER Project.

3.1. ULPGC MONITORING AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT

3.1.1. MONITORING OF D2.2 ACTION PLANS DEVELOPED

D2.2 Action Plans Developed defined the Action Plans designed to guide the institutional transformation of ULPGC and UAc, ensuring their alignment with the objectives of the EXPER project. These plans were based on the findings of previous assessments (WP1) and strategic co-design activities (WP2), focusing on three key areas:

- Excellent and Responsible Research.
- Talent attraction and retention.
- Knowledge Transfer and collaboration with surrounding ecosystems.

The document outlined the specific actions that each university had to implement, along with the associated KPIs, ensuring a structured and measurable, thoroughly designed approach to institutional development in the above-mentioned areas.

To assess the implementation and impact of the action plan developed by ULPGC under deliverable D2.2 Action Plans Developed, two tables are presented below. The first table outlines the strategic objectives and corresponding actions, providing a reference framework for evaluating progress. The second table compiles the KPIs used to monitor these actions, along with their recorded results. Additionally, complementary contextual

information is provided for each KPI, in order to facilitate interpretation, including the significance of the data, its context, relevant comparisons and implications.

Table 48. ULPGC's Strategic Objectives and corresponding actions

Strategic Objective	Actions
<p>SO1. Fostering an Entrepreneurial Culture</p>	<p>A1.1. Staff exchanges with project partners to improve the training and skills of ULPGC staff in knowledge transfer, innovation, and spin-offs.</p> <p>A1.2. Pilot implementation of the CLAB (Contamination LAB) model at the ULPGC.</p> <p>A1.3. Organisation of events and/or courses related to entrepreneurship and business for the Research Community, including expert visits and workshops.</p> <p>A1.4. Elaboration of a feasibility study (administrative, economic, and legal aspects will be addressed) for establishment of permanent spin-offs supporting offices and services.</p> <p>A1.5. Organisation of dissemination actions in schools to promote entrepreneurial culture in new generations.</p>
<p>SO2. Promoting Research, Knowledge Transfer, and Innovation</p>	<p>A2.1. Promotion of the training required for RTTP (Registered Technology Transfer Professionals) accreditation of Technical, Administration and Management Staff of the ULPGC.</p> <p>A2.2. Organisation of courses, seminars and/or workshops on Knowledge transfer and Innovation for the ULPGC Teaching and Research staff.</p> <p>A2.3. Promotion of activities to disseminate research results through the organisation of summer schools, conferences and/or workshops.</p> <p>A2.4. Encourage the incorporation of Invited Collaborative Researchers (ICR) from EXPER partners in the Recognised Research Groups of the ULPGC, in order to increase their participation in projects implemented by the ULPGC.</p>

Strategic Objective	Actions
<p>SO3. Developing a Committed University</p>	<p>A3.1. Training plan development for ULPGC Teaching and Research staff, addressing transversal skills in research such as Open Science Practices, research data management, responsible research and science education.</p> <p>A3.2. Organisation of forums and Open Science Practices to promote social initiatives and to enable the incorporation of ideas or initiatives to be developed at the ULPGC.</p> <p>A3.3. Promotion of applications for collaborative research projects with other institutions in Blue and Circular Economy, through the European Projects Office of the ULPGC, and in the framework of the SCWGs of the EXPER project.</p> <p>A3.4. Improvement in the communication and dissemination of calls for Research Human Resources.</p> <p>A3.5. Promotion of the incorporation of researchers from other institutions (European and/or abroad).</p> <p>A3.6. Promotion of researchers' participation in staff stabilisation processes and improvement of their evaluation to facilitate accreditation to stable positions.</p>
<p>SO4. Fostering an Open and Connected University</p>	<p>A4.1. Organisation of dissemination and participative events on the European University Alliance of which the ULPGC is a member (ERUA2).</p> <p>A4.2. Promoting the participation of researchers with success probabilities in calls for projects to be funded in the Horizon Europe program.</p>

In addition to the individual institutional strategies, D2.2 also formalized a **Joint Strategy** between ULPGC and UAc, which emerged from a dedicated Joint Strategy Workshop held on March 1, 2024. This workshop represented the next step in consolidating the strategic frameworks previously developed in WP2 and resulted in a coordinated approach to advancing the EXPER Action Plans. Through a collaborative effort involving key stakeholders—such as innovation leaders, researchers, gender equality experts, internationalization specialists, and educators—the **Joint Strategy** established a framework for cooperation, aligning the strategic objectives of both institutions with the three main action lines of the EXPER project.

This **Joint Strategy** included a set of jointly defined actions and KPIs, ensuring a structured monitoring framework for their implementation. The monitoring and impact

assessment of this strategy are specifically addressed in **Annex I** of the present deliverable, providing a detailed evaluation of its progress and outcomes.

Table 49. ULPGC's Strategic Objectives, KPIs and outcome results¹

Strategic Objective	KPIs	Result	Calculation and details
<p>SO1 - Fostering an Entrepreneurial Culture</p>	<p>K1.1. Increase in the participation of the university community in activities related to businesses and entrepreneurship.</p>	<p>50%</p>	<p>Data collected from 2022 to 2024 by the Knowledge Transfer Office of FCPCT includes various types of activities linked to the business world.</p> <p>The percentage increase is calculated as follows: $(18-12/12) \times 100 = 50\%$</p> <p>This indicates a 50% increase in participation from 2022 to 2024, reflecting the university's ongoing efforts to foster engagement with the business sector.</p>
	<p>K1.2. Number of outreach programmes aimed at fostering an entrepreneurial culture in children.</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>-</p>

¹ The exposed KPIs' results are referred to the period between September 2024 to March 2025.

SO2 - Promoting Research, Knowledge Transfer, and Innovation

<p>K2.1. Number of ULPGC staff with Registered Technology Transfer Professional (RTTP) certification.</p>	<p>0</p>	<p>Although four technical staff members from FCPCT-ULPGC have been actively involved in the process to obtain RTTP certification, the final registration has not yet been achieved due to circumstances beyond FCPCT-ULPGC's control.</p> <p>After receiving approval from the Project Officer (PO), four RTTP-valid courses were attended by the technical staff, but these were funded through other projects. Subsequently, upon securing the PO's approval, the four staff members applied to participate in an in-person RTTP course organized by RedTransfer in Valencia in November 2024. However, this course was ultimately cancelled due to reasons unrelated to FCPCT-ULPGC.</p> <p>Therefore, despite the staff's active participation and commitment, the final RTTP certification could not be obtained.</p>
<p>K2.2. Number of PDI members trained in key skills for technology transfer.</p>	<p>107</p>	<p>The data refers to the SpinON by ULPGC Programme, which consists of a training program designed for teams promoting entrepreneurial initiatives based on technologies and knowledge generated at the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC). Its goal is to strengthen knowledge transfer skills through entrepreneurship, facilitating the creation of knowledge-based companies (KBCs).</p> <p>The program is structured into two modalities:</p> <p>Modality 1: Business Idea Awards, focused on identifying and developing early-stage innovative ideas with market transfer potential.</p>

			<p>Modality 2: Business Model Awards, aimed at more advanced projects seeking to structure solid business models based on research results.</p> <p>Since September 2022, three editions of Modality 1 have been held, with a total of 93 participants, including 62 university faculty and researchers (PDI). During the same period, two editions of Modality 2 have taken place, involving 79 participants, of whom 45 were PDI.</p> <p>Through both modalities, the program has contributed to enhancing knowledge transfer capabilities at different levels, fostering initiatives with high potential for market and societal impact.</p>
	K2.3. Percentage increase in the dissemination of the university's scientific results.	17%	<p>The calculation compares the number of publications in 2024 (1,114) with those in 2022 (949), using the following formula: $(1114-949)/(949) \times 100 = 17.4\%$</p> <p>This results in a 17% increase in scientific dissemination from 2022 to 2024. The steady growth in publications highlights the university's commitment to expanding its research output.</p>
SO2 - Promoting Research, Knowledge Transfer, and Innovation	K2.4. Number of projects involving external researchers.	110	-
SO3 - Developing a Committed University	K3.1. Number of initiatives focused on social innovation.	4	Data obtained from the University Chair of Social Economy of Gran Canaria - ULPGC

	K3.2. Percentage increase in participation in collaborative projects within the Blue Economy and Circular Economy sectors.	No available data	Unfortunately, It has not been possible to obtain data for this KPI due to the limitations of the internal institutional databases, which do not allow filtering down to the level of detail required to isolate participation specifically in collaborative projects within the Blue Economy and Circular Economy sectors.
	K3.3. Number of candidates applying to human resources research calls.	550	-
	K3.4. Number of researchers hired from international institutions and organisations.	11	-
	K3.5. Percentage of hired researchers who secure a stable and permanent contract at ULPGC.	4.5%	The final value of 4.5% has been calculated by dividing the number of researchers who secured a stable and permanent contract (7) by the total number of researchers hired (156). This results in a percentage of 4.5% (7/156).
SO4 – Fostering and open and Connected University	K4.1. Number of events organised on European university alliances in the Outermost Regions (ORs).	7	-

	K4.2. Number of project proposals submitted to European projects (European calls).	116	-
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3.1.2. MONITORING OF D4.2 CAPACITY BUILDING PLAN AND REPORT ON CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

D4.2 Capacity Building Plan and Report on Capacity Building Activities performed the *Capacity Building Plan (CBP)*, with the crucial aim of supporting the institutional transformation of ULPGC and UAc by enhancing research management, Open Science practices and innovation capacities. The CBP was structured around the three pillars of Exper Project:

- Excellent and Responsible Research.
- Talent attraction and retention.
- Knowledge Transfer and collaboration with surrounding ecosystems.

The document described the capacity-building activities that had been carried out and those that were planned, such as training sessions, workshops, and staff exchanges, with the aim of enhancing the skills needed to achieve institutional excellence in the aforementioned areas.

To effectively monitor the implementation of the actions drawn in the Capacity Building Plan (CBP) from D4.2, this section presents two comprehensive tables. The first table details the capacity-building actions planned, ensuring no overlap and being complementary to those specified in D2.2: Action Plans Developed. The second table provides a systematic overview of the KPIs associated with these actions, thoroughly showing their progress through the project life, including future trend indications and sustainability aspects.

Table 50. Objectives of the ULPGC’s CBP and associated actions

CBP Objective	Actions
1. Strengthening Research Excellence	Action 1.1: Targeted Training Courses on Research Project Management
	Action 1.2: Workshops on Best Practices in Research Management
2. Fostering Responsible Research and Societal Impact	Action 2.1: Scientific Outreach Activities
	Action 3.1: Development of competencies in Open Science and Data Management

3. Developing digital and Open Science skills	Action 3.2: Implementation of Infrastructures for Open Science
4. Promoting Innovation and KTT	Action 4.1: Awareness Campaign for the OTC Platform of the ULPGC
5. Empowering Stakeholders	Action 5.1: Training external partners in collaboration with the ULPGC
	Action 5.2: Training Activities and Workshops for CIDE Network Technicians
6. Enhancing International collaborations	Action 6.1: Training on European Research and Innovation Frameworks
	Action 6.2: Attracting International Talent through European Projects

Table 51. Strategic objectives of the ULPGC's CBP, KPIs and outcome results

Strategic Objective	KPIs	Result	Calculation
1. Strengthening Research Excellence	K1.1 Number of participants completing the Project Management programme ² .	51	-
	K1.2 Percentage of successfully submitted proposals to European calls.	12%	-
	K1.3 Number of Workshops Organized	26	-

² Initially, KPI K1.1 was defined as the *Percentage of participants reporting improved competence in Research Project Management in the D4.2 Capacity Building Plans*. However, the available and reported data corresponds to the *Number of participants completing the Project Management programme*.

2. Fostering Responsible Research and Societal Impact	K2.1 Number of events organized	23	-
	K2.2 Number of educational entities participating (schools, high schools, etc.)	120	-
	K3.1 Number of training actions delivered	9	-
3. Developing digital and Open Science skills	K3.2 Number of attendants to the training actions delivered	407	-
	K3.3 Percentage increase in the adoption of Open Science Practices and Data management.	25%	The number of open access publications in September 2022 was 22,609. As of today, this number has increased to 28,332. This represents a 25.3% increase in the adoption of Open Science practices over the reference period.

<p>4. Promoting Innovation and KTT</p>	<p>K4.1 Social media outreach of the information campaign.</p>	<p>270.060</p>	<p>This figure refers to the reach metrics of LinkedIn, Facebook, and the official website of the Fundación Parque Científico Tecnológico. These platforms provide data only for the last year, meaning that the reported figures correspond to the period from March 2024 to February 2025. This KPI reflects the extent to which the campaign's content has been seen across these digital channels.</p>
<p>5. Empowering Stakeholders</p>	<p>K5.1 Number of external partners trained</p>	<p>31</p>	<p>-</p>
	<p>K5.2 Number of training courses or workshops conducted for CIDE network technicians on R&D transfer from research organizations</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>-</p>
	<p>K6.1 Number of projects funded by HE programme.</p>	<p>9</p>	<p>-</p>

6. Enhancing International collaborations	K6.2 Number of MSCA and ERC proposals evaluated and advised by the OPE.	20	-
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3.2. UAC MONITORING AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT

3.2.1. MONITORING OF D2.2 ACTION PLANS DEVELOPED

Following the previous developed deliverable “D2.2 Action Plans Developed, which described the actions to be conducted by each institution (ULPGC & UAc) under the EXPER project framework and within the planned schedule, with the ultimate goal of reaching the objectives previously established both in the Individual Strategy and the Joint Strategy of both institutions, it’s now time to assess and report the implementation process of the actions previously outlined in the UAc Action Plan.

The UAc Action Plan was designed to guide the institutional transformation of UAc, document detailed the specific actions required to be carried out, along with their corresponding KPIs, ensuring a well-structured, measurable, and carefully designed approach to institutional development in the EXPER main lines of action: a) Excellent and responsible research; b) Attraction and retention of talents; c) KTT, cooperation with surrounding ecosystems.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the UAc's Action Plan (D2.2), this report provides a structured analysis using two tables. The first table clearly lays out the plan's strategic objectives and the actions taken to achieve them, providing a clear reference point for our evaluation. The second table presents the key performance indicators (KPIs) used to track progress, along with the results achieved. To make these results easier to understand, we've included contextual information for each KPI, explaining its calculation, trend indication and context observations (when applicable), highlighting the implications of that data.

Table 52. UAc’s Strategic Objectives and corresponding action

Strategic Objective	Actions
<p>Strategic Objective 1: Foster applied research, interdisciplinarity and internationalization</p>	<p>A1.1. Offer an updated informational platform for the externally funded projects.</p> <p>A1.2. Preparation of joint research projects under European funded calls.</p> <p>A1.3. Establishment and participation in multidisciplinary working groups contributing to the achievement of SDGs and response to societal challenges.</p> <p>A1.4. Participate in international workshops to develop transversal scientific skills (Open Science, Data Management, Responsible Research, Science Communication, etc).</p>

Strategic Objective	Actions
	<p>A1.5. Establish actions to promote cooperation and institutional internationalization, such as international networks and alliances.</p> <p>A1.6. Maintain and increase UAc's scientific research activity outputs, such as bibliometric indicators</p>
<p>Strategic Objective 2: Promote a culture of innovation and technology transfer</p>	<p>A2.1. Increase in the participation of the university community in activities related to businesses and entrepreneurship.</p> <p>A2.2. Promote training of teaching and research staff in various skills to enhance their performance in technology transfer activities.</p> <p>A2.3. Foster the creation of Technology Transfer Office (TTO) within InUAc department, support office with the objective of assisting and coordinating technology transfer processes, as well as acting as a bridge for the establishment of external projects and partnerships.</p> <p>A2.4. Promote dynamics that can create value, based on the knowledge produced at the University, transforming the research outputs in social and economic value, through InUAc support services for pre-incubation, incubation, and post-incubation purposes, increasing the number of incubated projects and spinoffs creation.</p>
<p>Strategic Objective 3: Invest in a people-centric University</p>	<p>A3.1. Review and approve the teaching staff performance evaluation regulation to improve the well-being and increase productivity and career satisfaction.</p> <p>A3.2. Reduce job insecurity, by increasing hiring efforts to reach 50% of teaching staff with tenure.</p> <p>A3.3. Submit an institutional application for the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R).</p> <p>A3.4. Modernise the existing or create new infrastructures, such as university residences.</p> <p>A3.5. Promote physical activity through sports, maintenance or leisure activities, which can contribute to physical and psychological well-being, and also promote informal coexistence between its members.</p> <p>A3.6. Foster gender equality and promote diversity, by formulating a diverse strategy.</p>
<p>Strategic Objective 4: Stimulate cooperation, external communication and social connection</p>	<p>A4.1. Foster a culture of collaboration with relevant actors such as science and technology parks, science centres, governmental bodies and local authorities, businesses associations, companies and NGOs, among others.</p> <p>A4.2. Foster the involvement of young people in the university activities and research.</p>

Strategic Objective	Actions
	<p>A4.3. Promote study visits to increase the institutional external visibility within primary, preparatory, secondary and vocational schools.</p> <p>A4.4. Maintain and increase the current student mobility through the Erasmus+, Euroeudisseia and other programs.</p> <p>A4.5. Maintain and increase the current academic staff mobility (teaching and training assignments).</p> <p>A4.6. Carry out educational games with primary and secondary schools to bring young students closer to science.</p> <p>A4.7. Promote the external institutional visibility through fairs and science events participation (regional, national or abroad).</p>

Table 53. UAc's Strategic Objectives, KPIs and outcome results

Strategic Objective	KPIs	Result	Calculation and details
SO1 - Foster applied research, interdisciplinarity and internationalization	K1.1. No. of project proposals submitted to European funded calls, namely Horizon Europe and Interreg funding programs.	154	Includes 56 European, 51 National and 47 Regional funding proposals (in 2024)
	K1.2. No. of projects in the Information Platform for external funded projects.	260	130 ongoing, 130 closed
	K1.3. No. of workshops participation aiming to develop transversal scientific skills.	6	EXPER UAc Summer School, IPN Workshop on Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property, MetaRedX International Exchange Program, InUAc Workshop in Brand Strategy, EXPER Workshop "From Research to Idea", EXPER Workshop "TTO Training"
	K1.4. No. of researchers involved in the societal challenges working groups.	2	Joana Barcelos (IITAA) and Zita Botelho (CIBIO-Açores)

	K1.5. No. of European University Alliances (EUAs) proposals submitted.	1	EUNICOAST (on 05/Feb/2024)
	K1.6. No. of scientific articles indexed in the international Web of Science database.	148	In 2024
SO2 - Promote a culture of innovation and technology transfer	K2.1. No. of UAc staff participating in training schemes certified by Association of European Science and Technology Transfer Professionals (ASTP).	12	From EXPER Workshop "From Research to Idea", ATRINEO pending certification renewal from ASTP
	K2.2. No. of UAc staff with training in key skills for technology transfer (market analysis, IPR management, business models, grow hacking techniques, etc).	12	From EXPER Workshop "From Research to Idea" and "TTO Training"
	K2.3. Implementation of the Technology Transfer Office (TTO) within InUAc department.	Yes	Established in Dec/2023

	K2.4. % increase of incubated projects within InUAc	100%	Started 2024 with 1 incubated project, ended 2024 with to 2 incubated projects
	K2.5. No. of UAc created spinoffs.	0	1 already created in 2023 - Biotech Synergy, no more created since then.
SO3 - Developing a Committed University	K3.1. Review and approve the teaching staff performance evaluation regulation.	No	The process started in 2024 and will be concluded in 2025. In 2024, some relevant indicators were already identified that need to be reviewed within the scope of the process of reviewing the UAc's Teaching Staff performance evaluation regulation. This process will be implemented in 2025, which will include consultation within teaching and research units.
	K3.2. Achieve and secure the maintenance of the minimum percentage of 50% of teaching staff with tenure.	Yes	Currently 50,9%, based on 2024 data per organic unit of teaching and research (ESS 52%, FCAA 45%, FCT 46%, FCSH 58%, FEG 53%)
	K3.3. Submit a HRS4R application in 2025.	No	Pending (still working on applicable required documentation (GAP-Analysis + OTM-R Checklist + Action Plan)

	K3.4. No. of consultations promoting the entire academic community well-being, through UAc's Health Office.	582	Psychology/Psychiatry (278 in Ponta Delgada and 123 in Angra do Heroísmo); General and Family Medicine (65 in Ponta Delgada and 37 in Angra do Heroísmo); Nutrition (79 in Ponta Delgada)
	K3.5. No. of participants from the academic community in sports, maintenance or leisure activities promoted by UAc.	35	N/A
	K3.6. No. of students involved in UAc Senior Academy.	73	N/A
	K3.7. No. of infrastructures modernization or creation.	16	Maintenance of the Scientific complex; Library and Sports building roofs, Removal of asbestos at FSCH building; External conservation of the Rectory building; Painting Works at the FEG, FSCH, Rectory, Aula Magna and Scientific Complex; Maintenance in the carpentry and hydraulic areas in all buildings; Renovation of the water supply network of the SASE building with interventions on the exterior and interior; Renovation of the bars in the Scientific Complex and ESS buildings; Renovation of the kitchens located in the buildings of the ESS and Extension of the Rectory; Repaving the street around the ESS and Administration building; Maintenance of eight elevators in the

			various campus buildings; Replacement of one of the sewage pumps in the Interdepartmental building; Change of the ESS main door; External painting of the Walter Bensaúde building; External painting of houses 1 to 6 of Block B, Horteco neighborhood; Creation of the multimedia laboratory
SO4 - Stimulate cooperation, external communication and social connection	K4.1. No. of collaborative projects initiated with regional actors.	5	Interreg MACs ACUICONETA, INNOVAMOS, FISHMAC, PRISMAC and TEXTIL
	K4.2. No. of students involved in UAc summer school “Verão Jovem na UAc”.	30	Explorers - 3rd Cycle of Basic School: 27 Scientists – High School: 3
	K4.3. No. of incoming study visits.	48	102 professors and 1112 students involved
	K4.4. No. of incoming/outcoming mobility students from Erasmus+, Eurodisseia and other programs.	337/104	Incoming 337 (4 Almeida Garret, 260 Erasmus+, 5 Convénios, 1 Free Mover, 29 Internships, 9 Bridging the Atlantic, 29 Eurodisseia) / Outgoing 104 (89 Erasmus+, 3 Almeida Garret, 12 Bridging the Atlantic)
	K4.5. No. of incoming/outcoming staff mobility.	147/30	Incoming 147 (145 Erasmus+, 2 Bridging the Atlantic) / Outgoing 30 (28 Erasmus+, 2 Bridging the Atlantic)

	K4.6. No. of primary/secondary schools involved in educational games.	1	1 secondary school (several classes)
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3.2.2. MONITORING OF D4.2 CAPACITY BUILDING PLAN AND REPORT ON CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

Following the previous developed deliverable “D4.2 Capacity Building Plan and Report on Capacity Building Activities”, which described the training and capacity building activities to be conducted by each institution (ULPGC & UAc) under the EXPER project framework and within the planned schedule, it’s now time to assess and report the implementation process of the actions previously outlined in the Capacity Building Plan.

The UAc’s Capacity Building Plan (CBP) was designed to address transversal key skills in project management, Open Science practices, research data management, responsible research and communication, KTT and entrepreneurship. Specifically, the plan included training on Open Science practices, project management and preparation of project proposals to secure funding within the framework of European Union Programs, responsible research, scientific education and communication to foster the use of Horizon Europe research results into education and society. The document detailed the specific actions required be carried out, along with their corresponding KPIs, ensuring a well-structured, measurable, and carefully designed approach to institutional development in the EXPER main lines of action: a) Excellent and responsible research; b) Attraction and retention of talents; c) KTT, cooperation with surrounding ecosystems.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the UAc's CBP (D4.2), this report provides a structured analysis using two tables. The first table clearly lays out the plan's strategic objectives and the actions taken to achieve them, providing a clear reference point for our evaluation. The second table presents the key performance indicators (KPIs) used to track progress, along with the results achieved. To make these results easier to understand, we've included contextual information for each KPI, explaining its calculation, trend indication and context observations (when applicable), highlighting the implications of that data.

Table 54. Objectives of the UAc's CBP and associated actions

CBP Objective	Actions
1. Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	Action 1.1: Research Project Management Training
	Action 1.2: Workshops on Best Practices in Science Communication
	Action 1.3: Development of competencies in Open Science
	Action 1.4: Implementation of Digital Tools
2. Strengthen KTT and Innovation	Action 2.1: Enhancement of Innovation and KTT
3. Foster scientific education and societal involvement	Action 3.1: Scientific Outreach Activities
4. Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization	Action 4.1: Training external partners in collaboration with the UAc
	Action 4.2: Enhancement of the Regional and International networks
	Action 4.3: Integrate and maintain the participation on EUAs
	Action 4.4: International Mobility Programs

Table 55. Objectives of the UAc’s CBP and outcome results

Strategic Objective	KPIs	Result	Calculation
1. Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	K1.1 Number of participants attending the trainings on European project writing and Science Communication	91	In UAc EXPER Summer School participants
	K1.2 Number of submitted proposals to European calls	154	Includes 56 European, 51 National and 47 Regional funding (in 2024)
	K1.3 Number of Trainings Organized	5	UAc EXPER Summer School, InUAc Workshop on Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property, InUAc Workshop in Brand Strategy, EXPER Workshop "From Research to Idea", EXPER Workshop "TTO Training"
	K1.4 Number of participants attending the trainings on Open Science good practices	67	In UAc EXPER Summer School 1 st day participants

	K1.5 Number of projects in the Information Platform for external funded projects	260	130 ongoing, 130 closed
2. Strengthen KTT and Innovation	K2.1 Number of UAc staff with training in key skills for technology transfer	12	From EXPER Workshop "From Research to Idea", EXPER Workshop "TTO Training", IPN "Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property Awareness", INPI "General Course on Industrial Property", INPI "Knowledge Transfer and IP Valuation Strategies"
	K2.2 Number of KTT promoted training events	5	UAc EXPER Summer School, InUAc Workshop on Technology Transfer and Intellectual Property, InUAc Workshop in Brand Strategy, EXPER Workshop "From Research to Idea", EXPER Workshop "TTO Training"
3. Foster scientific education and societal involvement	K3.1 Number of events with UAc organization / participation	198	In 2024
4. Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization	K4.1 Number of external partners trained	41	40 from EXPER Summer School + 1 from EXPER workshop "TTO Training"
	K4.2 Number of active UAc networks	12	EMSO, COST, Equine Genetic Diversity Consortium, International Paleontological Association, RETI – Excellence Network of Island Territories, Macaronesian Biotechnology Excellence Network, National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures of Strategic Interest, Iberian Network of Philosophy of Science,

			International Research Network of the Universities of the Outermost Regions of the European Union, MetaRedX – Collaborative Network of Entrepreneurship Units and Workshops of Ibero-American HEIs, RIEA – Network of Business Incubators of the Azores, GAPI – INPI Industrial Property Support Office Network
	K4.3 Number of active collaborative protocols	195	Signed in 2024
	K4.4 Number of European University Alliances participation	1	EUNICOAST
	K4.5 Number of UAc staff participating in mobility programs	30	28 Erasmus+, 2 Bridging the Atlantic

3.3. MONITORING OF D4.1 SOCIETAL CHALLENGES WORKING GROUPS AND THEMATIC ACTION PLANS

D4.1 Societal Challenges Working Groups (SCWGs) established the Societal Challenges Working Groups (SCWGs), promoting excellent and responsible research through transnational and multisectoral cooperation. These groups, composed of researchers from ULPGC and UAc and key actors from the ecosystems of both regions, addressed the regional challenges of the Canary Islands and the Azores, aligning with RIS3 priorities and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Two thematic groups were created, each with a defined Action Plan for implementation, focusing on the following thematic areas:

SCWG1: Adaptation to Climate Change in the Blue and/or Circular Economy

This group focused on understanding regional climate vulnerabilities and supporting adaptation efforts to mitigate current and future climate change impacts. Their work aligned with the priorities of the European Green Deal, including biodiversity protection, pollution reduction, circular economy transitions, waste management improvements, and the sustainability of the blue economy and fisheries sectors. Their efforts aimed to build regional resilience by implementing nature-based solutions and innovative adaptation measures.

SCWG2: Restore our Ocean and Waters in the Blue and/or Circular Economy

This group was dedicated to protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems, particularly within the Atlantic Ocean basin, recognized as one of the “EU lighthouses.” It addressed pollution reduction, biodiversity regeneration, and carbon neutrality in the blue economy. Its cross-cutting actions included fostering public engagement and contributing to the development of a digital ocean knowledge system, the Digital Twin Ocean, to enhance data-driven decision-making and marine conservation efforts.

The thematic action plans defined under D4.1 structured the activities of these SCWGs, including the identification of new research lines, the preparation of proposals for the Horizon Europe programme, and the organisation of collaborative events, among other activities. The activities defined in the action plans were implemented under the coordination of the Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias (ITC) and FCPCT-ULPGC, ensuring strategic alignment and operational efficiency.

The SCWGs—**SCWG1: Climate Change Adaptation and Sustainability** and **SCWG2: Protection and Restoration of Oceans and Waters**—share common objectives despite focusing on different thematic areas. As such, both groups follow a unified set of actions and monitoring KPIs to assess their performance and progress.

These KPIs were designed to ensure the effective operation of the SCWGs and the successful implementation of their thematic action plans. Minimum compliance thresholds for KPI compliance were established to maintain a high level of activity and impact. For instance, the minimum number of meetings to be held by each group during the operational period was set at six, among other targets.

The table below summarizes the actions undertaken by the SCWGs, the associated KPIs, the results achieved, and relevant contextual information to ensure proper understanding and interpretation.

Table 56. Objectives of the SCWG´s CBP and associated actions

CBP Objective	Actions
1. Promote transversal skills for excellence in research	Action 1.1: Research Project Management Training
	Action 1.2: Workshops on Best Practices in Science Communication
	Action 1.3: Development of competencies in Open Science
	Action 1.4: Implementation of Digital Tools
2. Strengthen KTT and Innovation	Action 2.1: Enhancement of Innovation and KTT
3. Foster scientific education and societal involvement	Action 3.1: Scientific Outreach Activities
4. Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization	Action 4.1: Training external partners in collaboration with the UAc
	Action 4.2: Enhancement of the Regional and International networks
	Action 4.3: Integrate and maintain the participation on EUAs
	Action 4.4: International Mobility Programs

Table 57. Monitoring KPIs for SCWGs

Action	KPIs	Compliance Threshold	Results		Remarks and comments
			SCWG1	SCWG2	
1.2 SCWG Meetings	Number of meetings	> 6	9	9	Both SCWGs meetings took place together
	Number of participants per meeting	10	8	8	Both SCWGs meetings took place together
2.1 Identification of new research strands involving multidisciplinary research groups from both Widening and leading HEIs according to the societal challenge	Number of members profile	> 10	38	38	Online webinars: 17 GC Summer School: 8 Terceira Regional event: 10 Final Conference: 3
3.1 Identifying key institutions/actors/stakeholders	Number of stakeholders identified	> 10	21	21	GC Summer School: 8 Terceira Regional event: 10 Final Conference: 3
3.2 Identifying External Networking Events	Number of external events identified	> 2	2	2	Online: example European Ocean Days 2024 ERC webinar 2024 European Ocean Days 2025

4.1 Identifying funding opportunities	Number of calls/topics identified	> 5	13	13	Funding opportunities for both groups
4.2 Building potential consortiums to develop new research proposals	Number of proposals submitted	> 1	1	1	1 submitted under EIT HEI Initiative. Transversal topic. 1 ready to be submitted under Twinning call. SCWG2. 1 half-ready to be submitted under ERC call. SCWG1. 3 project ideas in process
5.1 Dissemination of SCWG activities	Number of news generated	> 6	10	10	Pieces of news generated in common for both groups

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The EXPER project has successfully contributed to the institutional transformation of ULPGC and UAc, fostering modernization through a diverse range of strategically planned activities aligned with the project's three core pillars: Research Excellence, Attraction and Retention of Talent, and Knowledge Transfer. Throughout the project, a structured and coordinated approach has ensured the effective implementation of action plans, capacity-building initiatives, and engagement with key stakeholders.

The diversity of activities carried out under EXPER has been instrumental in addressing institutional challenges from multiple perspectives:

- The Action Plans and Capacity Building Plans have provided a structured roadmap for institutional modernization, guiding both universities in adopting new strategies for growth and development.
- The implementation of the Contamination Lab (CLAB) model has fostered entrepreneurship and interdisciplinary collaboration, equipping students and researchers with key skills to bridge the gap between academia and business.
- The establishment of the Societal Challenge Working Groups has strengthened collaboration among researchers, promoting multidisciplinary approaches to tackle regional and global challenges.
- Various events and activities promoting knowledge transfer, such as workshops, seminars, and networking initiatives, have enhanced the connection between universities and external stakeholders, reinforcing the role of higher education institutions as drivers of innovation and socio-economic development.

The standardized methodology used to document each activity detailing objectives, tools, participants, and results provided a clear and measurable framework for assessing progress. The strong collaboration among partners, the commitment of all involved institutions, and the continuous exchange of best practices have been key factors in achieving significant progress. The project has not only met its objectives but has also laid the foundation for long-term institutional improvements.

The achievements of EXPER set a solid groundwork for further development beyond the project's duration. The strategies, methodologies, and networks established during the project will continue to support institutional growth, international collaboration, and research excellence at ULPGC and UAc. Ensuring the sustainability of these efforts will be essential, particularly in areas such as talent retention, interdisciplinary research, and strengthening connections with external stakeholders.

Moving forward, the results of EXPER can serve as a reference model for other institutions seeking institutional transformation, offering valuable insights into effective modernization strategies. Additionally, the established cooperation frameworks provide a strong basis for future joint initiatives, ensuring that the impact of EXPER extends

beyond its initial scope and contributes to the continued strengthening of the European Research Area.

5. ANNEXES

This section provides supplementary and detailed information to support the monitoring and impact assessment of the EXPER project activities, specifically:

 Annex I: Documentation from Workshops on Good Practices and Action Planning (Task 1.4)

 Annex II: Monitoring and Impact Assessment of the Joint Strategy

This annex presents the results of the monitoring and impact assessment of the Joint Strategy developed between ULPGC and UAc. The strategy, which integrates the individual strategic objectives of both institutions under the EXPER framework, includes a set of jointly defined actions and their corresponding KPIs. The annex provides a comprehensive analysis of the progress achieved, offering insights into the alignment of these actions with the overarching goals of the EXPER project and their contribution to institutional transformation.

 Annex III: Catalogue of Good Practices for ULPGC (HRS4R Strategy)

 Annex IV: Surveys Conducted under Task 6.2

As part of Task 6.2: *Monitoring and Impact Assessment of Action Plans Implementation*, led by ULPGC and UAc, surveys were conducted to collect qualitative data. These surveys targeted students, researchers, and university staff from both ULPGC and UAc to evaluate the implementation, results, and impact of the actions outlined in the Action Plans. The annex includes:

- A summary of the data collected, highlighting key findings.
- An analysis of target perceptions regarding the effectiveness and outcomes of the implemented actions.

These annexes are intended to provide a deeper understanding of the monitoring processes, the data collected, and the assessed impact, complementing the main sections of the report and reinforcing the transparency and accountability of the evaluation process.

5.2. ANNEX I. DOCUMENTATION FROM WORKSHOPS ON GOOD PRACTICES AND ACTION PLANNING (TASK 1.4)

This annex includes the documentation and results produced during the online workshops held from September 25 to 27, 2023, as part of Task 1.4 "Good Practices from Leading Universities" led by UROS within the EXPER project.

The following documents are included in this annex:

- Workshop Summary
- Information Sheets for WP3, WP4 & WP5
- Recommendations for Action Plans
- SMART Action Plan for UAc
- SMART Action Plan for ULPGC
- UROS Best Practices Catalogue

Task 1.4: Workshop on Good Practices 25th – 27th of September 2023 via Zoom

Task Leader: UROS
Michael Leyer, Wieland Müller, Angelina Schilling

Task Description

The three concluded workshops are an integral component of the EXPER modernization strategies. Focused on promoting excellent and responsible research, fostering academia-business cooperation, and enhancing the attractiveness of researchers' careers, the workshop served as a collaborative platform for all EXPER partners and their communities. Participants had the opportunity to discuss existing structures, services, and practices, particularly those successfully implemented by UROS and UNICAL. Beyond knowledge-sharing, the workshop aimed to collectively plan for upcoming capacity-building activities under work packages WP3, WP4, and WP5. This planning was informed by insights gathered from assessments completed under Tasks 1.2 and 1.3.

Preparation

Before the workshop, UROS collected topics from widening universities. These topics were then sorted into categories and directly assigned to work packages WP3, WP4, and WP5. This straightforward approach set a clear framework for the workshop's discussions and activities, ensuring that the agenda was aligned with the overarching goals of the EXPER modernization strategies.

Agenda

Time	Description	Provided Material
BLOCK 1: 15MIN	Topic: Recap of best practices of UROS + and UNICAL on a more in-depth level. Goal: Overview of practices	Short information on program points of interest
BLOCK 2: 15MIN	Topic: Evaluation and selection of practices (Separate for ULPGC + UAc) Goal: Selection of practices	Assessment sheet for practice selection
BLOCK 3: 30MIN	Topic: Definition of tasks for each selected practice (Separate for ULPGC + UAc) Goal: Initial SMART Actionplan	SMART Template for tasks
BLOCK 4: 10MIN	Wrap-up/ Closure	

Workshop Structure

BLOCK 1: 15 Minutes

Topic: Recap of best practices from UROS and UNICAL, explored on a more in-depth level.

Method: Presentation by UROS members.

Goal: To provide an overview of proven practices that have been effective in achieving the objectives of the EXPER modernization strategies.

BLOCK 2: 15 Minutes

Topic: Evaluation and selection of practices, conducted separately for ULPGC and UAc.

Method: Participants ranked each action individually within an online form.

Goal: To select practices that are most relevant and beneficial for the participating universities.

BLOCK 3: 30 Minutes

Topic: Definition of tasks for each selected practice, again conducted separately for ULPGC and UAc.

Method: Participants were assigned into breakout sessions, elaborated on possible tasks, and entered them within the online form.

Goal: To develop an initial SMART action plan, outlining specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound tasks for implementation.

Note: Blocks 2 and 3 were conducted separately for each university, allowing for a focus on individual requirements and enabling a more tailored approach to selecting and defining tasks.

BLOCK 4: 10 Minutes

Topic: Wrap-up/Closure

Method: Room for comments and closure by UROS members

Goal: To summarize the key outcomes of the workshop and outline the next steps for implementing the action plans.

Provided Material

To facilitate the workshop's discussions and goal-setting, several key materials were provided to participants:

1. Information Sheet: A concise summary of best practices for each work package (WP3, WP4, WP5) was distributed to give attendees a solid understanding of proven approaches.
2. Assessment Sheet: This document contained a list of practices for participants to rate each action. The assessment sheet served as a tool for evaluating the efficacy and relevance of various practices. The ranking ranged from 0=not relevant to 5=nice-to-have to 10=absolutely necessary. Each participant rates the actions individually. Out of this ranking the mean is calculated automatically.

3. SMART Template: Aimed at brainstorming and collecting specific tasks, this template utilized the SMART criteria (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound) to help participants formulate actionable steps. Owing to time constraints the focus lies on the collection of specific tasks. The other SMART categories will be filled by the UROS members after the Workshop.

Participants

The majority of participants were project members hailing from various project partners, as well as interested university staff members. The workshops were inclusive and open to anyone interested in participating, thereby broadening the scope of input and collaborative potential.

A noticeable improvement in the working mode was observed as the structure for each work package remained consistent across the sessions. This continuity in structure allowed participants to complete tasks more quickly, signaling a growing familiarity and efficiency in addressing the workshop's objectives.

Acknowledgements

We really would like to thank all participants for the active engagement during the workshops and their valuable ideas.

Contact Information

Prof. Dr. Michael Leyer

Chief Scientific Executive

Institute for Business Administration- Center for Entrepreneurship

Tel.: +49 (0)381 498 4100

michael.leyer@uni-rostock.de

Dr. Martin Setzkorn

Managing Director

Institute for Business Administration- Center for Entrepreneurship

Tel.: +49 (0) 381 498 1198

martin.setzkorn@uni-rostock.de

Wieland Müller

Research Assistant University of Rostock

Institute for Business Administration- Center for Entrepreneurship

Tel.: +49 (0)381-498 4380

wieland.mueller@uni-rostock.de

Angelina Schilling

Research Assistant University of Rostock

Institute for Business Administration- Center for Entrepreneurship

Tel.: +49 (0)381-498 4570

angelina.schilling@uni-rostock.de

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Task 1.4 – Good practices from leading universities
Workshop WP3
Task Leader: UROS
Michael Leyer, Wieland Müller, Angelina Schilling
25th of September 2023

Funded by
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Agenda

Time	Description	Provided Material
BLOCK 1: 15MIN	Topic: Recap of best practices of UROS + and UNICAL Goal: Overview of practices	Short information on program points of interest
BLOCK 2: 15MIN	Topic: Evaluation and selection of practices (Separate for ULPGC + UAc) Goal: Selection of practices	Assessment sheet for practice selection
BLOCK 3: 30MIN	Topic: Definition of tasks for each selected practice (Separate for ULPGC + UAc) Goal: Initial SMART Actionplan	SMART Template for tasks
BLOCK 4: 10MIN	Wrap-up/ Closure	

Task 1.4 Good practices from leading universities

- The aim of the workshops will be to share knowledge on good practices from UROS and UNICAL and to **jointly plan the deployment of capacity building activities**

D1.4 Conclusions from 3 workshops

- UROS: recommendations for the EXPER strategy and action plans

WP3 - Attracting and retaining talents

This WP will deploy concrete activities to attract new talents and retain existing ones and thus deal with brain drain.

- Task 3.1 : HRS4R
- Task 3.2: CLAB model
- Task 3.3: Gender Equality and Diversity
- Task 3.4 Addressing brain drain

Topics of Interest

- ULPGC: Staff Loyalty: what kind of measures are implemented at your university to achieve this loyalty?. For example, mental health programs, health insurance services, etc. In short, what extras/additional incentives are available for your staff?
- ULPGC: Regarding the HRS4R, we would like to know if there are any “Welcoming programs” for new staff at your university, for example including some kind of welcoming packages. Also, the information which is provided to new staff about career development and what a career at your institution entails would be especially interesting for us.
- UAC: Onboarding and career development service
- ULPGC: What are leader Universities doing to ensure that these activities are important on researchers' CVs (incentive policy, objectives, achievement system, etc.)?

→ 1. Services for Staff

→ 2. HRS4R

→ 3. Career Development

1. Services for Staff at UROS

- Diversity Office
- Gender Equality Office
- Family Office
- Welcome Centre for Foreign Researchers
- Online Service Portal for Employees

1. Services for Staff at UROS

- Inclusion Action Plans
- Female Mentoring
- University Health Management
- *Onboarding Plan*

2. HRS4R at UNICAL

3. Career Development at UROS

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UAc

actions	
Onboarding plan	9,1
Scientific Qualification Courses	8,8
Service Portal for Employees	8,5
Incentive Policy	8,3
Online Learning Platform	8,1
University Health Management	8,0
Welcome Centre for Foreign Researchers	7,9
Inclusion Action Plans	7,3
Gender Equality Office	6,9
Didactic Certificate	6,8
Diversity Office	6,2
Female Mentoring	6,2
Family Office	5,9

ULPGC

actions	
Online Learning Platform	8,4
Onboarding plan	8,4
Welcome Centre for Foreign Researchers	8,0
Service Portal for Employees	7,6
Inclusion Action Plans	7,0
Diversity Office	7,0
Family Office	7,0
Gender Equality Office	6,6
University Health Management	6,4
Incentive Policy	6,3
Scientific Qualification Courses	5,7
Didactic Certificate	5,7
Female Mentoring	5,0

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Task 1.4 – Good practices from leading universities
Workshop WP4
Task Leader: UROS
Michael Leyer, Wieland Müller, Angelina Schilling
26th of September 2023

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Agenda

Time	Description	Provided Material
BLOCK 1: 15MIN	Topic: Recap of best practices of UROS + and UNICAL Goal: Overview of practices	Short information on program points of interest
BLOCK 2: 15MIN	Topic: Evaluation and selection of practices (Separate for ULPGC + UAc) Goal: Selection of practices	Assessment sheet for practice selection
BLOCK 3: 30MIN	Topic: Definition of tasks for each selected practice (Separate for ULPGC + UAc) Goal: Initial SMART Actionplan	SMART Template for tasks
BLOCK 4: 10MIN	Wrap-up/ Closure	

WP4 - Promoting Excellent and Responsible Research

This WP will aim at sharing research & innovation strategies and roadmaps to create directional and interdisciplinary critical mass, in order to more effectively create impact for society. New research strands involving multidisciplinary research groups from both Widening and leading HEIs will thus be identified. Joint workshops will be organized to define new research activities and develop new research proposals (including also research proposal for Horizon Europe).

Topics of Interest

- ULPGC: How to promote interdisciplinarity in the universities: to ensure that multidisciplinary groups are created within the university itself to jointly research topics of interest. → 1. Interdisciplinarity
- UAC: Interdisciplinary research projects → 2. Communication
- ULPGC: Ways to improve internal communication, top-down and bottom-up: achieving effective communication channels. → 3. Partnerships (Research)
- UAC: Internal communication processes → 4. Automation Processes
- ULPGC: To improve the connection and engagement between the university and external sectors, both public and private
- UAC: Partnerships improvement
- ULPGC: To improve red tape (automation processes at our University).

1. Interdisciplinarity

- Interdisciplinary Faculty
- University Alliance → EU-CONEXUS
- Interdisciplinary Faculty Forum
- *Cross-departmental collaboration awards*

2. Communication

3. Partnerships (Research)

- Information Platform for External Funded Projects
- Project Service Center
- Research Camp
- International Meeting Center

4. Automation Processes

- Online/ Digital Forms
- E-Signatures
- Workflow Automation
- Digital Document Management
- Remote Access

**See you in the separate
university sessions**

ULPGC: stay in this room

UAC: follow the link into a new room

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UAc

actions	
Bilingual Website	9,7
Project Service Center	9,4
Remote Access	9,3
Online/ Digital Forms	9,2
Cross-departmental collaboration	9,0
Interdisciplinary Faculty	8,8
University Alliance	8,8
Workflow Automation	8,8
Digital Document Management	8,7
Information Platform for External Funded Projects	8,4
Research Camp	8,4
Interdisciplinary Faculty Forum	8,1
Intranet	8,1
Communication concept	8,0
Knowledge Sharing Hub	7,6
Newsletter: Weekly via Mail	7,1
International Meeting Center	6,9
E-Signatures	6,9

ULPGC

actions	
Intranet	9,7
Project Service Center	9,7
Workflow Automation	9,7
Remote Access	9,7
University Alliance	9,3
Cross-departmental collaboration	9,3
Bilingual Website	9,3
E-Signatures	9,3
Digital Document Management	9,3
Online/ Digital Forms	9,0
Knowledge Sharing Hub	8,3
Information Platform for External Funded Projects	8,3
Communication concept	8,0
Newsletter: Weekly via Mail	8,0
Interdisciplinary Faculty	7,3
Interdisciplinary Faculty Forum	7,3
International Meeting Center	7,0
Research Camp	6,7

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Task 1.4 – Good practices from leading universities
Workshop WP5
Task Leader: UROS
Michael Leyer, Wieland Müller, Angelina Schilling
27th of September 2023

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Agenda

Time	Description	Provided Material
BLOCK 1: 15MIN	Topic: Recap of best practices of UROS + and UNICAL Goal: Overview of practices	Short information on program points of interest
BLOCK 2: 15MIN	Topic: Evaluation and selection of practices (Separate for ULPGC + UAc) Goal: Selection of practices	Assessment sheet for practice selection
BLOCK 3: 30MIN	Topic: Definition of tasks for each selected practice (Separate for ULPGC + UAc) Goal: Initial SMART Actionplan	SMART Template for tasks
BLOCK 4: 10MIN	Wrap-up/ Closure	

WP5 - Connection with business environment: knowledge transfer and spin-offs

This WPs will aim at improving and restructuring current knowledge transfer supporting mechanisms and practices at Widening organizations. In particular dedicated trainings for researchers will be organized and technical assistance will be provided to Widening Universities for the establishment of Spin-offs supporting offices.

Topics of Interest

- ULPGC: How to promote technology transfer activities (patents, spin-offs, etc.) among university teaching staff
 - UAC: KTT office and KTT literacy for UAc staff members and researchers
 - UAC: Patent and IP activities
 - UAC: Startup and Entrepreneurs events support + Incubation services
 - UAC: Industry engagement
- 1. Knowledge and Technology Transfer
 - 2. Start-Up and Entrepreneurship Centre
 - 3. Partnerships (Business)

1. Knowledge and Technology Transfer

Knowledge and Technology Transfer Office:
University of Rostock Service GmbH (URSG)

Patent and Standards Centre

2. Start-Up and Entrepreneurship Centre

- Idea Contests: Country, Nation, Europe
- Seminars in University Teaching
- Spinoff Program
- Incubation Program
- Accelerator Program

3. Partnerships (Business)

- Partnerships between Chairs and Industry
- Careers Service
- Job Fair
- "Entrepreneur Days"

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**Thank you for participating
and your valuable input!**

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UAc

actions	
Partnerships between chairs and industry	10,0
Careers Service	9,6
"Entrepreneur Days"	9,0
Seminars in University Teaching	8,8
Spinoff Program	8,8
Careers Service	8,6
Idea contests: Country wide, nation wide, Europe	8,5
Accelerator Program	8,5
Job Fair	8,3
Patent and Standards Centre	8,1
Centre for Entrepreneurship	7,6
University of Rostock Service GmbH (URSG)	5,6

ULPGC

actions	
Partnerships between chairs and industry	10,0
Spinoff Program	9,5
Incubation Program	9,5
Accelerator Program	9,5
Patent and Standards Centre	9,0
Centre for Entrepreneurship	8,0
University of Rostock Service GmbH (URSG)	7,5
Careers Service	7,3
"Entrepreneur Days"	7,3
Seminars in University Teaching	6,8
Idea contests: Country wide, nation wide, Europe	6,5
Job Fair	6,5

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Excellent Peripheries for a Strong European Research Area (EXPER)

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Task 1.4: Workshop on Good Practices 25th – 27th of September 2023 via Zoom

Task Leader: UROS
Michael Leyer, Wieland Müller, Angelina Schilling

Task Description

The three concluded workshops are an integral component of the EXPER modernization strategies. Focused on promoting excellent and responsible research, fostering academia-business cooperation, and enhancing the attractiveness of researchers' careers, the workshop served as a collaborative platform for all EXPER partners and their communities. Participants had the opportunity to discuss existing structures, services, and practices, particularly those successfully implemented by UROS and UNICAL. Beyond knowledge-sharing, the workshop aimed to collectively plan for upcoming capacity-building activities under work packages WP3, WP4, and WP5. This planning was informed by insights gathered from assessments completed under Tasks 1.2 and 1.3.

Results

The workshops spanned over a period of three days, providing ample time for in-depth discussions and planning. As a result, participants

1. Ranked each action from leading universities (in an assessment sheet) by the importance to fulfill the goal of each WP (WP3, WP4, WP5)
→ Results are presented in a ranking for each WP and each university individually
see next sections within this document
2. Collected specific tasks for each action. Thereby integrating best practices from leading universities, proposals by UROS members and new ideas
→ Results are presented in a SMART action plan for each university
see Recommendations SMART Action Plan

For a comprehensive overview of the workshop structure and content please see the document

 Workshop Summary

Key Takeaways: Assessment Sheets

It could be observed that each university has a different focus as their rating diverges recognizably. Thus, separate action plans are required for each university. Another observable was that some universities have already implemented certain best practices, confirming their effectiveness. As for the evaluation of practices, the ratings varied between 5.6 and 10. This range shows that all discussed practices hold value and are worth considering for adoption. However, special attention should be given to those practices with a rating above 8, as they are likely to offer the most immediate and impactful benefits.

ULPGC Ranking

For all work packages, it can be seen that the focus is more on work packages 4 and 5 than on work package 3. For WP3, the most important is the implementation of an induction plan, an online learning platform and a welcome center for foreign researchers to attract researchers from other countries and to promote global collaboration. For WP4, all automation measures (workflow automation, remote access, electronic signatures, digital document management, digital forms) are scored at least 9. In addition, an intranet for employees and a bilingual website should be prioritized. Other important measures include interdepartmental collaboration and participation in university alliances. In addition, the establishment of a project service center to support researchers in all administrative activities for externally funded projects should be prioritized. Within WP5, it is particularly important to promote partnerships between chairs and industry. This also involves the implementation of an Entrepreneurship Center and its offered programs, such as Spinoff, Incubation and Accelerator. It is to be decided whether only the programs or the implementation of such a center itself is required. With a rating of 9 points, the implementation of a patent and standardization center is recommended.

For detailed recommendations for every action please see the table

Recommendations SMART Action Plan

WP3 ULPGC

actions	
Online Learning Platform	8,4
Onboarding plan	8,4
Welcome Centre for Foreign Researchers	8,0
Service Portal for Employees	7,6
Inclusion Action Plans	7,0
Diversity Office	7,0
Family Office	7,0
Gender Equality Office	6,6
University Health Management	6,4
Incentive Policy	6,3
Scientific Qualification Courses	5,7
Didactic Certificate	5,7
Female Mentoring	5,0

WP4 ULPGC

actions	
Intranet	9,7
Project Service Center	9,7
Workflow Automation	9,7
Remote Access	9,7
University Alliance	9,3
Cross-departmental collaboration	9,3
Bilingual Website	9,3
E-Signatures	9,3
Digital Document Management	9,3
Online/ Digital Forms	9,0
Knowledge Sharing Hub	8,3
Information Platform for External Funded Projects	8,3
Communication concept	8,0
Newsletter: Weekly via Mail	8,0
Interdisciplinary Faculty	7,3
Interdisciplinary Faculty Forum	7,3
International Meeting Center	7,0
Research Camp	6,7

WP5 ULPGC

actions	
Partnerships between chairs and industry	10,0
Spinoff Program	9,5
Incubation Program	9,5
Accelerator Program	9,5
Patent and Standards Centre	9,0
Centre for Entrepreneurship	8,0
University of Rostock Service GmbH (URSG)	7,5
Careers Service	7,3
"Entrepreneur Days"	7,3
Seminars in University Teaching	6,8
Idea contests: Country wide, nation wide, Europe	6,5
Job Fair	6,5

UAc Ranking

Across all work packages, it can be seen that the focus is more on work packages 4 and 5 than on work package 3. With regard to WP3, the implementation of an onboarding plan is particularly important. In addition, there is a high demand for scientific qualification courses and an online learning platform. The implementation of a service portal for employees, which is essentially a website with all relevant information and documents, is also desired. With a score above 8 points, an incentive policy and university health management should also be addressed. For WP4, almost all measures received a high rating. Outstanding here are the establishment of a bilingual website and a project service center that supports researchers with administrative questions regarding third-party funding. Measures to automate processes are rated highly, but have already been implemented at the university. There would therefore be no need for action. With regard to WP5, the most important thing is to promote partnerships between chairs and industry. Furthermore, it is about the implementation of an Entrepreneurship Center and its offered programs, such as Spinoff, Incubation and Accelerator. It has to be decided whether only the programs or the implementation of such a center itself is needed.

For detailed recommendations for every action please see the table

Recommendations SMART Action Plan

WP3 UAc

actions	
Onboarding plan	9,1
Scientific Qualification Courses	8,8
Service Portal for Employees	8,5
Incentive Policy	8,3
Online Learning Platform	8,1
University Health Management	8,0
Welcome Centre for Foreign Researchers	7,9
Inclusion Action Plans	7,3
Gender Equality Office	6,9
Didactic Certificate	6,8
Diversity Office	6,2
Female Mentoring	6,2
Family Office	5,9

WP4 UAc

actions	
Bilingual Website	9,7
Project Service Center	9,4
Remote Access	9,3
Online/ Digital Forms	9,2
Cross-departmental collaboration	9,0
Interdisciplinary Faculty	8,8
University Alliance	8,8
Workflow Automation	8,8
Digital Document Management	8,7
Information Platform for External Funded Projects	8,4
Research Camp	8,4
Interdisciplinary Faculty Forum	8,1
Intranet	8,1
Communication concept	8,0
Knowledge Sharing Hub	7,6
Newsletter: Weekly via Mail	7,1
International Meeting Center	6,9
E-Signatures	6,9

WP5 UAc

actions	
Partnerships between chairs and industry	10,0
Careers Service	9,6
"Entrepreneur Days"	9,0
Seminars in University Teaching	8,8
Spinoff Program	8,8
Careers Service	8,6
Idea contests: Country wide, nation wide, Europe	8,5
Accelerator Program	8,5
Job Fair	8,3
Patent and Standards Centre	8,1
Centre for Entrepreneurship	7,6
University of Rostock Service GmbH (URSG)	5,6

Information on the table recommendations for SMART Action Plan

This table serves as a recommendation for the action plan being developed as part of Task 2.4 with Task Leader ULPGC. The table includes the overarching practices presented by UROS during the workshops and evaluated by participants in the second block of the workshop. The remainder of the table follows the SMART template:

- The "S-Specific" contains the specific task from the 3rd block of workshops where the participants collected ideas.
- The "M-Measurable" contains suggestions from UROS on how to measure the success of implementing the task.
- The "A-Achievable" follows a categorization made by UROS from easy to difficult. However, universities are advised to cross-check the values.
- The "R-Relevant" provides information on the relevance of the measure to meeting the goal of the corresponding AP.
- The "T-Timebound" field must be completed by the universities as they have the information about the resources available to implement each task.

Contact Information

Prof. Dr. Michael Leyer

Chief Scientific Executive
Institute for Business Administration- Center for Entrepreneurship
Tel.: +49 (0)381 498 4100
michael.leyer@uni-rostock.de

Dr. Martin Setzkorn

Managing Director
Institute for Business Administration- Center for Entrepreneurship
Tel.: +49 (0) 381 498 1198
martin.setzkorn@uni-rostock.de

Wieland Müller

Research Assistant University of Rostock
Institute for Business Administration- Center for Entrepreneurship
Tel.: +49 (0)381-498 4380
wieland.mueller@uni-rostock.de

Angelina Schilling

Research Assistant University of Rostock
Institute for Business Administration- Center for Entrepreneurship
Tel.: +49 (0)381-498 4570
angelina.schilling@uni-rostock.de

Recommendations UAc SMART Action Plan					
Superordinate Practise	Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Relevant	Timebound
	Ideas for specific tasks from UAc Workshop	Measurement proposals from UROS	Simple, medium or difficult?	Does it meet our goals of the WP?	Time target of Uac
WP3 - Strengthening researchers' careers attractiveness					
Diversity Office	Cultural Awareness Workshops Celebration of thematic days (Erasmus day, Different New Years, etc)	Attendance numbers, pre- and post-workshop surveys Number of events, attendee feedback	Medium Simple	Cultural diversity Cultural integration	
Gender Equality Office	Gender Equality Plan	Gender ratio in staff, policy adoption rate	already implemented	Gender equality	
Family Office	Childcare Assistance Program Celebration of several family days (reception of new students, opening and closure of academic year, christmas, etc.)	Enrollment numbers, parent feedback Number of events, attendance numbers	Medium to Difficult Simple	Work-life balance Family-friendly policies	
Welcome Centre for Foreign Researchers	Implementation of structures for foreign researchers Tour around university	Number of foreign researchers, satisfaction surveys Attendance, tour completion rates	Medium Simple	Talent acquisition Onboarding process	
Service Portal for Employees	One Platform with all documents and information Internal information, requests for sick, parental leave Tracking of employee internal training	Unique logins, documents downloaded Completion rates for leave requests, HR feedback Completion rates, skill assessments	Medium to Difficult Medium Medium	Centralized information Staff welfare Skill development	
Inclusion Action Plans	Implement inclusion action plan	Diversity indices, retention rates	Medium to Difficult	Inclusivity	
Female Mentoring	Skill-Building Workshops for females	Attendance, skill assessments	Medium	Gender equality, skill development	
University Health Management	Mental health support Work life balance awareness	Counseling session attendance, mental health surveys Attendance rates, pre- and post-event surveys	Medium to Difficult Medium	Employee well-being Work-life balance	
Onboarding Plan	Welcome Package Mail with all relevant information (including Academia documentation) Tour to main facilities Senior Tutor advisor Rectory welcoming protocol Life quality support (accommodation, etc)	Email open rates, user engagement Tour completion rates, attendee feedback Session attendance, skill assessments Protocol adoption rate, feedback forms Usage rates, user satisfaction surveys	Simple Simple Medium Simple to Medium Medium to Difficult	Onboarding procedure Onboarding, orientation Skill development, mentoring Institutional welcome Quality of life, well-being	
Online Learning Platform	Platform Online seminars	Unique logins, features used Attendance, engagement metrics	Medium to Difficult Medium	Centralized information Skill and knowledge development	
Didactic Certificate	University Quality teaching programs	Program enrollments, graduation rates	Medium to Difficult	Quality teaching	
Scientific Qualification Courses	Scientific calls and programs workshops Advance research methods Focus on the top ranking R Project Management Skills How-to-publish workshops IP Workshops	Application numbers, attendee evaluations Paper submissions, research outcomes Rankings improvement, citations Project completion rates, team feedback Workshop attendance, post-workshop publications Attendance, post-workshop IP applications	Medium Medium to Difficult Medium to Difficult Medium Medium Medium	Research development Research advancement Research excellence Skill development, project efficiency Academic publishing skills Knowledge transfer, skill	
Career Development and Incentives	Foment and recognize knowledge and technology transfer - patent, spinoff creation recognition Offer competitive compensation Merit recognition Share of best practices to young professors/researchers Improving working conditions Improving work/life balance Reward professors/researchers which are more dedicated to KTT (performance metrics) Career progression	Number of patents, spinoffs, recognitions Retention rates, job satisfaction surveys Number of recognitions, feedback Workshop attendance, implementation rates Employee satisfaction surveys, turnover rates Work/life balance survey results Number of rewarded individuals, KTT activity Promotion rates, job satisfaction	Medium to Difficult Medium to Difficult Medium Medium Medium to Difficult Medium Medium to Difficult Medium to Difficult	Knowledge transfer, research Career conditions, retention Career advancement, motivation Skill development, knowledge transfer Work environment, satisfaction Work/life balance, well-being Recognition, knowledge transfer Career advancement, skill development	
WP4 - Promoting Excellent and Responsible Research					
Interdisciplinary	Interdepartmental/intercenter cooperation External partnerships with other HEIs Community Management Department or Responsible Showcasing of R&D achievements (internal/external) Internal R&D strategy for optimization of tasks/resources	Number of joint projects Number of partnerships Community engagement metrics Event attendance, media coverage KPI improvements	Medium Medium to Difficult Medium Medium Medium to Difficult	Fosters transnational working groups Enhances transsectoral collaboration Facilitates civil society participation Showcases research related to societal challenges Improves research management, optimizes resources	
Communication	Newsletter: Weekly via Mail Intranet Bilingual website EU funding opportunities	Subscriber count, open rates User engagement metrics Language-specific user metrics Funds obtained, applications submitted	Simple Medium to Difficult Medium Medium to Difficult	Disseminates information, Open Science practices Facilitates internal communication Increases reach, fosters inclusivity Secures financial resources	
Partnerships (Research)	Information Platform for External Funded Projects Project Service Center (support to designed and submit projects) Research Camp Promoting R&D staff mobility EU University Alliances - get in touch with other existing Alliances	User count, projects listed Projects submitted, success rate Attendee count, post-camp surveys Number of staff exchanges Partnerships formed	Medium Medium to Difficult Medium Medium to Difficult Medium to Difficult	Provides a database for collaborative projects Improves project submission quality Fosters R&D staff skill development Enhances research capabilities, new perspectives Builds broader collaborative networks	
Automation Processes	Online/ Digital Forms E-Signatures Workflow Automation Digital Document Management Remote Access	Usage rates, error rates Adoption rates, saved time Task completion speed, error reduction Retrieval speed, user satisfaction Utilization rates, access speed	already implemented already implemented already implemented already implemented already implemented	Simplifies data gathering, improves efficiency Streamlines workflow, improves efficiency Enhances research management Facilitates data management Enables flexible work, ensures data access	
WP5 - Connection with business environment: knowledge transfer and spin-offs					
Knowledge and Technology Transfer Office	Training on IP for the researchers Identify the resources needed for KTT Secure additional funding (public and private) Seminars to raise awareness and KTT Literacy (processes, importance, benefits)	Attendance, knowledge retention List completeness, staff involvement Funds raised, source diversity Attendance, engagement metrics	Medium Medium Medium to Difficult Medium	Directly enhances knowledge transfer Critical for KTT and innovation Enables other WP5 activities Raises KTT awareness and literacy	
Patent and Standards Centre	Training on the registration of patents Alert the researchers for the importance of licensing Promotion and outreach of concepts	Completion rates, follow-up actions Engagement rates, licensing actions taken Reach, engagement	Medium Simple Medium	Enhances IP management and KTT Raises awareness about the value of licensing Expands the impact of WP5 activities	
Start-Up and Entrepreneurship Centre	Idea Contests: Country, Nation, Europe Seminars in University Teaching Spinoff Program Accelerator Program Stimulate the academic community for the importance of entrepreneurship	Entries received, quality Attendance, teaching effectiveness improvement Spinoff creation, milestones achieved Startups accelerated, funding acquired Awareness level, start-up initiatives	Medium to Difficult Medium Medium to Difficult Medium to Difficult Medium	Stimulates innovation and Improves teaching skills, indirectly aiding KTT Directly supports WP5's spin-off goals Supports the spin-off and innovation focus Builds a culture that supports WP5 objectives	
Partnerships between Chairs and Industry	Define a clear strategy for partnerships Narrow the relationship between the lead researchers and the local companies Involve the industry in the curriculum development and research projects	Partnerships formed, goals alignment Meetings held, collaborations formed Industry partnerships, curriculum changes	Medium Medium to Difficult Medium to Difficult	Facilitates other WP5 objectives through collaborative efforts Fosters relationships crucial for KTT Aligns curriculum and research with industry needs	
Careers Service	Entrepreneur Days Tours on industry Job Fair and Job procurement from the private sector	Attendance, engagement, follow-up initiatives Number of tours, participant feedback Companies participated, job placements	Medium Medium Medium	Encourages entrepreneurship in line with WP5 objectives Enhances understanding of industry-relevant research and tech Directly links researchers with employment opportunities in industry	

Recommendations ULPGC Smart Action Plan

Superordinate Practise	Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Relevant	Timebound
	Ideas for specific tasks from ULPGC Workshop	Measurement proposals from UROS	Simple, medium or difficult? Assessment by UROS	Does it meet our goals of the WP?	Time target of ULPGC
WP3 - Strengthening researchers' careers attractiveness					
Diversity Office	Cultural Awareness Workshops	With the facilitator of the workshop, Attendance, feedback surveys	Simple to Medium	Inclusive Career Conditions	
	Rector Delegate for diversity (culture, disability, religion)	Number of foreign employees/different culture/religion employees, Policies implemented, diversity metrics	Medium	Safe and Inclusive Environment	
	Anti-violence desk	Satisfaction rates, successful relocations	Simple	Addressing Diversity and Brain Drain	
Gender Equality Office	Rector Delegate for gender equality	Policies implemented, gender metrics	Medium	Safe and Inclusive Environment	
	Gender Equality Plan	Compliance rate, gender metrics	Difficult	Gender Equality Assurance	
Family Office	Childcare Assistance Program	Utilization rates, feedback	Simple	Gender Equality Enhancement	
	Flexible Work Policies	Adoption rates, employee satisfaction	Medium	Work-Life Balance Improvement	
	Kindergarden for children of employees	Utilization rates, feedback	Difficult	Better Work-Life Balance	
	Baby pit stop	Utilization rates, feedback	Simple	Work-Life Balance Augmentation	
Welcome Centre for Foreign Researchers	Anti-violence desk	Satisfaction rates, successful relocations	Simple	Immediate Relief for Working Parents	
	Assistance before, during and after the stay	Applications number,	Medium	Talent Retention and Attraction	
	Helping before coming	Number of foreign researchers who arrive, Successful relocations, satisfaction rates	Medium	Initial Talent Relocation Assistance	
	International office	Number of international collaborations	Simple	International Opportunities and Brain Drain Reduction	
	Creation of a community of local researchers (Sharing common interests, knowledge, academic opportunities, etc.)	Membership numbers, engagement metrics	Medium	Local Researcher Collaboration	
Service Portal for Employees	IT support	Ticket resolution time, user satisfaction	Simple	Program Functional Necessity	
Inclusion Action Plans	Implement inclusion action plan	Metrics on inclusion, policy adoption	Medium	Direct Impact on Diversity and Career	
Female Mentoring	Skill-Building Workshops for females	Attendance, skills improvement metrics	Simple to Medium	Gender Equality and Skill Development	
	Networking events	Attendance, follow-up collaborations	Simple to Medium	Career Opportunities and Collaborations	
University Health Management	Access to a variety of Sports services	Utilization rates, feedback	Simple	Well-being and Work-Life Balance	
	University Sport Centre (CUS)	Utilization rates, feedback	Simple	Well-being Promotion	
	Health Centre	Utilization rates, health metrics	Simple	Overall Well-being Support	
	Preventive Medicine Office	Utilization rates, effectiveness of prevention	Simple	Preventive Health Focus	
	Nutritional advisor	Consultation rates, improvement in metrics	Simple	Overall Well-being Support (repeated)	
Onboarding Plan	Welcome Package Mail with all relevant information	Open rates, engagement	Simple	Initial Settling-in Assistance	
	Tour to main facilities	Attendance, feedback	Simple	Newcomer Facility Acquaintance	
	Welcome Workshops	Attendance, feedback	Simple	New Member Orientation	
	working before by internet	Productivity metrics, employee satisfaction	Simple	Work-Life Balance Improvement	
	Senior Tutor advisor	Consultation rates, feedback	Simple	Academic and Research Progress	
Online Learning Platform	Forma mentis (Platform for training and up-dating of skills for employees)	Course completion rates, skills assessments	Medium	Employee Skill Up-Dating	
Didactic Certificate	Implementation of didactic course	Attendance, course evaluations	Medium	Educational Opportunities Enhancement	
Scientific Qualification Courses	Scientific calls and programs workshops	Attendance, number of proposals submitted	Medium to Difficult	Research Skills and Career Boost	
Career Development and Incentives	Incentives policy	Engagement rates, employee satisfaction	Medium	Career Progression and Work Satisfaction	
WP4 - Promoting Excellent and Responsible Research					
Interdisciplinary	Interdisciplinary Faculty	Number of departments involved, number of projects	Difficult	Transnational and Transsectoral Groups	
	Promote participation in calls among departments for new projects	Number of joint applications	Simple to Medium	Interdisciplinary Research	
	Interdisciplinary studies degree programs	Enrollment rates, program evaluations	Medium	Interdisciplinary Training	
	assembling interdisciplinary research teams broadening participation outside academia (ex. startups, corporates, etc)	Number of interdisciplinary projects Number of partnerships with external entities	Medium Medium	Diverse Research Approaches Societal and Industrial Impact	
Communication	Newsletter: Weekly via Mail	Subscription rates, engagement metrics	Simple	Community Engagement	
	Intranet	User activity, number of documents shared	Simple to Medium	Internal Communication	
	Establish easy ways of new communication, such as periodic meetings on interesting topics	Frequency of periodical meetings	Simple to Medium	Knowledge Sharing	
	Staff training on IT communication	Number of people enrolled on the courses	Simple to Medium	Communication Efficiency	
Partnerships (Research)	Information Platform for External Funded Projects	User engagement, number of accessed resources	Medium	External Funding	
	Project Service Center: inform about open opportunities, support preparation of the project proposals, administrative, etc.	Number of supported projects, satisfaction surveys	Medium	Project Support	
	Research Camp	Attendance, number of research ideas generated	Medium	Intensive Collaboration	
	Promote attendance of international conferences	Number of attendees, conferences attended	Simple to Medium	International Collaboration	
	Promoting staff mobility	Number of staff participating, destinations	Simple to Medium	Research Skills and International Relations	
International Meeting Center	Translation of research projects in English	Number of projects translated	Simple to Medium	International Research Accessibility	
Automation Processes	Online/ Digital Forms	User completion rates, number of forms	Simple	Administrative Streamlining	
	E-Signatures	Usage rate, number of documents	Simple	Documentation Speed	
	Workflow Automation	Tasks automated, time saved	Simple to Medium	Operational Efficiency	
	Digital Document Management	Number of documents stored, access frequency	Simple to Medium	Information Management	
	Remote Access	Number of users, usage frequency	Simple to Medium	Flexible Working Conditions	
	One user interface	User satisfaction, number of apps integrated	Simple to Medium	Tech Simplification	
WP5 - Connection with business environment: knowledge transfer and spin-offs					
Knowledge and Technology Transfer Office	KTT Education and training programs	Number of participants, feedback, completion rate	Medium	Direct Knowledge Transfer	
	Active scouting of KTT opportunities	Number of opportunities identified, engagement metrics	Simple to Medium	Innovation and External Partnerships	
	Orientation on application and use of knowledge	Number of orientation sessions, feedback	Simple to Medium	Effective Knowledge Utilization	
	Giving access to infrastructures and resources	Number of projects tested, utilization rates	Simple to Medium	Practical Testing and Validation	
Patent and Standards Centre	Up-to-date knowledge on IP protection	Number of participants, feedback	Simple to Medium	IP Protection	
	Financial support for IP procedures	Amount of funding secured, number of supported projects	Simple to Medium	Enabling IP Procedures	
	Develop an IP marketplace	Number of listings, user engagement	Medium	IP Transactions and Licensing	
Start-Up and Entrepreneurship Centre	Idea Contests: Country, Nation, Europe	Number of submissions, audience size	Simple to Medium	Community Involvement in Innovation	
	Seminars in University Teaching	Number of seminars, participant feedback	Simple	Teaching Quality Capacity	
	Networking with local startups and SMEs	Number of partnerships formed, feedback	Simple to Medium	Local Industry Relations	
	Supporting internships with the industry	Number of internships, intern feedback	Simple to Medium	Practical Training and Industry Relations	
	Promoting open innovation programs	Number of programs, participant metrics	Simple to Medium	Knowledge Transfer and Innovation	
Partnerships between Chairs and Industry	Programs where researchers work closely with industry	Number of joint projects, outcomes	Medium	Industry-Research Collaboration	
	Promoting industrial PhD programs, scholarships,	Number of scholarships, application rate	Medium	Advanced Research Training	
Careers Service	Full information program on research career & KTT	Program completion rates, participant feedback	Simple to Medium	Career Paths and KTT Capabilities	
	Entrepreneur Days	Attendance, number of ventures showcased	Simple to Medium	Community Entrepreneurship	
	Job Fair	Number of companies attending, job placements	Simple to Medium	Employment and Industry Relations	
	Training in specific skills demanded by companies	Number of trainings, participant feedback	Simple to Medium	Academic-Industry Alignment	

Best practices for promoting scientific and economic capacities at the University of Rostock

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Prof. Dr. Michael Leyer (michael.leyer@uni-rostock.de)

M.Sc. Angelina Schilling (angelina.schilling@uni-rostock.de)

M.Sc. Wieland Müller (wieland.mueller@uni-rostock.de)

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1 DIVERSITY MANAGEMENT

1.1 DIVERSITY OFFICE

The Diversity Office supports the strategic development of the university in the overarching fields of diversity management and equal opportunities, welcoming culture, inclusion and accessibility, health management, family friendliness, and equality and, since the end of 2020, sustainability development. The “KarriereWegeMentoring” (Career Path Mentoring) project is also part of the staff unit and provides targeted support for (young) female scientists.

1.2 GENDER EQUALITY OFFICE

The Equal Opportunities Officer supports the management and the central bodies of the University of Rostock in fulfilling their legal mandate to promote the actual implementation of equal rights for women and men and to work towards the elimination of existing disadvantages - especially for women in science.

Furthermore, the Equal Opportunity Officer advises, informs and supports all university members in reconciling study/work and family and accompanies the enforcement of the General Equal Treatment Act with regard to protection against discrimination on the grounds of gender and sexual harassment.

1.3 INCLUSION ACTION PLANS

Students with disabilities or chronic illnesses in particular are still confronted with study and learning conditions that take their individual needs into account only to a limited extent or not at all in everyday university life.

Against the background of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) of the United Nations (2006) inclusive university teaching aims at the development and implementation of barrier-free study structures and barrier-free teaching offers.

1.4 FAMILY OFFICE

A scientific qualification means fixed-term contracts and often a double burden. How can the compatibility of family and science be achieved? What do scientists who want to pursue an academic career with children have to consider? We would like to support you in finding the right information and advice for you from the existing offers on the topic of reconciling science and family.

2 RESEARCHER SUPPORT

2.1 UNIVERSITY HEALTH MANAGEMENT

The “URgesund” steering committee is the central steering and decision-making body of university health management. The goal is to initiate and support health-promoting working and living conditions at the University of Rostock. The main task is to create and establish information offers and measures in the field of health in order to maintain and promote the well-being and health of employees and students at the University of Rostock. “URgesund” advise on the strategic orientation as well as financial and legal issues that arise in this context.

2.2 FEMALE MENTORING PROGRAM

The focus here is on supporting female doctoral students in their orientation toward a further career in science or a professional career in business, industry, public administration or associations.

The special focus of the mentoring program is on one-to-one mentoring, i.e., each mentee is individually accompanied by a mentor in her personal career planning. In addition, a high-quality seminar program is offered on topics such as self-marketing and career planning. The two networking events on "Successful Careers" and "Research Funding" focus on connecting with established women in order to share in and benefit from their experiences. In peer mentoring, mentees work on self-determined topics in a peer group of 5 to 6 mentees. They support each other effectively and deal intensively with their own goals and progress. For this purpose, the mentees learn the method of "collegial consultation". This results in a non-competitive exchange at a very high level, which also benefits from the fact that the mentees come from different disciplines.

2.3 WELCOME CENTRE FOR FOREIGN RESEARCHERS

The Welcome Center / Global Café supports and advises foreign doctoral candidates and visiting scientists. Here they can obtain information on topics such as work permits, immigration law and language courses. The services offered by the Welcome Center also include help with filling out forms and support in finding accommodation.

2.4 GRADUATE ACADEMY

The university-wide Graduate Academy is the central service institution and coordination point for young scientists.

The central goal of the Graduate Academy is to support and promote young scientists at the University of Rostock. The range of services includes the qualification program, funding offers for participation in external qualification measures, travel allowances and various networking opportunities. The qualification program serves the further

development of interdisciplinary competences in a conscious and intrinsically motivated way. Members of the Graduate Academy can use their budget, which is made available to them by the Graduate Academy, for the fee-based courses. Members of the Graduate Academy can use up to 500 EUR of their membership budget for travel grants. In addition, the Graduate Academy is the contact point for all questions and concerns regarding young scientists. We see accompanying, advising and informing as our elementary basis. We focus on the needs of our addressees - the young scientists.

2.5 GRADUATE SCHOOLS

Graduate schools are structured doctoral programs funded in Germany by the German Research Foundation (DFG). These programs promote interdisciplinary research projects and offer doctoral students' intensive supervision and a broad range of qualification measures.

Graduate schools offer doctoral students an intensive research environment and the opportunity to work in an interdisciplinary team. The doctorate in a Research Training Group is usually scheduled for three to four years and, in addition to the actual research work, also includes a variety of qualification measures, such as workshops, colloquia and summer schools.

Current research focus areas at the University of Rostock are: Smart Appliance Ensembles for Mobile Applications, Interactions between Implants and Biosystems or Smart Appliance Ensembles for Mobile Applications. However, any other subject areas can also be funded.

3 RESEARCHER TRAINING AND SKILL ENHANCEMENT

3.1 ONLINE LEARNING PLATFORM

The online learning portal offers an interdisciplinary selection of online learning opportunities on a wide range of topics. It distinguishes between short micro-lectures, video lectures and complex online courses with exercises and tests. The educational offer of the open University of Rostock is aimed, among others, at professionals, teachers, companies, project partners and students

Examples:

- Project management
- Patent protection for start-ups
- Bogs - an introduction

3.2 SCIENTIFIC QUALIFICATION COURSES

The qualification program serves the further development of interdisciplinary competences in a conscious and intrinsically motivated way. It targets PhD students of the university. Topics are among others academic writing, reading, project management and disputation training.

3.3 DIDACTIC CERTIFICATE OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ROSTOCK

The University Didactics of the University of Rostock supports teachers of the University of Rostock and of universities and colleges in the state of MV in their competence development and continuing education. The portfolio of events in higher education didactics offers workshops that are designed to meet the current needs of teaching and provide a framework for interdisciplinary exchange. Through a practical approach, the participants are able to apply the knowledge gained directly in their own teaching.

4 SCHOLARSHIPS AND RESEARCH FUNDING

4.1 PHD STUDENTS

- Financing of external qualification measures - funding offer for members of the Graduate Academy
- HERMES Funding: supports research stays of young scientists abroad that are linked to an application for third-party funding
- “KarriereWegeMentoring” - support program for female doctoral students ([see 2.2](#))
- State Graduate Support - Doctoral Scholarship Program for Graduates with Outstanding Achievements
- Open Access Publication Fund - Fund for the financial support of open access publications
- Female professors' program: Equal opportunity measures (scholarships, material grants, fund for student assistants) for the promotion of young female researchers
- Doctoral scholarship program "Our best masters do their doctorate in Rostock" - Doctoral scholarship program for the best master's graduates
- Travel allowances for participation in symposia - Support for members of the Graduate Academy
- Bridging, reintegration and graduation scholarships for junior researchers - Scholarships for junior researchers with extensive family responsibilities

4.2 POSTDOCS

- Funding of external qualification measures - funding offer for members of the Graduate Academy
- HERMES research funding - funding for research stays abroad
- “Impuls Forschung” - start-up financing of research cooperations of the member universities in the Association of North German Universities (VNU)
- “KarriereWegeMentoring” - Strengthening of young female scientists on their career path ([see 2.2](#))
- Open Access Publication Fund - Fund for the financial support of open access publications
- Program for female professors: Equal opportunity measures (scholarships, material grants, funds for student assistants) for the promotion of young female researchers
- Travel allowances for participation in symposia - Support offered by the Graduate Academy
- Scholarships for bridging, reintegration and graduation scholarships for junior researchers - Scholarships for junior researchers with extensive family responsibilities to complete their qualification phase

4.3 JUNIOR PROFESSORS

- “Impuls Forschung” - start-up funding for research cooperation of the member universities in the Association of North German Universities (VNU)
- Open Access Publication Fund - financial support for open access publications in journals
- Program for female professors: equal opportunity measures (scholarships, material grants, funds for student assistants) for the promotion of young female researchers
- Program for Female Professors:
 - advancing the equality of women and men at universities,
 - a sustainable improvement in the representation of women at all levels of qualification in the science system, and
 - increasing the number of female scientists in top positions in the scientific field.

4.4 “SOCIETY OF PROMOTERS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ROSTOCK “

The “Society of Promoters of the University of Rostock” (“Gesellschaft der Förderer der Universität Rostock”) was founded to give members, graduates and friends of the

university, politicians and representatives from business, science and culture the opportunity to help stimulate the development of the university.

For example, the sponsoring society awards up to three University of Rostock sponsorship prizes annually for outstanding dissertations defended at the University of Rostock. In addition, a sponsorship prize for teaching is awarded annually.

5 RESEARCH PROJECTS

5.1 PROJECTS SERVICE CENTER

The team of strategic research consulting advises and accompanies members of the university on research programs that are particularly relevant to higher education policy, such as EU Horizon Europe (especially ERC grants), as well as DFG Collaborative Research Centers and Research Training Groups.

The Project Administration team combines all services provided by Central University Administration related to the administrative processes of acquiring, accepting, managing, and closing projects.

5.2 INFORMATION PLATFORM FOR EXTERNAL FUNDED PROJECTS

The research database is a platform of the University of Rostock, through which information on third-party funded projects, doctorates and postdoctoral theses as well as scientific publications at the University of Rostock can be searched.

In addition, national third-party funders are presented online. In addition, current calls for proposals for funding programs are presented in funding news or made available via links to the websites.

5.3 INFORMATION SERVICE "RESEARCH, INTERNATIONAL AFFAIRS AND TRANSFER"

The information service is an e-mail service that provides you with targeted and accurate information on research funding.

Members can register with their e-mail address and create an individual user profile. They can specify scientific fields, types of funding and sponsors about which you would like to receive information. At a time of their choice, members receive an e-mail with the current information that is important for them. If members need additional information, they can search the database at any time.

The system includes calls for proposals from the funding institutions DFG, BMBF & ministries, EU, foundations, DAAD & AvH as well as others and lists the funding

categories project funding, promotion of young researchers, prizes & competitions, international, transfer and events.

6 NETWORKING

6.1 BEYOND PEERS

The project beyond peers is a joint initiative for women from the fields of business, science, society, creative industries and politics. The aim of the initiative beyond peers is to expand your target group regionally and nationally, to increase your visibility and to grow together with others in the network.

6.2 RESEARCH CAMP

The research camp is an interdisciplinary exchange and networking platform. In an informal and familiar atmosphere, scientists from all disciplines/collaborative projects of the University of Rostock as well as the affiliated institutes present their own research topic in the popular poster session, openly offer other scientist's potential synergies for active networking and cooperation, and keep an eye out for existing contacts and new ones to be established themselves. The research camp is an important orientation point for young scientists and offers representatives of the state government and industry an opportunity to get an overview of the status of current research projects.

6.3 MARE BALTICUM FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMM

With the aim to combine the interdisciplinary guiding principle of the University of Rostock with the support of scientists in early career phases, the University of Rostock announces the MARE BALTICUM FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM annually. The fellowship program supports guest stays (max. 3 months) of national as well as international scientists*. Scientists of the University of Rostock who are members of the Interdisciplinary Faculty are eligible to apply.

On the one hand, the program is intended to provide impulses for the initiation and preparation of joint research projects. At the same time, the application is connected with the conception of a series of events for scientists in early career phases. The series of events is intended to serve the scientific examination of a superordinate topic and to facilitate an interdisciplinary and interfaculty exchange.

6.4 ROSTOCK INTERNATIONAL HOUSE

At the Rostock International House, all international exchange activities of the University of Rostock come together. It is our task to coordinate international relations and to develop and implement projects and programs with foreign partners. In addition, we provide advice and consultation for foreign students and prospective students, advices for German students who wish to study abroad and implement the ERASMUS+ program.

6.5 INTERNATIONAL MEETING CENTER

The aim of the International Meeting Center Rostock is to enable and promote scientific and cultural exchange among members of the university and other research institutions in the region, as well as the residents of the Hanseatic City of Rostock, and thus to further internationalize Rostock as a university location. The guest house is therefore more than just a place to live. For a temporary stay of 3 months to 2 years, the IBZ offers its guests comfortable living space in fully furnished apartments and a comprehensive range of support services for scientists and their families.

6.6 ENTERPRISE EUROPE NETWORK

The University of Rostock benefits together with the region through its membership in the Enterprise Europe Network. The Enterprise Europe Network supports and connects companies, universities and research institutions on issues related to innovation and internationalization, opening up foreign markets, finding business and project partners, participating in European funding programs and much more.

The Enterprise Europe Network focuses on the internationalization of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in industry, commerce and trade. Another focus is the promotion of cooperation and cluster formation between companies, universities and research institutions.

6.7 EU-CONEXUS

The University of Rostock is part of EU-CONEXUS. EU-CONEXUS is an association of nine European universities from France, Spain, Croatia, Romania, Greece, Lithuania, Ireland and Cyprus. The aim is to enable innovative and interdisciplinary research across national borders and to offer students a European study program. The thematic focus is on the sustainability of coastal regions.

The thematic focus is particularly relevant in view of the advancing climate change and its consequences on the increasingly densely populated coastal areas, as these regions are of crucial importance for energy production and transport, trade, aquaculture, fisheries as well as tourism.

In addition to the research and innovation dimensions, EU-CONEXUS also opens up a wide range of opportunities for students, for example European degree programs at Bachelor, Master and PhD level. Jointly, courses on different topics are offered, which can be credited at the University of Rostock.

- Minor in Coastal Development and Sustainable Maritime Tourism
- Minor in Blue Economy and Growth
- Joint Master Program in Marine Biotechnology
- PhD

7 ACADEMIA AND BUSINESS COOPERATION

7.1 URSG - TECHNOLOGY AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

The URSG (University of Rostock Service GmbH) is the central internal and external service point for transfer at the University of Rostock and sees itself as a mediator between science and industry. It supports both scientists and companies in the context of technology and knowledge transfer ...

- in the initiation and coordination of joint projects,
- in the acquisition of third-party funding
- in the transfer of scientific research results into the economy as well as
- in finding adequate partners.

7.2 VVB-MV – EXPLOITATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

From evaluation and patenting to the commercial exploitation of scientific inventions - the VVB-MV, together with its partners, supports the state's scientific institutions in all phases of the patenting and exploitation process.

In doing so, the VVB-MV is the contact point for around 3,000 scientists and also offers access to research results that are protected under patent law.

7.3 PNZ- PATENT AND STANDARD CENTER

The Patent and Standards Center (PNZ) of the Rostock University Library was opened in 1985. It provides information and services in all areas of industrial property protection. The services of the PNZ are not only available to university members, but can also be used by employees from small and medium-sized enterprises as well as by private inventors to realize innovative ideas.

7.4 CAREER SERVICE

The Careers Service supports students and graduates of the University of Rostock in planning their career entry - whether into dependent employment or self-employment. We want to enable students to discover the variety of possibilities after graduation, to formulate career goals early on and to contribute to their realization. We support graduates in making well thought-out, individually tailored decisions for their career paths and in presenting themselves convincingly to the job market in all respects.

At the same time, we are the contact address for companies wishing to recruit at the University of Rostock. We are the interface between the university and potential employers for students.

7.5 STUDENT RESEARCH PROJECTS AND THESES

Upon request and agreement, students can be given the opportunity to write their Bachelor's or Master's thesis in cooperation with a company.

8 ENTREPRENEURSHIP

The Center for Entrepreneurship is the central contact point for people interested in founding a company at the University of Rostock. The team of the center accompanies the students, graduates & scientists of the university in every phase of your start-up project - starting with the evaluation and structuring of your ideas and concepts up to the support in the formal and organizational implementation of the business start-up. The Center for Entrepreneurship advises on funding opportunities and provides support in the application process, e.g., for the EXIST-Start-up Grant, EXIST- Research Transfer. The Center for Entrepreneurship organizes various programs and events:

8.1 SEMINAR: SUCCESS FACTORS FOR PROFESSIONAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

The sub-module I of start-up teaching "Success factors of professional self-employment" serves to generally sensitize students to the entrepreneurial perspective. Entrepreneurial action competencies are acquired that enable the innovative utilization of knowledge.

8.2 SEMINAR: IDEA GENERATION AND DEVELOPMENT

In sub-module II of the start-up teaching "Idea generation and development", students learn the theoretical and practical basics of professional self-employment, work on a problem from the business world, among other things, and develop approaches to solutions using the design thinking method.

8.3 IDEA CONTEST

A yearly idea contest supports the development of founding ideas and the utilization of research results at the University of Rostock as well as the research area Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania and increases their chances of success. Since 2016 local idea competitions are executed at participating universities and colleges in Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania, which are financed with European social funds from 2014 to 2020. Furthermore, the best submissions from the local competition qualify for the participation on the national competition. The local as well as the national competition are executed only once per year through 2019.

The "Zentrum für Entrepreneurship" (ZfE) of the University of Rostock is responsible for the execution of the local competition as well as for the coordination of the national competition. The ZfE emphasizes to integrate the majority of the research institutes in

the country into the local competition at the University of Rostock as well as to cooperate with them and to support them with the identification respectively implementation of research and transfer potential.

There will be money-awards for the first three winners in both categories and money-awards in additional certain categories, which are sponsored from various businesses. Despite this, there is a possibility for participants to attend subsequent events to work targeted on their idea respectively on the implementation.

8.4 SPINOFF INCUBATION

This program refers to the support before the formal foundation of a start-up. The services provided by SPiNOFF range from the early identification of high-potential research ideas, to the acquisition of financial resources, to the support of the company's own start-up.

Among others, the program provides information on the following topics:

- Business model according to CANVAS
- Business plan development
- Marketing strategy and sales concept
- Financial planning
- Financing of the pre-foundation phase through support programs

8.5 INCUBATOR PROGRAM

The “Incubator” program has the goal of supporting innovative and young people interested in founding their own businesses. In doing so, the program not only want to promote the regional start-up scene, but also network with each other at the same time and thus create a community among like-minded people. The target audience is interdisciplinary, coaching and programs educate on: Pitch Training, Speech Training, Clarification of Financial Terms, Marketing Basics, Self-Promotion, Social Media Consulting. In addition, support is provided in the form of technology, facilities and a prototype workshop.

8.6 ACCELERATOR PROGRAM

The accelerator program builds on the incubator program. With the "accelerator" program, the University of Rostock supports young companies, teams and individuals with promising business models to further develop their business ideas, technologies and products in a customer-centric and fast way.

The program offers innovative start-ups not only mentoring and coaching by experienced and committed experts, but also access to a large network of investors, business partners and customers. During a maximum period of nine months, the founders are also

provided with the necessary infrastructure. The program focuses on the individual needs of the participating startups, for example, to help them enter international markets, grow faster, build up a customer base faster and develop the personnel pool faster.

8.7 MVPRENEUR DAY

The MVpreneur Day is organized annually by the Center for Entrepreneurship (ZfE) of the University of Rostock, this year modified as a weekly event series in cooperation with the Digitales Innovationszentrum Rostock (DIZ) GmbH.

9 INTERDISCIPLINARY FACULTY

In the Interdisciplinary Faculty, the various scientific disciplines merge and enter into a close dialogue with each other beyond the original disciplinary boundaries. The members of the faculty drive a wide range of externally funded, coordinated and often interdisciplinary research projects.

9.1 INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH PROJECTS

The members of the Department Maritime Systems drive a wide range of externally funded, coordinated and often interdisciplinary research projects.

Baltic Transcoast is a graduate program that explores the reciprocal processes between land and sea. The main goal is to train doctoral students in three-year steps to become experts of the coastal region. All research activities of the 13 ongoing doctoral theses are focused on the common research site "Heiligensee and Hütelmoor" northeast of Rostock.

Within the BACOSA (Baltic Coastal System Analysis and Status Evaluation) project, data on changes in land use pressure are compared with data on the historical ecosystem state of the German Baltic Sea coast from partners at the Universities of Rostock and Kiel. The focus is on trophic interactions, i.e. interactions in the nearshore network, and events that have a short-term effect.

More interdisciplinary ones can be found here: <https://www.inf.uni-rostock.de/en/mts/research/research-projects-and-networks/>

9.2 OCEAN TECHNOLOGY CAMPUS (OTC)

The Ocean Technology Campus is intended to strengthen German marine technology by opening up important markets and providing impetus for a worldwide knowledge-based sustainable use of the oceans. The campus with its location in Rostock's fishing port offers, on the one hand, real conditions for carrying out a wide variety of underwater tests in a specially constructed underwater test field and, on the other hand, a bundling of forces by locating companies and research institutions at the OTC.

9.3 OTC: SUMMER SCHOOL

Rostock's Ocean Technology (RoOT) Summer School is a two-week course at the end of August, which is based in and around the Ocean Technology Campus (OTC). 16 carefully chosen participants from academia and industry will have the unique opportunity to gain insight into various interdisciplinary aspects of ocean technology, with a special focus on the five fields of innovation which make up the Cluster OTC Rostock:

- Subsea Mobility & Autonomy
- Ocean Lense
- Digital Mission
- Sustainable Ocean Use
- Open Innovation

Specially tailored lectures and exercises will provide the participants with the required know-how to tackle real-world problems within various practical applications both on land and at sea (aboard Rostock's research catamaran Limanda). The program will also offer the opportunity to participate in a hackathon (with no-code/low-code options for participants that are not so familiar with coding) and to learn about advantages of open innovation, open source, networking and generally out-of-the-box thinking.

9.4 OTC: OPEN OCEAN LAB

The Ocean Open Lab (OOL) will be an open experimental workshop, a 'makerspace' dedicated to ocean technology. It doesn't matter if you are a citizen:in, a student, a graduate, an employee of a university or a company, a startup founder, a freelance inventor or a Best Ager. Everybody can come to our lab and gets free access to tools and technical equipment (e.g. 3D printer, soldering station), as well as to the necessary know-how for the realization of own marine technical ideas.

The aim of the project is to try out and establish open innovation processes as new forms of collaboration between business, science and the general public. Through a variety of event formats (hackathons, demo days, workshops, etc.), the networking of citizens with companies and research institutions is promoted.

9.5 OTC: INTERNATIONAL OCEAN ACCELERATOR

This novel accelerator program supports innovative marine and underwater technology companies in their start-up: from the idea to the growth phase.

With the International Ocean Accelerator, teams of experts from around the world are brought together to further develop start-up ideas related to marine and underwater topics.

The teams receive targeted support via the Accelerator network. They are given access to the marine technology infrastructure of the Future Cluster and can contact international experts and consortia from science and industry at any time.

The goal of the program is to enable talented individuals and their teams to realize their first projects with customers after the support period of six months, to arrange a start-up or follow-up financing round, and to aim for settlement at the Ocean Technology Campus Rostock.

5.3. ANNEX II. MONITORING AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF THE JOINT STRATEGY (ULPGC & UAC)

The Joint Strategy between the ULPGC and UAc was established to promote long-term collaboration in alignment with the objectives of the EXPER project. This strategy emerged from the Joint Strategy Workshop held on March 1, 2024, where key stakeholders from both institutions identified common strategic objectives and defined joint actions to enhance the institutional transformation of both HEIs.

This annex presents the monitoring and impact assessment of the Joint Strategy, focusing on the implementation progress of the defined joint actions and their associated KPIs. The following table provides a structured overview of these joint actions, including their strategic relevance and the outcomes of the key performance indicators (KPIs), their context and trend indication.

Table 58. Monitoring of the Joint Strategy Actions and KPIs

Actions	KPIs	Result	Additional details and comments
A.1. UAc joining a EUA	I.1. Creation of a forum to bring the interest ORs and share information, good practices and integrate new European Universities Alliances.	UAc joined EUA EUNICOAST in 2024	-
A.2. Implementing the CLAB model in Widening Universities	I.2. No. of UAc/ULPGC working groups participating in the CLAB model implementation at the ULPGC.	4	<p>A total of 4 student groups were created at ULPGC under the CLAB model:</p> <p>Canarias Retro – A student association aiming to reconnect young people with the Canary Islands' cultural heritage through photo recreations and interactive events.</p> <p>Gran Venture – An online platform offering personalised tourism experiences in Gran Canaria based on tourists' preferences and mobility needs.</p> <p>Safewotah – A water management service for hotels using IoT-based meters to monitor consumption, identify issues, and promote water-saving among guests.</p>

			ScanMyCity – A smart traffic system that optimises traffic light timing and prioritises emergency vehicles to reduce congestion and emissions.
A.3. Implementing the HRS4R at UAc & ULPGC	I.3. Best practices for the HRS4R certification procedure. Knowledge exchange with ULPGC	Catalogue of Good Practices for ULPGC (UNICAL)	A draft Catalogue of Good Practices for ULPGC was shared, serving as a key reference for the implementation process (See Annex III. Catalogue of Good Practices for ULPGC (HRS4R Strategy))
A.4. Encourage joint participation in collaborative projects that contribute to achieving SDGs and address the social challenges of the ORs.	I.4. No. of collaborative European projects proposals submitted with ULPGC.	14	1 (EIT HEI Biotech Venture Pathway), 13 (INTERREG MAC ReVeMAC, BIOBLUE4MAC, INTERTAGUA II, ADAPTATION, MARIAM, SAMMAR, NATUR-EXT, ACUICONECTA, CALYPSO, InnoVamos, TEXTIL, MICROCLI-MAC and ALSEMAC)
	I.5. Creation of a Working Group for identifying funding opportunities of on-going specific calls and topics of interest.	2 SCWGs	-
	I.6. Best practices workshop for writing projects proposals. Knowledge exchange with EXPER universities partners.	2 Summer Schools	Two Summer Schools were organised to enhance proposal writing and research management skills. The ULPGC Summer School (July 17–19, 2024) focused on open science, Horizon Europe proposal writing, and entrepreneurial innovation. The UAc Summer School (September 24–26, 2024) covered science communication, technology transfer, and Horizon Europe proposal writing, fostering

			collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society.
A.5. Improving the dissemination of research results between Universities (UAc/ULPGC) and entrepreneurial/business ecosystem in both regions.	I.7. No. of joint open days to disseminate research results developed at ULPGC and UAc close to the business sector (collaborative companies will explain their collaboration with the HEIs, ideally with the same departments).	3	Three dissemination activities were held: two online seminars (December 4, 2024 – UAc; January 9, 2025 – ULPGC) showcasing research on societal challenges and fostering new collaborations; and the ICEX Colloquium (February 22, 2024), where startups engaged with ICEX to explore international opportunities and strengthen business-research links.
A.6. Developing a joint summer-school.	I.8. No. of joint summer-schools organised.	2	-
A.7. Capacity building plan elaboration for UAc/ULPGC, including open science practices, research data management, scientific education, etc.	I.9. Capacity building plan report/deliverable	1	-
A.8. Promote the capacities and training of UAc/ULPGC staff in KTT and innovation.	I.10. No. of UAc/ULPGC staff participating in training schemes certified by Association of European Science and Technology Transfer Professionals (ASTP).	ULPGC: 0; UAc: 12	-

	I.11. No. of UAc/ULPGC staff with training in key skills for technology transfer (market analysis, IPR management, business models, grow hacking techniques, etc).	ULPGC: 24; UAc: 18	-
	I.12. No. of Staff exchanges within the project foreseen activities.	ULPGC: 3; UAc: 3	ULPGC: Staff exchange with UROS (1), UNICAL (1), and KIT, Germany (1); UAc: Staff exchange with UROS (1), ULPGC – Summer School (1), and TERINOV event (1)
A.9. Establishment of an OTC at the University of the Azores	I.13. Best practices workshop for OTC creation. Knowledge exchange with ULPGC.	UAc OTC (Knowledge Transfer and Valuation Center) was established in Dec/2023.	Numerous ULPGC contacts were made to exchange good practices and seek support in IPR management and other specific topics.
A.10. Promote informative-educational activities in primary and secondary schools in both ORs, with the aim of bringing research and science closer to the new generations and fostering their critical and creative thinking.	I.14. No. of Azores-Canaries primary/secondary schools involved in EXPER educational games.	14	-

A.11. Transversal actions	I.15. No. of incoming ULPGC mobility students from Erasmus + Eurodisseia and other programs.	ULPGC: 2034 (in 2022/2023 and 2023/2024) ³ UAc: 8 (in 2023/2024 academic year)	The indicator refers to the total number of incoming students at ULPGC through the Erasmus and SICUE programs for the academic years 2022/2023 and 2023/2024
	I.16. Continuing the ongoing joint PhD programs between UAc and ULPGC (namely on Atlantic islands: History, heritage, and legal-institutional framework).	Ongoing	-

³ [Data collected from ULPGC academic reports for the 2022/2023 and 2023/2024 academic year](#)

5.4. ANNEX III. CATALOGUE OF GOOD PRACTICES FOR ULPGC (HRS4R STRATEGY)

Excellent peripheries for a strong
European Research Area

Task 3.1
Implementing the HRS4R and improving
framework conditions

Catalogue of good practices for ULPGC

University of Calabria

Grant Agreement n°. 101071329

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The document is a part of D3.1 Good practices for the implementation of HRS4R and for researchers' careers.

Responsible	University of Calabria
Version	1 (15 July 2024)
Author(s)	Andrea Luca Attanasio, Stefania Chimenti, Francesca Principato

Catalogue of good practices for the implementation of HRS4R and for researchers' careers for ULPGC

From Action Plan HRS4R - ULPGC		From Action Plan HRS4R - UNICAL		
Action	Principles of European Charter & Code for Researchers	Action	Principles of European Charter & Code for Researchers	Good practices proposed
Acción 4. Diseñar un programa piloto de tutoría para apoyar el desarrollo de la carrera de los investigadores.	28. Career development 30. Access to research training and continuous development	Action 14. Encourage supervisors to follow their student's providing information about any possibility of working in the field of non-academic research and opportunities (European Job market).	8. Dissemination, exploitation of results 30. Access to career advice 39. Access to research training and continuous development	The UNICAL Placement service is designed to support graduates and young researchers (R1-R2) in their transition to the workforce, promoting career opportunities beyond academia. Various initiatives are implemented, notified via email to graduates and young researchers. For instance, matchmaking events with local companies by involving the Regional Association of firms (Confindustria Calabria), in order to promote industrial PhD programs and establish close partnerships to leverage research outcomes and assist PhD students in identifying job opportunities.
Acción 10. Mejorar la gestión de la investigación haciendo hincapié en	4. Professional attitude 9. Public Engagement	Action 5. Support the continuing professional development, by	27. Gender balance, 28. Career	1. Digital educational videos: "Language Resources for Academic Purposes" and "The use of Moodle for secure programming tests in laboratories, featuring coding tools and

la formación de los investigadores.	37. Supervision and managerial duties 40. Supervision	improving the quality of teaching	Development, 33. Teaching	automated corrections" 2. E-learning platform (https://elearning.unical.it/), the utilization of which will be further improved through the design and dissemination of a Vademecum. 3. Teaching methodology videos: "Interactive lectures and complex concepts" and "Tools for improving teaching methodologies and assessment tests for students with disabilities or specific learning disorders".
		Action 17. Strengthen the professionalism of R2 researchers by increasing their continuing professional development.	38. Continuing Professional Development	Support for R2 by covering the costs of training and preparatory actions (e.g. seminars on 'how to write a successful proposal'), with specialised technical assistance in connection with National Contact Points (e.g. the Agency for the Promotion of European Research (APRE, https://apre.it/en/homepage/) aimed at improving the success rate of applications.
		Action 30. Monitor the satisfaction of temporary researchers in the relationship with the supervisors through a dedicated survey.	31. Intellectual Property Rights 32. Co-authorship 36. Relation with supervisors	Anonymous survey dedicated to PhD students of a specific session on satisfaction with the relationship with one's supervisor.

<p>Medida 14. Promover medidas para atraer y retener el talento.</p>	<p>23. Research environment 24. Working conditions 33. Teaching 13. Recruitment (Code) (suggested by UNICAL)</p>	<p>Action 7. Encourage external candidates to apply by publishing a fact sheet of the call in English and the Rector's decree also in English.</p>	<p>13. Recruitment (Code)</p>	<p>Launch of calls to attract international researchers: the 'Chiara Fama' programme (with two calls open in 2022-2023) Regulations for the recruitment of researchers funded by ERC/MSCA Global Fellowships https://www.unical.it/ricerca/giovani-ricercatori/marie-sklodowska-curie-fellowships/"</p>
<p>Acción 16. Aplicar políticas de igualdad eficaces.</p>	<p>5. Contractual and legal obligations</p>	<p>Action 10. Ensure a balanced gender composition on committees in R1-R2 recruitment procedures.</p>	<p>14. Selection (Code) 27. Gender balance</p>	<p>Regulations for the Selection of: R1. The "Regulation on doctoral programmes" (https://www.unical.it/media/medias/2023/Phd_Regulations_RD_13-5-2022.pdf) extends the principle of gender-balanced composition in recruitment committees for R1 as follows "The Rector shall appoint the selection boards by decree for entry tests to PhD courses with administrative headquarters at the University upon proposal of the Boards of Lecturers, respecting gender balance, if applicable." R2 , see the Italian regulation, in particular Law 79/2022, which has brought about significant changes to post-doctoral recruitment and training. R3 and R.4. The regulations for the selection of R3-R4 already provide for the selection committee to be appointed according to the principle of gender balance, when the lack of</p>

				gender balance in some Sectors/Scientific Areas does not prevent this.
		Action 13. Organize more initiatives to stimulate debate and promote the importance of gender balance.	27. Gender balance	R2. R2 , see the Italian regulation, in particular Law 79/2022.
	7. Good practice in research	Action 20. Offer a training course on Gender language aimed at preventing gender-based violence, specifically addressing sexual harassment and any form of violation of personal dignity and freedom.	10. Non discrimination 27. Gender balance 38. Continuing Professional Development	R3 and R.4. The regulations for the selection of R3-R4 already provide for the selection committee to be appointed according to the principle of gender balance, when the lack of gender balance in some Sectors/Scientific Areas does not prevent this.
		Action 23. Define a more efficient communication strategy by implementing a dedicated online platform for Gender Equality, serving as a	10. Non discrimination 27. Gender balance	a) Gender Equality Plan, available at the link below: https://www.unical.it/media/m medias/2023/Gender_Equality_Plan.pdf b) Development of various initiatives to promote the GEP, coordinated by the Guarantee Committee and the Rector's delegate for Equal Opportunities, with particular focus on the areas identified as

		<p>hub to foster dialogue and promote initiatives outlined in the Gender Equality Plan (for more detail https://www.unical.it/media/medias/2024/GEP_Eng_summary.pdf)</p>	<p>critical by the first GEP monitoring focus group (2023): 1. leadership training; 2. harassment and gender-based violence (strengthening communication and dissemination of guarantee tools); 3. discrimination in STEM disciplines.</p> <p>c) Events open to the entire academic community:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Workshop "Tools for preventing and combating gender-based violence. The Unical experience", - Presentation of the book "Female Leadership. Does it really exist?" (by Valeria Santoro and Chiara Galgani), - Conference "MoviMenti. Women's knowledge and practices", - Workshop/laboratory "Countering gender discrimination in STEM. The actions of the University of Calabria", - Presentation of the book "Now it's our turn. Women, leadership and other misdeeds", - Workshop "Violence against women and tools to combat it: the Unical experience". <p>d) Production of 2 videos</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tools to combat harassment and gender-based violence (https://www.unical.it/contents/news/view/10195-lo-sportello-antiviolenza-unical-uno-spazio-sicuro-contro-molestie-e-
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				discriminazioni/); 2. Training and research activities on gender studies (https://www.instagram.com/reel/C4P3Ns_Lk2V/?igsh=MWw4czA5eXVnYmpzaw%3D%3D).
	27. Gender balance (suggested by UNICAL)	Action 26. Promote the role of Confidential Counsellor and all initiatives already implemented to intercept and manage cases of gender violence and harassment.	10. Non discrimination 27. Gender balance 34. Complaints and appeals	a) Training course (12 hours) on gender inclusive language for UNICAL staff b) To involve a wider audience of researchers, focus groups (2 hours) within departments to disseminate the guidelines on inclusive language. The initial evaluation of our GEP recommends expanding (up to 100 people) training to address sexual harassment/violence.
		Action 27. Promote the integration of a gender dimension into research content.	1. Research freedom 27. Gender balance	Publication of an annual university call for proposals for a prize for the best doctoral thesis that includes a gender dimension, aimed at PhD candidates.
Acción 17. Apoyar el desarrollo de la carrera científica de los jóvenes investigadores, formándolos para su	28. Career development 33. Teaching	Action 5. Support the continuing professional development, by improving the quality of teaching	27. Gender balance 28. Career Development 33. Teaching	see above

posterior acceso al cuerpo docente de la universidad.		Action 7. Encourage external candidates to apply by publishing a fact sheet of the call in English and the Rector's decree also in English.	13. Recruitment (Code)	see above
		Action 17. Strengthen the professionalism of R2 researchers by increasing their continuing professional development.	38. Continuing Professional Development	see above

References

Action Plan HRS4R of UNICAL https://www.unical.it/media/medias/2022/UNICAL_Action_Plan_T4_23-3-2022.pdf

Internal Review Action Plan 2024-2027 of UNICAL https://www.unical.it/media/medias/2024/HRS4R_Internal_Review_Action_Plan_2024-2027_UNICAL.pdf

Institutional webpage of HRS4R UNICAL <https://www.unical.it/ricerca/human-resources-strategy-for-researchers/?lang=en>

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5.5. ANNEX IV. SURVEYS CONDUCTED UNDER TASK 6.2

The following section presents the study conducted through surveys at ULPGC and UAc, aimed at gathering insights based on the KPIs established in D2.2. and D4.3. Each university independently designed its interviews, resulting in differences in the execution of the surveys. ULPGC developed multiple interviews tailored to different targets while maintaining some common questions across all versions. In contrast, UAc designed a single interview and distributed it to all target groups. These methodological differences reflect the distinct approaches taken by each institution while ensuring alignment with the overall task objective.

4.5.1. ULPGC SURVEYS

According to the indications of T6.2, three types of surveys were designed to target three groups (students, researchers, and University staff) and gather qualitative data to measure the impact of the action plans.

A fourth survey addressed to stakeholders was also designed and sent several times, but no response was received, so it will not be included in this qualitative analysis.

The surveys were designed based on the KPIs proposed in deliverables D2.2 and D4.2.

The participation is displayed in the following table:

Researcher survey	52 responses	Researchers survey link
Students	38 responses	Students survey link
University staff survey	163 responses	University staff survey link

The following are the resulting surveys for the different targets.

RESEARCHER SURVEY (52 RESPONSES)

K1.1. Increase in the participation of the university community in activities related to businesses and entrepreneurship. (Action Plans)

1. Have you participated in the last year in any activity that promotes the connection between universities and companies?
 - Yes 38%
 - No 62%
2. Do you think there are enough activities that promote the connection between universities and companies?
 - Yes 35%

- No 25%
- Don't know 40%

K1.2. Number of outreach programmes aimed at fostering an entrepreneurial culture in children.

3. Do you think that ULPGC dedicates enough effort (lectures, events, conferences, etc.) to promote entrepreneurship among children?. **(Action Plans)**

- Yes 46%
- No 23%
- Don't know 31%

K2.2. Number of PDI members trained in key skills for technology transfer. (Action Plans)

4. Do you think that the ULPGC offers enough support/resources to its PDI focused on improving their competences in knowledge transfer?

- Yes 40%
- No 37%
- Don't know 23%

K2.3. Percentage increase in the dissemination of the university's scientific results. (Action Plans)

5. Do you consider that the ULPGC provides sufficient means to develop activities for the dissemination of scientific results?

- Yes 53%
- No 33%
- Don't know 14%

6. Do you actively participate in activities to disseminate scientific results through conferences, publications or other channels?

- Yes 85%
- No 15%

7. Are you up to date / Do you receive notifications or news about the scientific results produced by the ULPGC?

- Yes 48%
- No 38%
- Don't know 13%

8. In relation to news, reports, results, etc., on ULPGC scientific research, which are the channels through which you receive most of this type of information? (k2.3 – SO)

- Social Media 10%
- Press 8%
- ULPGC web or affiliates 67%
- Scientific webs 8%
- Other 2%
- None 6%

K2.4. Number of projects involving external researchers. (Action Plans)

9. Do you consider the ULPGC an institution open to scientific collaboration with external researchers?

- Yes 79%
- No 12%
- Don't know 10%

Have you collaborated with researchers outside the ULPGC in recent years?

- Yes 92%
- No 8%

10. To what extent do you think that the involvement of external researchers enriches the scientific results?

- Greatly 58%
- Very much 33%
- Some 8%
- A Little 2%
- Nothing 0%

K3.1. Number of initiatives focused on social innovation. (Action Plans)

11. Do you think that the ULGC sufficiently supports projects aimed at the advancement of society in terms of innovation and welfare?

- Yes 35%
- No 25%
- Don't know 39%

K3.2. Percentage increase in participation in collaborative projects within the Blue Economy and Circular Economy sectors. (Action Plans)

12. How would you value being part of the consortium of a project focused on the blue and circular economy?

- Very positive 55%
- Indifferent 27%
- No value for me 18%

13. Do you think the ULPGC is really involved in the challenges posed by the blue and circular economy?

- Yes 44%
- No 6%
- Don't know 50%

K3.3. Number of candidates applying to human resources research calls. (Action Plans)

14. How would you evaluate the working conditions of the ULPGC job offers that request research personnel?

- Very good 4%
- Good 32%
- Regular 52%
- Bad 8%
- Very bad 4%

K3.4. Number of researchers hired from international institutions and organisations. (Action Plans)

15. Do you think that researchers are more interested in offering services to international institutions/organizations than to the ULPGC?

- Yes 35%
- No 16%
- Don't know 49%

K3.5. Percentage of hired researchers who secure a stable and permanent contract at ULPGC. (Action Plans)

16. How would you evaluate the stability of the ULPGC staff?

- Very good 6%
- Good 38%
- Regular 40%
- Bad 12%
- Very bad 4%

K4.1. Number of events organised on European university alliances in the Outermost Regions (ORs). (Action Plans)

17. How do you perceive the connection (exchanges, invitations to events, etc.) with other universities in outermost regions such as the Azores?

- Close, I believe that many activities are developed between both universities. 26%
- One-off relationship, I believe that more activities could be developed between the two universities. 56%
- Far away, I believe that not enough activities are developed between the two universities. 18%

18. Have you participated in the last year in any event related to European University Partnerships in the outermost regions?

- Yes 27%
- No 73%

K4.2. Number of project proposals submitted to European projects (European calls). (Action Plans)

19. Do you think that the ULPGC makes sufficient efforts to obtain funds from the European Commission for the development of projects?

- Yes 38%
- No 23%
- Don't know 38%

K6.2 Number of MSCA and ERC proposals evaluated and advised by the OPE. (Action Plans)

K1.1 Percentage of participants Reporting improved competence in Research Project Management. (OPE) (Capacity Building Plan)

20. During your career as a researcher/university staff, do you consider that thanks to the resources offered by the ULPGC, you have improved your skills in the management of research projects?

- Yes 44%
- No 42%
- Don't know 13%

K1.2 Percentage of successfully submitted proposals to European calls (OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

21. . Would you consider the ULPGC as a reference in obtaining European funding for the implementation of European projects?

- Yes 17%
- No 46%
- Don't know 37%

22. Regarding the approval of proposals for European calls for proposals by the ULPGC, how would you evaluate/perceive its success rate (calls requested/ calls granted)?

- Very good 8%
- Good 18%
- Regular 27%
- Bad 8%
- Very bad 4%
- Don't know 35%

K1.3 Number of Workshops Organized (VRRT, OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

23. Do you think that the ULPGC offers enough training workshops to improve skills in participation/coordination of European projects?

- Yes 60%
- No 17%
- Don't know 23%

K2.1 Number of events organized (VRRT, OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

24. Do you think that the scientific results of the ULPGC are connected to social needs?

- Yes 61%
- No 24%
- Don't know 16%

K2.2 Number of participating educational entities (schools, high schools, etc) (VRRT, OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

25. Do you think that the ULGC is an institution connected to schools and colleges?

- Yes 37%
- No 37%
- Don't know

K3.1 Number of training actions delivered (VRRT, VRTAE, OPE). (Action Plans)

K3.2 Number of attendants to the training actions delivered (VRRT, VRTAE, OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

26. Do you think that the ULPGC offers sufficient training/support to researchers on Open Science and Data Management?

- Yes 46%
- No 23%
- Don't know 31%

27. How would you rate the degree of involvement of ULPGC researchers in acquiring competences in Open Science and Data Management?

- Very high 8%
- High 16%
- Medium 54%
- Low 22%
- Very low 0%

K3.3 Percentage increase in the adoption of Open Science Practices and Data management. (VRRT, UAI) (Capacity Building Plan)

28. Do you think that, as a researcher, it is important to be competent in Open Science and Data management?

- Yes, it is very important 59%
- It is of average importance 39%
- No, it is not very important 2%

29. Do you consider the research community to be competent in open science and data management?

- Yes 28%
- No 65%
- Don't know 7%

K4.1 Social media outreach of the information campaign. (Capacity Building Plan)

30. Do you follow the social networks of the science and technology park foundation?

- Yes 19%

- No 81%

K6.1 Number of projects funded by HE programme. (Capacity Building Plan)

31. Do you consider the ULPGC European Project Office (EPO) a valuable resource for obtaining European funding from Horizon Europe?

- Yes 63%
- No 0%
- Don't know 37%

K6.2 Number of MSCA and ERC proposals evaluated and advised by the OPE. (Capacity Building Plan)

32. Do you think that the ULPGC and the European Project Office (EPO) is a valuable resource for the elaboration of proposals for Marie Skłodowska-Curie programmes and the publication of articles in the European Research Council?

- Yes 50%
- No 2%
- Don't know 48%

ANALYSIS AND CONCLUSION

The survey, reflecting the voices of ULPGC's researchers, illustrates a landscape of opportunity and growth. Although the connection between universities and businesses remains tenuous, with only 38% of participants engaging in such activities, there is optimism amongst the 35% who believe more initiatives could bridge this divide. The university's efforts to nurture young entrepreneurial minds are valued by 46%, but the next steps lie in enhancing these initiatives. Knowledge transfer and scientific dissemination demonstrate promising signs of progress, with 53% believing resources are adequate, yet awareness must expand further, as only 48% remain informed. External collaborations shine brightly, with 92% of researchers having partnered with individuals outside the university, showcasing the institution's welcoming approach to global partnerships. However, as the winds of change sweep through the realms of social innovation and the circular economy—where 44% feel the university's involvement is lacking—there remains a call for deeper engagement. The domain of open science and data management is at a crossroads, with 65% of researchers feeling less competent in these areas, awaiting greater focus and training. Ultimately, ULPGC's potential is immense, and with careful nurturing, these areas of growth will flourish into something transformative.

STUDENT SURVEY (38 RESPONSES)

K1.1. Increase in the participation of the university community in activities related to businesses and entrepreneurship. (Action Plans)

1. Have you participated in the last year in any activity that promotes the connection between universities and businesses?
 - Yes 21%
 - No 79%
2. Do you think that there are enough activities that promote the connection between universities and businesses?
 - Yes 8%
 - No 45%
 - Don't know 18%

K1.2. Number of outreach programmes aimed at fostering an entrepreneurial culture in children. (Action Plans)

3. Do you think that ULPGC dedicates enough effort (talks, events, conferences, etc.) to fostering an entrepreneurial spirit among children?
 - Yes 29%
 - No 26%
 - Don't know 17%

K2.3. Percentage increase in the dissemination of the university's scientific results. (Action Plans)

- Are you updated / Do you receive notifications or news about the scientific results produced by the ULPGC?
- Yes 39%
 - No 53%
 - Don't know 3%
5. In relation to news, reports, results, etc. about ULPGC scientific research, which are the channels through which you mostly receive this type of information?
 - Social networks 16%
 - Press 8%
 - Web ULPGC or affiliates 32%
 - Scientific websites 11%
 - Others 24%
 - None 11%

K3.1. Number of initiatives focused on social innovation. (Action Plans)

6. Do you think that the ULGC sufficiently supports projects aimed at the advancement of society in terms of innovation and welfare?

- Yes 29%
- No 24%
- Don't know 47%

7. Do you think that the ULPGC is really involved in the challenges of the blue and circular economy?

- Yes 53%
- No 13%
- Don't know 34%

K1.1 Percentage of participants Reporting improved competence in Research Project Management (OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

8. During your career as a researcher/staff/student at the university, do you consider that thanks to the resources offered by the ULPGC, you have improved your competences in research project management?

- Yes 32%
- No 55%
- Don't know 13%

K1.3 Number of Workshops Organized (VRRT, OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

9. Do you think that the ULPGC offers enough workshops to improve skills in participation / coordination of European projects?

- Yes 16%
- No 47%
- Don't know 37%

K2.1 Number of events organized (VRRT, OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

10. Do you think that the scientific results of the ULPGC are connected with social needs?

- Yes 45%
- No 16%
- Don't know 39%

K2.2 Number of participating educational entities (schools, high schools, etc) (VRRT, OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

11. Do you think that the ULGC is an institution connected with schools and high schools?

- Yes 24%
- No 47%
- Don't know 29%

12. Do you think that the ULPGC should increase its activities with schools and institutes with the aim of improving the business fabric and social welfare?

- Yes 84%
- No 3%
- Don't know 3%

K4.1 Social media outreach of the information campaign. (Capacity Building Plan)

13. Do you follow the social networks of the science and technology park foundation?

- Yes 42%
- No 58%

ANALYSIS AND CONCLUSION

The survey, conducted among ULPGC students, reveals areas where the university can improve its engagement and outreach. Only 21% of students have participated in activities that connect the university with businesses, and 79% have not, highlighting a significant gap in such initiatives. Furthermore, 45% of students feel there are insufficient activities promoting the connection between universities and businesses. In terms of entrepreneurship, 29% of students believe the university does enough to foster an entrepreneurial spirit in children, but there is still room to expand these efforts.

On scientific dissemination, 39% of students are updated on ULPGC's scientific results, while 53% are not, indicating that communication could be more effective. The majority of students (84%) agree that the university should increase its activities with schools and institutes to improve the business fabric and social welfare. However, only 24% see the university as connected to schools and high schools, pointing to a need for stronger partnerships with educational institutions.

Regarding social innovation and sustainability, 53% of students believe the university is involved in blue and circular economy challenges, but there is still uncertainty, as 34% don't know. Furthermore, only 16% feel that ULPGC offers enough workshops to improve skills in European project coordination, suggesting that more focused training opportunities are needed.

In conclusion, while students value the potential for greater involvement in entrepreneurship, scientific dissemination, and social innovation, there is a clear demand for increased efforts to foster stronger connections with schools, businesses, and the community, along with more opportunities for skill development and communication of research outcomes.

K1.1. Increase in the participation of the university community in activities related to businesses and entrepreneurship. (Action Plans)

1. Have you participated in the last year in any activity that promotes the connection between universities and businesses

- Yes 48%
- No 50%
- Don't know 25

2. Do you think that there are enough activities that promote the connection between universities and businesses?

- Yes 27%
- No 45%
- Don't know 28%

K1.2. Number of outreach programmes aimed at fostering an entrepreneurial culture in children. (Action Plans)

3. Do you think that ULPGC dedicates enough effort (talks, events, conferences, etc) to fostering an entrepreneurial culture among children?

- Yes 31%
- No 40%
- Don't know 29%

K2.1. Number of ULPGC staff with Registered Technology Transfer Professional (RTTP) certification. (Action Plans)

4. Do you think that the ULPGC offers sufficient support/resources to its staff in obtaining RTTP credits (Official Register of Technology Transfer Professionals)?

- Yes 11%
- No 27%
- Don't know 62%

K2.2. Number of PDI members trained in key skills for technology transfer. (Action Plans)

5. Do you think that the ULPGC offers enough support/resources to its teaching and research staff to improve skills for knowledge transfer?

- Yes 34%
- No 43%
- Don't know 23%

6. Are you up to date / Do you receive notifications or news about the scientific results produced by the ULPGC?

- Yes 60%
- No 40%

7. In relation to news, reports, results, etc. about ULPGC scientific research, which are the channels through which you receive most of this type of information?

- Social networks 14%
- Press 10%
- Web ULPGC or affiliates 50%
- Scientific websites 9%
- Others 9%
- None 9%

K3.1. Number of initiatives focused on social innovation. (Action Plans)

8. Do you think that the ULGC sufficiently supports projects aimed at the advancement of society in terms of innovation and welfare?

- Yes 32%
- No 35%
- Don't know 33%

K3.2. Percentage increase in participation in collaborative projects within the Blue Economy and Circular Economy sectors. (Action Plans)

9. How would you rate being part of the consortium of a project focused on the blue and circular economy?

- Positive 70%
- Indifferent 14%
- No value for me 16%

10. Do you think the ULPGC is really involved in the challenges posed by the blue and circular economy?

- Yes 38%
- No 16%
- Don't know 46%

K3.5. Percentage of hired researchers who secure a stable and permanent contract at ULPGC. (Action Plans)

11. How would you rate the stability of ULPGC staff?

- Very good 9%
- Good 34%
- Fair 31%

- Bad 14%
- Very bad 12%

K4.1. Number of events organised on European university alliances in the Outermost Regions (ORs). (Action Plans)

12. How do you perceive the connection (exchanges, invitation to events, etc.) with other universities in outermost regions such as the Azores?

- Close, I think that many activities are developed between both universities. 17%
- Occasional relationship, I think that more activities could be developed between both universities. 57%
- Distant, I think that not enough activities are developed between the two universities. 26%

13. Have you participated in the last year in any event related to European University Partnerships in the outermost regions?

- Yes 22%
- No 78%

K4.2. Number of project proposals submitted to European projects (European calls). (Action Plans)

14. Do you think that the ULPGC dedicates enough efforts to obtain funds from the European Commission for the development of projects?

- Yes 22%
- No 32%
- Don't know 46%

K1.1 Percentage of participants Reporting improved competence in Research Project Management (OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

15. During your career as a researcher/university staff, do you consider that thanks to the resources offered by the ULPGC, you have improved your competence in research project management?

- Yes 35%
- No 55%
- Don't know 10%

K1.2 Percentage of successfully submitted proposals to European calls (OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

16. Regarding the approval of proposals to European calls by the ULPGC, how would you rate/perceive its success rate (calls requested/ calls granted)?

- Very good 3%
- Good 17%

- Intermediate 30%
- Poor 9%
- Very bad 4%
- Don't know 38%

K1.3 Number of Workshops Organized (VRRT, OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

17. Do you think that the ULPGC offers enough workshops to improve skills in participation / coordination of European projects?

- Yes 34%
- No 39%
- Don't know 28%

K2.1 Number of events organized (VRRT, OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

18. Do you think that the scientific results of the ULPGC are connected with social needs?

- Yes 46%
- No 27%
- Don't know 28%

K2.2 Number of participating educational entities (schools, high schools, etc) (VRRT, OPE). (Capacity Building Plan)

19. Do you think that the ULGC is an institution connected with schools and high schools?

- Yes 35%
- No 44%
- Don't know 21%

K4.1 Social media outreach of the information campaign. (Capacity Building Plan)

20. Do you follow the social networks of the Science and Technology Park Foundation?

- Yes 34%
- No 54 %
- Don't have social networks 12%

K5.2 Number of training courses or workshops conducted for CIDE network technicians on R&D transfer from research organizations. (Capacity Building Plan)

21. Do you think that the ULPGC offers/supports sufficient training (courses, workshops, seminars) to the technicians of the knowledge transfer office (OTC)?

- Yes 18%

- No 20%
- Don't know 62%

22. Do you think that the ULPGC European Projects Office is active in obtaining European funds for the development of research projects?

- Yes 34%
- No 19%
- Don't know 47%

K6.2 Number of MSCA and ERC proposals evaluated and advised by the OPE. (Capacity Building Plan)

23. Do you think that the ULPGC and the European Project Office (EPO) are a valuable resource in the development of proposals for Marie Skłodowska-Curie programmes and the publication of articles in the European Research Council?

- Yes 37%
- No 10%
- Don't know 53%

ANALYSIS AND CONCLUSION

The University Staff Survey presents a nuanced view of the staff's perception of the university's activities and support systems. A notable conclusion is the mixed involvement in activities that connect universities with businesses, with only 48% of respondents having participated in such initiatives. This suggests that while efforts are made, the reach or appeal of these programs may need to be expanded to ensure greater engagement. Furthermore, there is a significant gap in the perceived sufficiency of these activities, with 45% of respondents believing that there are not enough initiatives to foster this crucial connection.

Another key area is the fostering of an entrepreneurial culture in children, where only 31% of respondents feel the university is dedicating enough effort. This indicates that the university may need to reassess its outreach programs to ensure that they are effectively targeting younger audiences and fostering entrepreneurship from an early stage. Similarly, staff members expressed uncertainty regarding support for technology transfer, with 62% unsure whether the university offers enough resources for obtaining certification in this area. This highlights a possible communication gap or a need for more transparent resources and guidance.

Despite these gaps, there are some positive trends. 60% of staff reported staying updated on scientific results from the university, primarily through the university's website. This suggests that the university is somewhat successful in disseminating its scientific output, but the low percentages following other channels (such as social media or press) suggest a need for a more diversified communication strategy.

Regarding European projects, the survey reveals a positive view of the university's involvement in Blue and Circular Economy projects, with 70% of staff viewing participation as beneficial. However, only 22% think the university is putting enough effort into securing European funding, indicating a potential underutilization of available resources or perhaps a mismatch between staff expectations and the university's actual efforts in this area.

The survey also highlights concerns about staff stability, with 31% rating it as fair and 26% seeing it as unstable. This points to potential issues in staff retention and job security, which could affect morale and long-term commitment to the university's goals.

In conclusion, while the UPLGC is making strides in several areas, there is a clear need for improved communication, increased participation in key initiatives, and greater clarity and support regarding the university's offerings, particularly in areas of knowledge transfer, European project funding, and entrepreneurial outreach. Engaging staff more effectively in these areas and addressing concerns related to support, visibility, and stability could enhance both the internal experience of staff and the university's broader impact.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AMONG TARGETS

Comparing the three surveys (students, researchers, and staff), key trends emerge. Across all groups, participation in activities connecting the university with businesses was low, with 48% of staff, 21% of students, and 50% of researchers reporting involvement. A significant portion of all groups—45% of staff, 45% of students, and 47% of researchers—felt that more activities were needed in this area.

Regarding fostering an entrepreneurial culture among children, 40% of staff and 26% of researchers felt insufficient effort was made, while students were more optimistic (29%). Communication about scientific results varied, with 60% of staff and 39% of students staying informed, but only 53% of researchers did, suggesting room for improvement in updates for researchers.

There was a common sentiment across all groups that more workshops and resources were needed for skill development in knowledge transfer and European project coordination, with 43% of staff, 47% of researchers, and 47% of students feeling these resources were lacking. Lastly, staff expressed concerns about stability, with 31% rating it as fair or poor, while students and researchers showed less focus on this issue.

Overall, the surveys reveal a need for improved communication, more support for entrepreneurial initiatives, better skill-building opportunities, and a focus on staff stability to increase engagement and satisfaction across the university community.

4.5.2. UAC SURVEYS

In order to monitor the implementation of the UAc's Action Plan (AP) and UAc's Capacity Building Plan (CBP) and assess their impact, as indicated in the T6.2, UAc also conducted an internal qualitative survey, targeting the 9 applicable responsible departments for measuring each of the UAc Actions Plans (AP) and Capacity Building Plan (CBP) KPIs and outcomes (as described in the "D2.2 Action Plans developed" and "D4.2 Capacity Building Plan and report on capacity building activities"), namely the Vice-Rectorate for Science, Innovation and Knowledge Transfer (VReCITC), Vice-Rectorate for Education and Academic Affairs (VReEGA), Vice-Rectorate for Administration, Planning and Infrastructures (VReAPI), Vice-Rectorate for Students, Well-being and Institutional Communication (VReEBECI), Pro-Rectorate for Cooperation, Internationalisation and Distance Learning (ProCIED), Pro-Rectorate for Quality and Pedagogical Innovation (ProQIP), as well as the Academic Association (AAUA), Technology-based Incubator (InUAc) and the Science and Technology Service (SVCT) departments.

The surveys were designed based on the indicators proposed in the UAc's Action Plan (AP) and UAc's Capacity Building Plan (CBP) and their results can be found below.

QUESTIONS BASED ON THE ACTIONS AND KPIS FROM THE ACTION PLAN (AP) STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES

Strategic Objective 1: Foster applied research, interdisciplinarity and internationalization

K1.1. No. of project proposals submitted to European funded calls, namely Horizon Europe and Interreg funding programs / K1.2. No. of projects in the Information Platform for external funded projects / K1.5. No. of European University Alliances (EUAs) proposals submitted

1. Do you consider that the UAc Science and Technology Service (SVCT) is a valuable resource for attracting European funding, in particular for the Horizon Europe programme.

- Yes 88,9%
- No 0%
- I don't know 11,1%

K1.1. No. of project proposals submitted to European funded calls, namely Horizon Europe and Interreg funding programs / K1.5. No. of European University Alliances (EUAs) proposals submitted

2. Do you think that the UAc makes the necessary efforts to attract funding for European projects?

- Yes 55,6%
- No 33,3%
- I don't know 11,1%

K1.4. No. of researchers involved in the societal challenges working groups

3. Do you think UAc is really involved in responding to the societal challenges posed by the blue and circular economy?

- Yes 55,6%
- No 11,1%
- I don't know 33,3%

K1.1. No. of project proposals submitted to European funded calls, namely Horizon Europe and Interreg funding programs. / K1.4. No. of researchers involved in the societal challenges working groups

4. Do you consider UAc an institution open to scientific collaboration with external researchers?

- Yes 88,9%
- No 0%
- I don't know 11,1%

K1.4. No. of researchers involved in the societal challenges working groups / K1.6. No. of scientific articles indexed in the international Web of Science database

5. To what extent do you consider that involvement with external researchers enriches scientific results?

- Greatly 55,6%
- Very much 44,4%
- Some 0%
- A little 0%
- Nothing 0%

Strategic Objective 2: Promote a culture of innovation and technology transfer

K2.1. No. of UAc staff participating in training schemes certified by Association of European Science and Technology Transfer Professionals (ASTP) / K2.2. No. of UAc staff with training in key skills for technology transfer (market analysis, IPR management, business models, grow hacking techniques, etc)

1. Do you think that UAc offers sufficient support/resources to its employees (teachers/researchers/TTO staff) in regard of improving their skills in knowledge transfer?

- Yes 22,2%
- No 44,4%
- I don't know 33,3%

K2.2. No. of UAc staff with training in key skills for technology transfer (market analysis, IPR management, business models, grow hacking techniques, etc) / K2.3. Implementation of the Technology Transfer Office (TTO) within InUAc department

2. Do you think there are enough initiatives that promote the connection between the university and the business sector?

- Very good 0%
- Good 22,2%
- Reasonable 66,7%
- Bad 11,1%
- Very bad 0%

K2.2. No. of UAc staff with training in key skills for technology transfer (market analysis, IPR management, business models, grow hacking techniques, etc) / K2.3. Implementation of the Technology Transfer Office (TTO) within InUAc department

3. Do you think that UAc dedicates enough efforts (lectures, events, workshops, etc.) to promote the entrepreneurial spirit among its students?

- Yes 44,4%
- No 33,3%
- I don't know 22,2%

Strategic Objective 3: Invest in a people-centric University

K3.4. No. of consultations promoting the entire academic community well-being, through UAc's Health Office / K3.5. No. of participants from the academic community in sports, maintenance or leisure activities promoted by UAc

1. To what extent do you think the UAc has the necessary mechanisms to sufficiently support the academic community in terms of health and well-being?

- Very good 0%
- Good 55,6%
- Reasonable 33,3%
- Bad 0%
- Very bad 11,1%

K3.1. Review and approve the teaching staff performance evaluation regulation

2. How do you value the current teaching evaluation system at UAc?

- Very good 0%
- Good 22,2%

- Reasonable 77,8%
- Bad 0%
- Very bad 0%

K3.1. Review and approve the teaching staff performance evaluation regulation / K3.3. Submit a HRS4R application in 2025

3. How do you evaluate the working conditions, career development and incentives available in the recruitment of researchers at UAc?

- Very good 0%
- Good 33,3%
- Reasonable 55,6%
- Bad 11,1%
- Very bad 0%

K3.7. No. of infrastructures modernization or creation.

4. How do you assess whether the current infrastructure of university campuses (buildings, equipment, furniture, Wi-Fi networks, etc.) is adequate?

- Very good 0%
- Good 44,4%
- Reasonable 44,4%
- Bad 11,1%
- Very bad 0%

Strategic Objective 4: Stimulate cooperation, external communication and social connection

1. Do you consider that the UAc carries out the necessary dissemination of its scientific results?

- Yes 11,1%
- No 77,8%
- I don't know 11,1%

K4.1. No. of collaborative projects initiated with regional actors

2. To what extent do you consider that the UAc is sufficiently involved in projects and initiatives with other actors/stakeholders from the regional ecosystem?

- Very good 0%
- Good 33,3%
- Reasonable 66,7%

- Bad 0%
- Very bad 0%

K4.4. No. of incoming/outcoming mobility students from Erasmus+, Eurodisseia and other programs / K4.5. No. of incoming/outcoming staff mobility.

3. How do you perceive the current mobility initiatives (staff/students) with other European universities?

- Very important 44,4%
- Important 55,6%
- Reasonable 0%
- Without importance 0%

K4.6. No. of primary/secondary schools involved in educational games.

4. How do you value the connection between UAc and the student community, particularly with primary and secondary schools, as well as the dissemination of research results and awareness of citizen science among these institutions?

- Very good 44,4%
- Good 44,4%
- Reasonable 0%
- Bad 11,1%
- Very bad 0%

QUESTIONS BASED ON THE ACTIONS AND KPIS FROM THE CAPACITY BUILDING PLAN (CBP) STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES

Objective 1: Promote transversal skills for excellence in research

K1.1 Number of participants attending the trainings on European project writing and Science Communication / K1.3 Number of Trainings Organized

1. Do you consider UAc offers enough training workshops to improve European project participation/coordination skills?

- Yes 11,1%
- No 77,8%
- I don't know 11,1%

K1.3 Number of Trainings Organized / K1.4 Number of participants attending the trainings on Open Science good practices

2. Do you consider that the academic research community (professors/researchers) has the necessary skills in Open Science and Data Management?

- Yes 22,2%
- No 55,6%
- I don't know 22,2%

K1.1 Number of participants attending the trainings on European project writing and Science Communication / K1.3 Number of Trainings Organized

3. Do you consider that the academic research community (professors/researchers) has the necessary skills in terms of Scientific Communication and dissemination of Scientific Research results?

- Yes 33,3%
- No 55,6%
- I don't know 11,1%

K1.2 Number of submitted proposals to European calls

4. Regarding the approval of applications for European projects by the UAc, how do you evaluate/perceive its success rate (number of applications vs. approvals)?

- Very good 0%
- Good 55,6%
- Reasonable 44,4%
- Bad 0%
- Very bad 0%

Objective 2: Strengthen KTT and Innovation

K2.1 Number of UAc staff with training in key skills for technology transfer / K2.2 Number of KTT promoted training events

1. How do you evaluate the UAc's offering in relation to training actions for its professors/researchers (courses, workshops, seminars) focused on knowledge transfer, creation of startups/spinoffs, business model and industrial property management?

- Very good 0%
- Good 44,4%
- Reasonable 44,4%
- Bad 11,1%
- Very bad 0%

K2.1 Number of UAc staff with training in key skills for technology transfer / K2.2 Number of KTT promoted training events

2. Do you consider that UAc offers sufficient training actions (courses, workshops, seminars) for its knowledge transfer support office employees - TTO (Knowledge Transfer and Valorization Centre)?

- Yes 44,4%
- No 22,2%
- I don't know 33,3%

CBP Objective 4: Stakeholders engagement and Internationalization

K4.1 Number of external partners trained

1. Do you think UAc promotes sufficient training actions (courses, workshops, seminars) open to the quadruple helix (academia, public sector, companies and civil society)?

- Yes 33,3%
- No 33,3%
- I don't know 33,3%

K4.2 Number of active UAc networks / K4.3 Number of active collaborative protocols

2. How do you value the importance of current collaboration protocols and networks participation in which UAc is currently involved?

- Very important 66,7%
- Important 11,1%
- Reasonable 22,2%
- Without importance 0%

K4.4 Number of European University Alliances participation

3. How do you consider the recent integration of UAc in a European University Alliance (EUNICOAST), from the point of view of cooperation in education, research and innovation, entrepreneurship and responding to societal and environmental challenges?

- Very important 88,9%
- Important 0%
- Reasonable 11,1%
- Without importance 0%

SURVEY ANALYSIS

The survey covered various aspects of the University of the Azores (UAc), including European funding and project capabilities, collaboration with external researchers, support for knowledge transfer and entrepreneurship, working conditions and infrastructures, training and professional development, involvement with the regional ecosystem and institutional support.

Most of the respondents agree that the Science and Technology Service department (SVCT) is widely recognized as a valuable resource for securing European funding, indicating a strong institutional foundation for research funding. (e.g., Horizon Europe). However, there is mixed feedback on whether UAc makes sufficient efforts to obtain European project funding. The majority believe UAc demonstrates a strong culture of openness to external collaboration, with near-unanimous agreement that such collaborations significantly enhance research outcomes. However, engagement in societal challenges (e.g., blue and circular economy) is seen as inconsistent.

From a training and knowledge transfer standpoint, several respondents feel that UAc does not provide enough resources to improve knowledge transfer skills among faculty, researchers, and staff. There's clearly also a lack of sufficient initiatives to connect the university to the businesses sector and training opportunities for participation in European projects are perceived as insufficient. There's also concerns about whether researchers have adequate transversal competencies like open science or data management, and even science communication since the majority feel that UAc does not adequately disseminate its scientific results.

On the entrepreneurship and innovation side, there is a divide on whether UAc promotes an entrepreneurial spirit among students through events and workshops. Many respondents feel UAc does not sufficiently support training for startup creation, intellectual property management, or business models and the university's efforts to connect with the business sector and support entrepreneurship are perceived as lacking.

Work Environment and infrastructure wise, responses indicate room for improvement in work conditions, career development, and faculty evaluation methods. The infrastructure (buildings, Wi-Fi, and equipment) receives mixed ratings, ranging from "Bad" to "Good", with most recognizing at "Reasonable" or " Good".

UAc's engagement with society and involvement with schools and the broader community is rated positively by most of the respondents, indicating effective educational pipeline development. However, there are concerns whether UAc promote sufficient training actions open to the quadruple helix of society (academia, public sector, businesses, and civil society).

As for UAc strategic international positioning and cooperation, the recent integration in the European University Alliance EUNICOAST is viewed very positively by most departments, suggesting recognition of the strategic importance of international partnerships.

AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT

The survey results suggest UAc has established a good foundation in international collaboration and research capacity but needs to focus on some areas to maximize its impact, mainly:

- **European Research Funding:** As some concerns have been raised whether enough efforts to obtain funding opportunities are being made, a dedicated support program in proposal writing as well as increasing the availability of workshops for European project participation/coordination should be prioritized.
- **Knowledge Transfer:** A significant majority of respondents identify insufficient support for knowledge transfer competencies, suggesting a disconnect between research capabilities and practical applications. Offering regular workshops and improving knowledge transfer training for TTO staff, as well as expanding entrepreneurship programs and providing mentorship and funding opportunities for students interested in launching startups, can benefit the institution.
- **Transversal Research Skills:** There are substantial perceived weaknesses in both Project Management/Coordination, Open Science/Data Management capabilities and Science Communication skills among the academic community, which may be limiting the visibility and impact of research, so regular trainings/workshop in the thematic fields should be encouraged.
- **Scientific Dissemination:** The widespread perception that UAc inadequately disseminates its scientific results points to a critical communications issue that may be hampering institutional recognition and impact. Developing stronger outreach initiatives to share research findings with the general public, strengthen partnerships with schools to promote citizen science projects and leverage social media and digital platforms to showcase UAc's research contributions should be discussed within VReEBECI.
- **Quadruple Helix Engagement:** Insufficient engagement with the broader society (academia, public sector, industry, and civil society) suggests UAc may be operating in relative isolation from key stakeholders. Developing public informative and training sessions, structuring partnerships with industry to encourage collaborative research, organizing Academia-Industry networking events, and being more involved in policy-making decisions is crucial to be perceived as an Institution opened to the society, decisive in the social, economic and cultural development of its region.

CONCLUSION

While UAc has a strong foundation in research collaboration and European networking, there is a clear need to improve institutional support for funding acquisition, training, industry engagement, and infrastructure. By addressing these gaps, the university can enhance its competitiveness and impact within the regional and international academic ecosystem.

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